

**A STUDY OF THE PROSPECTS IN THE YOUTH
ENTREPRENEURSHIP SECTOR IN ALGERIA**

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Abstract

The study builds on the conceptual and applied insights on the potential that young people might be particularly well equipped to drive Algeria's economy forward. The study confers the core barriers (venture capital, foreign direct investment, bureaucratic obstacles, gender discrimination, and soft skills) to entrepreneurship in Algeria. Furthermore, the study assessed the different economic forces in Algeria that appear to be promoting or sustaining entrepreneurship, particularly among young people. These forces tend to be connected to a broader possibility of economic development. This study adopted an empirical debate, where all the findings were based on the data collected from the participants, with practical and theoretical applications.

The overarching aim of the study was to investigate how to engage youth in small business entrepreneurship across Algeria and how to connect the development of entrepreneurship and the overall development of the Algerian economy in the post-oil landscape. There were four research objectives in this study: a) to assess the general economic and youth unemployment situation in Algeria, including its socio-economic impact; b) to identify and discuss the barriers to youth entrepreneurship/business start-ups; c) to evaluate the overall impact of government actions and programs on youth entrepreneurship; and d) to identify key prescriptions for the sustainability of development initiatives for youth entrepreneurship.

The study uses mixed methods, both quantitative and qualitative research approaches. The quantitative survey collected data from four hundred and thirty-three (433) young Algerian entrepreneurs some of them at the planning stage to start their own business. The qualitative study involved interviews with ten senior public sector respondents and ten established, experienced Algerian active entrepreneurs who compose the population of key informant interviewees in the research process. The quantitative and qualitative evidence from these different groups underpins key prescriptions on how youth entrepreneurship can be developed and sustained in the Algerian economy.

There are several theoretical and practical contributions to this research. This study helped to address a gap in the young population of entrepreneurs in Algeria and opened an avenue for future researchers to build on. This study also offered practical contributions. Government officials can use findings from this study to develop better-informed policies for promoting entrepreneurship in the country. This study also helped to start a potential social change in Algeria, where a new perspective can be developed to encourage the government to prioritise young people in its economic development. Moreover, a potential shift within the society could occur where more young people will feel understood, and their needs will be addressed. As a result, more of them would start business ventures in the country and become less dependent on the government for work.

It is overwhelmingly evident that young entrepreneurs have a remarkable amount of desire to pursue their business dreams. That can only be understood as a positive thing for the future of economic development in Algeria.

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I would like to dedicate my thesis to my family, including my mother, my wife, and my children especially to my late father. Without their support I would not have reached what I am now.

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CHAPTER ONE -INTRODUCTION

1.1 RESEARCH BACKGROUND AND STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

There have been several studies done on entrepreneurship in Algeria, however, only a few have focused on youth entrepreneurship. Some studies have focused on exploring the attitudes toward female entrepreneurship in Algeria (Benhabib et al., 2014; Salamzadeh et al., 2022), which provided some context into the entrepreneurship scene in the country. Moreover, other studies focus on exploring the business environmental factors that could affect small to medium-sized enterprises from starting in Algeria, including the legal and regulatory framework in the country, poor access to financing, and shortage of resources (Bouazza, 2015; Chohra, 2019). A study by Mohammed et al. (2017) focused on exploring the attitudes and behavioral intentions of Algerian students toward entrepreneurship. However, this study did not explore the barriers experienced by these students when setting up an entrepreneurial venture and did not explore the link between their attitudes and the external factors in Algeria. The current study will aim to close that gap as well as evaluate the effectiveness of existing government programs in promoting more youth entrepreneurship in the country.

It is important to offer a country context to better understand the entrepreneurial scene in Algeria. Algeria is the largest country in Africa, which experiences high levels of corruption, inequality, slow economic growth, double-digit national and youth unemployment, and continued poverty (Ahmed, 2018; Mehdi Abid et al., 2023; World Bank, 2016). Total unemployment sits at approximately 12% of the active population, while youth unemployment (i.e. aged under 30 years) sits at 29% (Constable, 2019; Focus Economics, 2019).

Figure 1.1: Average unemployment rate for people under 24 years old in North Africa 2010-2018 %

Source: International Labour Organisation 2020

The youth of Algeria, which account for two-thirds (70%) of the country's total population of 43.85 million, represent a total of 72% of all unemployed in the country (Mehdi Abid et al., 2023; Rarrbo, 2009). Due to poor economic opportunities and rising unemployment, the Algerian youth tend to enter small business start-ups and social enterprises to leverage creative solutions against unemployment and adverse economic climate and pursue a more sustainable means of survival and competitiveness (Jebari, 2016). However, it is still unknown exactly what opportunities and barriers the youth entrepreneurs face in Algeria, their attitudes toward entrepreneurship in Algeria, the benefits that come from setting up an entrepreneurial venture as a young person, and the effectiveness of government programs in promoting greater youth entrepreneurial activity in the country.

1.2 AIM AND OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This study aims to explore the benefits, attitudes, and barriers that are associated with youth entrepreneurship in Algeria. Moreover, this dissertation aims to explore the benefits of major government entrepreneurial interventions and programs in promoting youth entrepreneurship and economic development in Algeria.

In the context of the problem and the key questions, the conduct of the study will be guided by the following research objectives:

1. To explore the general economic and youth unemployment situation in Algeria and the benefits of youth entrepreneurship in the Algerian context through exploring existing literature and conducting desk research.
2. To identify and discuss the barriers and attitudes of young entrepreneurs based in Algeria.
3. To evaluate the overall impact of government actions and programs on youth entrepreneurship based on the effectiveness of these programs in promoting more entrepreneurship in Algeria.
4. To identify key prescriptions for the sustainability of development initiatives on youth entrepreneurship in Algeria based on the findings from this study.

1.3 STRUCTURE OF THE THESIS

1.3.1 Theoretical Framework

The two theories guiding the current research are the opportunity-based theory by Peter Drucker and the impact analysis theory (IAT) advocated by Murphy and Marvel (2008), Lenjo (2015), and Dontigney (2018).

Drucker's opportunity-based theory focuses on seven main sources of innovative opportunities that need to be present to promote entrepreneurial ventures (Dontigney, 2018). These include the unexpected (an event where an entrepreneurial opportunity arises), the incongruity (assumptions about the reality vs the reality), innovation based on process need (identifying a weak link in the process), changes in the industry or the market, demographic changes, changes in attitudes, perceptions, and meaning, and new knowledge. Essentially, this theory posits that entrepreneurship arises as a response to a stimulus (such as the economic, social, or political situation in Algeria) that generates a response where an entrepreneurial venture is pursued.

The impact analysis theory is a paradigm that deconstructs the cause-and-effect relationship between a phenomenon (i.e. youth entrepreneurship) and an intervention that helps to reap the desired effects (that is, greater youth entrepreneurship in Algeria). This theory will be applied in the current study, where the effectiveness of various government interventions and programs will be assessed in promoting youth entrepreneurship in Algeria.

1.3.2 Significance of the Study

The study introduces three original contributions to the literature on youth entrepreneurship in Algeria. First, this study will focus specifically on the barriers experienced by youth entrepreneurs in Algeria, a group that has not been thoroughly explored by past researchers, except for a few studies. This knowledge is important as youth make up a significant majority

of Algeria's working population, and knowledge of the challenges they experience when setting up business ventures is important to promote greater economic activity in the country. Moreover, this study will assess the impact of specific government actions and programs on youth entrepreneurship, which was not previously done by researchers. Assessing these interventions against the barriers and attitudes of youth entrepreneurs in Algeria will help to provide a more accurate representation of the youth entrepreneurship scene in the country. Last, this study will explore the economic, social, and political situation in Algeria in the context of youth entrepreneurship. While economic, social, and political factors in Algeria have previously been studied, these have not been explored in the context of youth entrepreneurship. This is an important contribution, as it will help to highlight the environmental factors that inhibit/promote youth entrepreneurial activity in the country.

1.3.3 Literature Review

Algeria has experienced major socioeconomic and political dysfunctions that continue to lead to a series of problems such as failed governance, corruption, sluggish economic performance, high unemployment, and poverty (Ahmed, 2018; Mehdi Abid et al., 2023; World Bank, 2016). Although naturally rich in oil-based resources, the Algerian government has been unable to use its resources for economic development, with many Algerians still living under the poverty line (Crisis Group, 2019; Rarrbo, 2009). As previous studies have indicated, youth unemployment in Algeria sits at a high rate of 29%, while the unemployment rate is at 12% (Constable, 2019; Focus Economics, 2019). Moreover, approximately 270,000 educated Algerian workers have left the country since the 1990s to seek a better future, which highlights the scale of the economic hardships in the country (World Bank, 2016). Due to the difficulty of entry into the labor force and the absence of a sufficient national policy or strategy to tackle youth employment, many young Algerians tend to go for the entrepreneurial path as a way of economic survival in the country. Many young Algerians take on new entrepreneurship ventures, even with limited government intervention or assistance (Jebari, 2016; Kabbani, 2019). As Jebari (2016, p.1) succinctly stated:

“A new generation of cinema producers and other cultural actors from Algeria's underground scene continue to portray today's youth as energetic and optimistic despite lagging structures and a stifling atmosphere...Similarly, social entrepreneurship has emerged from this challenging context as a practice of resilience and creativity.”

The Algerian government has no central strategy or policy that promotes youth entrepreneurship and helps to reduce youth unemployment (Looney, 2016). The Algerian government pacifies its militant and restive population with subsidies, government jobs, and public sector compensation increases, but the country remains weak in “rule of law, control of corruption, government effectiveness, and regulatory quality — all areas critical to successful economic development” (Looney, 2016, p.1). Algeria’s small-medium enterprises (SMEs) have been considered too fragile and weak that they are unable to promote any significant economic contribution to the country (Bouazza, 2015). Thus, in Algeria, there is a greater emphasis on promoting private and public sector jobs as opposed to promoting entrepreneurial activity in the country. There is little information about the impact generated by the Algerian government’s actions and programs on youth entrepreneurship and its impact on economic growth.

Based on Algerian political and socio-economic problems, youth entrepreneurship can help to promote immense benefits due to its ability to build competitive skills; increase job creation; reduce socioeconomic stress due to youth employability; create organizational competence; develop a global mindset; promote self-reliance, competitiveness, productivity, leadership, and teamwork among the youth; and foster economic transition (Boufeldja, 2014; 2017; Bourouaha et al., 2014; Jebari, 2016; Kew et al., 2013; Momani, 2017; World Learning, 2019). Moreover, 83% of the Algerian youth believe that “starting a business is a good career choice” (Momani, 2017, p.1). This is a general indication of a highly positive attitude toward entrepreneurship of the Algerian youth, with many business start-ups being engaged in web-based or online businesses, including e-commerce (D’Ignoti, 2017; Hoxha, 2015). Moreover, amid governmental shortcomings, there is a growing interest in new technology among young Algerian entrepreneurs, who are keen to use their IT skills in seeking new technological solutions in the country (Hoxha, 2015). Thus, there appears to be a positive attitude and interest toward entrepreneurship in the country, which is associated with multiple economic and social benefits for the country.

Nonetheless, despite a broad range of benefits, youth entrepreneurship in Algeria is faced with major barriers and challenges. Youth entrepreneurship in Algeria reckons with “an administered economy with heavy bureaucracy, an inefficient banking system, a total absence of venture capital, a lack of entrepreneurial culture based on risk and a lack of startup champions” (Global Entrepreneurship Network, 2015, p.1). Engaging in business start-ups in

Algeria involves going through regulatory obstacles, nepotism, and gender discrimination; building enormous soft and functional skills; and the requirement to learn English and French languages (World Learning, 2019). Youth entrepreneurship engagement also requires overcoming an ineffective and non-democratic political regime that remains non-aligned with what society and the labor force need (Constable, 2019; Jebari, 2016). Thus, to be successful as a young entrepreneur in Algeria, there are many challenges to overcome, which can be greater than the perceived economic and social benefits.

1.3.4 Methodology

This study will rely on both primary and secondary data collection methods. To explore the attitudes and challenges faced by young entrepreneurs in Algeria, semi-structured interviews will be conducted with entrepreneurs aged between 18-29. A sample of 20 participants will be sought for this study, focusing on recruiting participants who possess expert knowledge, background, education, and experience in entrepreneurship, experience in either private or public sector management, livelihood development and management, business management, and/or economic development policies. Ten active Algerian entrepreneurs and ten public sector respondents will compose the population of key informant interviewees. The interviews are to be conducted either personally, by phone, or by video call with the researcher. Research participants will be sourced through referrals from the key contacts of the researcher. The results of the interviews will be transcribed, organised, validated, and coded. In an integral context, the findings will be interrelated to underpin key prescriptions on how youth entrepreneurship can be developed and sustained in the Algerian economy. The study will abide by all ethical standards of research and sustain the requirements of originality and referencing while maintaining impartiality and avoiding research bias (Anderson, 2004; Grady, 2002).

To explore the economic, social, and political situation in Algeria, and assess the potential benefits of youth entrepreneurship in the country, desk research will be conducted using official databases and published country reports. To evaluate the overall impact of government actions and programs on youth entrepreneurship, desk research will be conducted on initiatives such as the Algeria Entrepreneurship and Employment Program, Tawdif Project, ImaGen Ventures Youth Challenge, career centers, and entrepreneurship houses.

This study relies on qualitative data based on the analysis of findings from the interviews and the desk research. Although some of the data collected from desk research will be numerical,

the researcher will qualitatively analyse the data. Findings from the interviews will be conducted using narrative analysis, which is used to understand the personal and lived experiences of a subject regarding a specific experience. Findings from the desk research will be analysed using thematic analysis, which is used to identify recurring patterns of meaning within data. Using qualitative analysis for both primary and secondary data will help to explore the information in more detail, offering more in-depth and profound findings.

This dissertation upholds a qualitative and inductive research format and uses an interpretivist paradigm, which is a representation of social meanings and people's lived experiences (Daymon & Holloway, 2002; Gomm, 2008). The study leverages the joint use of rationalist and empiricist models and embraces concepts, theories, and cases in explaining the research agenda, including the problem, objectives, assumptions, questions, and phenomena (Abend, 2008; Swanson, 2013; Weick, 2014). In Chapter 3, figure 4.1 the Research Onion Diagram provides a conceptual backdrop of the research framework that guides this study on youth entrepreneurship in Algeria.

CHAPTER TWO

YOUTH ENTREPRENEURSHIP SECTOR IN ALGERIA – TRENDS AND DYNAMICS

This chapter provides an examination of the entrepreneurship sector within the Algerian context. The chapter will focus on youth engagement, employment, motivations, and the experiences of young people in the Algerian economy. The chapter seeks to establish what are the core barriers to entrepreneurship in Algeria, regardless of the age of the entrepreneur. The chapter also examines the different economic forces in Algeria that appear to be promoting or sustaining entrepreneurship, particularly among young people. This chapter also intends to examine how the factors that promote youth entrepreneurship in Algeria are connected to greater prosperity of economic development, and how more analysis is required to demonstrate the potential upsides of promoting youth entrepreneurship. This chapter will be divided into five sections, discussing the perspective adopted by the researcher, the Algerian economy, youth engagement and employment, barriers to entrepreneurship, and entrepreneurship enablers.

2.1 PERSPECTIVE

To better understand, examine, and explain the significance of youth entrepreneurship in conjunction with the current research problem, key question, and objectives, this study will rely on the opportunity-based theory of Peter Drucker and the impact analysis theory. In principle, the opportunity-based theory posits that entrepreneurship represents a response to a stimulus (such as the economic, social, and political situation in the country), through a business venture, where an unemployed person exploits opportunities engendered by social, technological, and cultural changes in the environment. The impact analysis theory (IAT) advocated by Murphy and Marvel (2008), Lenjo (2015), and Dontigney (2018) deconstructs the causes and effects of a phenomenon (i.e. youth entrepreneurship) to afford greater understanding and appreciation of the research agenda while providing an indicative assessment of the overall impact of the issue (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development).

2.2 ALGERIAN ECONOMY

2.2.1 Banking and Hydrocarbon Industry

The Algerian economy at first appears as a prosperous environment for young entrepreneurs, who seek to set up new business ventures to further promote the economy. Ten years ago, the

recently resigned President Bouteflika promised a budget of more than \$60bn for infrastructure spending and new housing, the Algiers metro system, and a new East-West Highway project, alongside far-reaching reform of both the banking and hydrocarbon industries, which were designed to promote a significant expansion of the Algerian economy (Lloyds Bank, 2019). The goal of this reform was to transform the Algerian economy. Since 2014, Algeria's economy has experienced a steady growth of 3% to 4% per annum (Lloyds Bank, 2019). Moreover, looking at the non-oil part of the economy, growth has been closer to 6% per annum (Reuters, 2019). Algeria also has a strong foreign currency reserve, and during the mid-2000s the country experienced a significant debt relief program following the end of the Algerian civil war (Lefevre, 2017). Moreover, the Algerian economy also experienced a significant trade surplus, since the oil prices have recovered, meaning that there is surplus revenue to invest in economic expansion (Lefevre, 2017). By looking at these figures, it can be assumed that Algeria is a prosperous environment for young entrepreneurs.

However, while it is beneficial that the non-oil economy is growing in the country, it has been observed that these figures are quite misleading. For instance, more than 70% of all economic activity in Algeria is related to hydrocarbons, and the bulk of that activity is carried out through the state-owned oil company (Constable, 2019). This means that although the economic activity is there, most of the revenue goes to the government as opposed to businesses. Moreover, the 4% per annum overall growth in the economy is not related to any economic activity or policy directed by Algeria; it is rather the outcome of the global recovery in crude oil prices. However, as Constable (2019) suggested, the Algerian economy is now heavily unbalanced and there are no plans for a post-oil economy (an economy of the country that does not solely depend on the oil resources). Thus, there is a greater likelihood of an impending collapse within the economic lifetimes of those currently aged under 30.

Other Arab countries such as Saudi Arabia, Kuwait, and the United Arab Emirates are investing large amounts of their oil wealth in developing a post-oil economy, as oil reserves continue to decline, and there is a global shift to reduce hydrocarbon consumption (Al-Sabah, 2017; Isik, 2018). This means that although these countries are rich in oil wealth, the viability of the oil industry is not permanent. Even then, it is widely acknowledged that there is no certainty that these oil-reliant economies have transitioned their assets quickly enough, or whether they will be successful in transitioning their economies (Isik, 2018). In the case of Algeria, there is no noticeable activity to invest the oil-generated wealth into other economies as part of long-

term wealth preservation (Constable, 2019). It is difficult to model exactly what the impacts on the Algerian population would be if the oil revenue were to decline rapidly, but it has been theorised to be catastrophic (Aljazeera, 2019). Thus, unless this situation changes in Algeria, the economic situation in the country is likely to continue to go downhill in the future.

2.2.2 Housing and Employment

Although there have been significant capital investments in the Algerian infrastructure, it is not clear what overall impact it will have on the health of the economy in the country. Moreover, there is a significant shortage of housing in Algeria. While the government has pledged to add 2m units to the country's current stock of 8.5m (of which 50% are state managed) the government has encountered significant tax rises on property, and as a result banned the import of building materials (Oxford Business Group, 2018). This means that the likelihood of the housing shortage problem being addressed is limited. Moreover, unemployment is currently at a high rate of 11% (Reuters, 2019). In addition to this, the public sector is the second largest employer in the country, meaning that the commercial economy accounts for a comparatively small amount of employment (Reuters, 2019). As there is limited economic activity outside of government jobs, it means that unemployment is heavily dependent on the governmental job market.

It has been argued in several studies that the large number of people employed in the public sector in Algeria is a deliberate strategy on the part of the government to pacify large numbers of people and increase the number of people that are likely to support the government (Lorch & Bunk, 2017; Oxford Business Group, 2018). This has a reciprocal effect on the economy, as all these people need to be kept in employment, and part of the bureaucratic burden on the economy is simply keeping the large volume of public sector workers occupied (Lorch & Bunk, 2017). This is likely to have a cyclical effect on the Algerian economy in the future.

It has been noted that the lack of economic reforms has badly harmed the economy in terms of attracting foreign investors. For instance, the Algerian law enforces a 49:51 rule on foreign investors, which means that any business operating in the country must be at least 51% owned by the Algerians (Oxford Business Group, 2018; 2019). This is a huge deterrent to foreign investors. There have been potential reforms mooted on many occasions, but there have been very few outcomes. Moreover, the state controls the media and banking sectors, which means that there are industries where foreign investors cannot invest at all (Oxford Business Group, 2018). This is also likely to be another issue for potential foreign investors.

2.2.3 Informal Economy

As a result of the centralised economy and lack of genuine opportunities, there are now significant issues for the economy in Algeria and a potential rise for a ‘dark economy’. Temlali (2019) provides a comprehensive overview of the difficulty of trying to quantify a ‘dark economy;’ by its very nature, it is an economic activity in the country that is impossible to accurately locate. Nonetheless, Temlali (2019) notes that it is possible to trace a significant amount of people back to economic reforms in the mid-1990s when up to 800 state-owned companies were closed down, and around half a million people were made unemployed. This appears to have provided a catalyst for a significant development in the growth of the informal economy (Temlali, 2019). There is a potential that if the current economic situation in Algeria persists, there will be a rise in the dark economy.

There is little to no official information about the dark economy in the country. Temlali (2019) estimates that the size of the informal economy varies between \$20bn and \$40bn and that the lack of sustained research by the government into this means that there are no official figures available. Indeed, it is noted that the informal economy is something that the government has appeared to encourage as a mechanism for mitigating social problems and the outcome of a more extreme economy. For example, Temlali (2019) notes that there are huge differences between the official exchange rate for Algerian dinars and foreign currencies and the ones available within the informal economy. Temlali (2019) argues that this information is known to the Algerian government, which tactically encourages it as an economic facilitator. Although the state owns the majority of the housing, it has allowed the vast majority of tenancies to be arranged on the black market through unlicensed and unregulated intermediaries, as it helps to provide a highly effective buffer as the tax rises have made housing increasingly unaffordable (Lorch & Bunk, 2017; Oxford Business Group, 2018). Thus, it appears that the Algerian government promotes dark economic activities in the country.

It should be argued that an informal economy does not correspond to an illegal economy, although Algeria does have prosperous smuggling routes across its southern border with Mali. However, due to the global increase in the number of people working in freelance or ‘gig’ type positions, it becomes even more difficult to understand or monitor this part of the economy (Baklouti & Boujelbene, 2019). Moreover, Temlali (2019) demonstrates that the informal

economy also manifests the distrust that the Algerian people have toward their government and the public sector, notably the banking system; it has been estimated that up to 30% of all the cash and coin ever issued in Algeria is stored within the informal economy as domestic savings or in cash transactions (Temlali, 2019). Therefore, there are potentially billions of dollars worth of economic activity that is, in effect, invisible to official statistics, and it is within this informal economy that most of the entrepreneurial activity has taken place when considered from the perspective of the number of people starting up new businesses (Baklouti & Boujelbene, 2019). Thus, it becomes increasingly harder to understand the economic assets and activity in Algeria, as a lot of that activity is not seen.

2.3 YOUTH ENGAGEMENT AND EMPLOYMENT

One thing that is difficult to quantify because of a lack of official statistics is the extent to which people who start businesses do it to innovate and grow the economy, or whether they simply go into self-employment as a means to an end, or as a means to survive (Baklouti & Boujelbene, 2019). Therefore, this appears as an important issue, as to how one might differentiate all entrepreneurs that start a business because their motivations, practices, and ambitions are likely to be quite different.

As this thesis is concerned with the circumstances of young entrepreneurs in Algeria, there is a need to consider the overall economic circumstances of young people in the country. While the overall unemployment in Algeria is 11%, for people under 30 years old this figure increases to 29%, which is higher than in most other countries (Ahmed, 2018; Reuters, 2019). When this is combined with the fact that Algeria has a mostly young population, with approximately 70% of the population being under 30 years old, it represents a very serious social condition (Focus Economics, 2019). If most of the population is unemployed, this can have a substantial impact on the economy.

Regarding the commentary around the unofficial economy described in the previous section; those counted as unemployed may not receive social security payments, but they may be involved in some form of informal economic activity. Nonetheless, the general economic situation for young people in Algeria is quite poor. Even for those with a good education, including those with university degrees, there are limited opportunities for employment in a field that offers long-term prospects. There are two practical outcomes to this.

- 1) Algeria has very high rates of emigration, with hundreds of thousands of people every year leaving to search for better economic conditions elsewhere. However, Algeria is unique among countries with a large diaspora around the world, in that there is a comparatively small

flow of cash remittances back to the country. For instance, in most other developing countries, when people emigrate in search of work, they remit cash back to their home country (mainly to their family), and this can contribute to substantial flows of cash that can boost economic growth alone. In the case of Algeria, this appears not to be the case.

2) Many young people turn to entrepreneurship as a way of surviving. In this study, for clarity and amplification, an “entrepreneur is a “risk-taking innovative individual who establishes and manages a business for purposes of profit and growth” (Olson, 1987, p. 8) and “someone who perceives an opportunity and creates an organization to pursue it” (Bygrave & Hoffer, 1992, p.14). This references back to the point made in the previous section, that there is a clear debate about the number of business owners that this specific definition would apply in Algeria.

2.3.1 Two Distinct Forms of Entrepreneurship

In Algeria, there appear to be two distinct forms of entrepreneurship that are emerging within the economy.

1). The first is related to the internet and the generally associated industries of information technology and computing; there is a growing number of young Algerians developing and deploying businesses that exist online but have limited physical form in Algeria itself. They offer a variety of services such as coding, outsourced programming, and IT management services, and some focus on making online assets focused on the Algerian market. The most striking thing about this development is that it appears to be flourishing as it is largely outside of the purview of the government; global freelancing websites like UpWork and similar sites allow people to pitch for work without any legal form, and therefore the barriers to entrepreneurship in this field are low. Payment can be remitted via services such as PayPal, or recently more cryptocurrencies such as Bitcoin, which mean that it is not, necessarily, a requirement to have a bank account or other formal presence in Algeria. Thus, any economic activity in Algeria that is not monitored by the government appears to be more successful.

Therefore, one could argue that this is an avenue of entrepreneurship that is flourishing in part because younger people are more likely to have the skills to take advantage of these opportunities, and because many of the obstacles to entrepreneurship such as access to markets and regulatory barriers can be avoided. However, by nature, this type of entrepreneurship is quite difficult to track due to the informal economy. It has also been observed that it is much

easier for people to gain technical skills in these fields than in others because it is possible to complete most of the learning either through free online websites or through relatively low-cost online courses. Therefore, young Algerians can acquire the necessary market skills and put them to work without any societal restrictions. However, although this is something that might create an environment for entrepreneurship to start, it may not constitute entrepreneurship in and of itself. Nonetheless, there is a potential for online freelancing to potentially represent a sizeable sector of the Algerian economy in the future. For instance, countries such as India have built a huge economy based on outsourced information technology services, and there is the potential for that to be a key part of Algeria's economic future.

2). Many young Algerians become social entrepreneurs, rather than focusing explicitly on the commercial outcomes of a business. It has been theorised that this is because, for many young people, particularly those from marginal communities, there is no other way for them to drive any change in their circumstances. While the unemployment situation in Algeria continues to increase, 83% of the young people interviewed believe that "starting a business is a good career choice" (Momani, 2017, p. 1). Thus, entrepreneurship seems like a good idea, because there isn't another alternative to escaping poverty in the country, and more young people may be inclined to persist in a business venture as a result.

However, there is evidence to suggest that Algerian young people consider entrepreneurship to not just be about their business activity, but a powerful form of personal expression and empowerment, which they cannot otherwise manifest in other parts of their life in Algeria. There is evidence of entrepreneurship manifesting within all kinds of creative industries for young people:

"A new generation of cinema producers and other cultural actors from Algeria's underground scene continue to portray today's youth as energetic and optimistic despite lagging structures and a stifling atmosphere...Similarly, social entrepreneurship has emerged from this challenging context as a practice of resilience and creativity" Jebari (2016, p. 1).

Therefore, youth entrepreneurship is not simply about the activity in question, but it is also a way of considering young people's engagement with the state and trying to find some agency and power in difficult circumstances.

2.4 BARRIERS TO ENTREPRENEURSHIP

Within the specific Algerian context, this section aims to take into consideration the overall context of entrepreneurship and business in the country, and why the Algerian economy is

creating obstacles for young entrepreneurs. This is critical research for considering the experience of young entrepreneurs, and what might help them reach their potential when setting up business ventures in Algeria.

2.4.1 Venture Capital

It is widely acknowledged that the availability of business finance in Algeria is extremely limited, and therefore this acts as a significant barrier to economic growth. There are several different routes to this issue. The first issue is that the banking sector in Algeria is quite weak and highly restrictive, especially when compared to similar countries (Hacini, 2018). Secondly, the 49:51 rule described earlier also applies to banking, which means that no foreign bank can operate as a bank without having a majority local partner (Oxford Business Group, 2019). This can severely deter any foreign investment in the banking sector in Algeria. In addition to this, nearly all the domestic banks are state-owned, with six core banks representing a market share of greater than 90% in Algeria (Oxford Business Group, 2019). For instance, Banque Extérieure d'Algérie (BEA) is the largest bank in the country with a 22% market share, but it is effectively an adjunct to the hydrocarbon industry, as it is the main bank of the state oil company (Oxford Business Group, 2019). Banque Nationale d'Algérie (BNA) is the second largest with 20% of the market and was the first commercial bank in Algeria (Oxford Business Group, 2019). The fact that most of the banking activity in the country is controlled by the state, as well as the investments makes it very unattractive to potential foreign investors.

Government policy toward banks in Algeria has been highly disruptive in the last five years. Initially, there were plans based on an advanced monetarist policy to stimulate growth by the state by providing large amounts of liquidity into the banking system, so that banks could grow their assets and lend more into the economy (Oxford Business Group, 2019). However, although this part of the plan was accomplished, the second phase of listing some of the state-owned banks on the stock exchange, as a way of attracting overseas capital, was not fulfilled (Oxford Business Group, 2019). One of the reasons for this could be that a stock market listing and private investors would require more strict compliance and disclosure standards to be followed, as well as an introduction of protocols to protect against money laundering (Oxford Business Group, 2019). As these can be challenging to achieve in a country like Algeria, where a dark economy is actively supported by the government.

Although the restrictions preventing private banks from lending to State Owned Enterprises (SOE) were lifted in Algeria, there still appears to be little interest from the SOE managers to engage with private banks, given their limited capacity to invest (Groh & Wallmeroth, 2016).

Moreover, it can be assumed that the SEO managers are likely to object to being overseen by a commercial bank, which already has extremely preferential terms with state-owned banks (Groh & Wallmeroth, 2016). The outcome of this is that private entrepreneurs in Algeria have very limited sources of bank finances available to them, due to the market being rigid and uncompetitive. Access to credit is noted to be a key determinant of entrepreneurial activity and success, and the lack of competition and efficiency in the Algerian banking sector means that entrepreneurs often must find alternative finance routes (Groh & Wallmeroth, 2016). This makes it difficult to expand beyond a micro-business, as the business only has access to the cash that it generates by itself to expand. Items such as term loans, asset-backed loans, inventory or invoice finance, and the like are largely denied to small entrepreneurs in Algeria. Venture capital has, historically, been non-existent in Algeria. For instance, there is no ecosystem of angel investors or venture capital funds available to provide start-up capital to companies. The only available financing to Algerian entrepreneurs is the informal offers of investment through familial or business networks, but these are often limited in size and scope (Bakari, 2018). Other researchers have noted that in other countries, a vibrant venture capital scene and accessible bank financing are the precursors of an entrepreneurial sector in the country, as most ventures require some initial funding to develop products or services, protect intellectual property, or simply to meet overhead (Groh & Wallmeroth, 2016). It should also be noted that the 49:51 rule is the most prominent deterrent to international venture capitalists because they cannot have full control over a business that they invest in (Groh & Wallmeroth, 2016). Moreover, the construction sector currently has the highest number of foreign investors in relative terms, but this is still dominated by state activity, and most of the foreign activity is quite limited in scope (Bakari, 2018). Since most of the economy is held by state-owned organisations, no sector within the Algerian economy is substantially available to venture capital companies to invest in.

There is another factor where venture capital and industry-led investors are also deterred by the potential for civil unrest and instability in the country. Some of the main issues in Algeria are the corruption of the former President which has led to widespread protests across the country, an increasing turmoil on the southern border with Mali, and an ongoing long-term civil war (Aljazeera, 2019; Joffé, 2002). It can be argued that if the social conditions in the country do not improve, or if the oil-based economy were to experience another period of extreme distress, Algeria could potentially move into another period of civil war, or experience a potential coup

or similar uprising (Joffé, 2002). As a result of these uncertainties and risks, many investors choose not to pursue their investments in Algeria.

2.4.2 Corruption and the Rule of Law

Various anti-corruption organisations such as Transparency International (the global coalition against corruption) around the world note that Algeria is a country with extreme corruption problems and that these fall broadly into two categories: a cultural problem, and a general lack of enforcement (Transparency International, 2018). The cultural issue is that there is a historic cultural dynamic of patronage and nepotism in Algeria, which means that many business deals are conducted based on personal connections and relationships rather than based on merit or value (Transparency International, 2018). This means that for Algerian entrepreneurs to successfully set up a business, they must have the right connections in place, regardless of the quality of their ideas or business skills. It has been observed in a variety of different studies that any system based on patronage is likely to facilitate corrupt practices, while in Algeria it is common to accept bribes, particularly concerning interactions with the public sector, and notably the judiciary (Transparency International, 2018). On the other hand, Algeria has stringent anti-corruption laws that meet international standards, which should in theory make the country an attractive investment destination. However, several studies have demonstrated that more than 75% of surveyed Algerian households believe the judiciary to be wholly corrupted, with a similarly high percentage for the police (Transparency International, 2018). This means that despite bribes, patronage, and nepotism being identified as criminal offenses, prosecutions are extremely rare. The lack of implementation of anti-corruption policies in place makes potential new business ventures riskier and more vulnerable.

The background of corruption in Algeria started with the President; elections have been known to be manipulated with little to no accountability taken by the politicians (Sardar, 2018). Moreover, other authors have stated that the former President had previously rewritten the constitution to allow him to stay in power longer, which suggests an uncontrollable approach to matters of law and justice in the country (Sardar, 2018). The immediate impact of this is that the problems with corruption mean that international aid and sovereign debt are restricted, which would otherwise be one of the keys to greater economic expansion for Algeria in terms of giving private investors the confidence to invest alongside organisations like the World Bank or the International Monetary Fund (Sardar, 2018; Strachan, 2018). However, until such a situation changes in Algeria, there will continue to be little trust from foreign investors.

2.4.3 Foreign Direct Investments

For international investors, there is one aspect of Algerian corruption that is the most significant. Despite being a full signatory to the New York Convention of 1958, and a member of the International Centre for Settlement of Investment Disputes (ICSID), Algeria has a de facto policy of simply ignoring judgements handed down by foreign courts (Strachan, 2018; Transparency International 2018). The effect of this is to make Algeria an impossible destination for venture capitalists because there is no effective mechanism for them to protect their investments; that is, foreign investors cannot trust a corrupt judicial system to uphold their rights and provide suitable protection (Strachan, 2018). Therefore, there is little to no prospect for Algerian entrepreneurs to secure capital for their business through the traditional entrepreneurial systems found elsewhere in the world, which limits their ability to not only start but to their businesses. Some companies try and take advantage of the patronage regime by buying themselves protection and attempting to bribe their way to success, but that is no way to attempt to build an economy, and it further contributes to the problem.

2.4.4 Bureaucratic Obstacles

Algeria, a highly centralised state, has previously been noted to have problems in terms of the ability to obtain permits, licenses, or permissions for various business endeavours. This issue is slightly distinct from corruption, in the sense that the processes are very slow and required to undergo complex bureaucracy. This also links with the issue of large volumes of unofficial cash or otherwise informal economy, as entrepreneurs find it difficult to engage with the authorities, and often mistrust them completely. This then leads them to independently conduct unlicensed trade, and not formalise their business in the country. The impact of these actions is a significant hindrance to the overall economic growth of the country, and continued inequalities and corruption encourage entrepreneurs to set up businesses in the dark economy.

Lengthy bureaucratic procedures also inhibit the attractiveness of the country to venture capitalists, as it is evident that it is difficult to make companies efficient and agile if they are burdened with excessive bureaucratic requirements just to allow them to operate. The process of forming a company is quite difficult in Algeria compared to the ease with which a company can be formed in the UK, which is also further made difficult by the 49:51 rule. It has been argued in the literature that in many ways, it is easier for foreign nationals to set up Algerian companies as opposed to the native Algerians. There are a variety of consultants and registration agents that will manage the process and act as the 51% local shareholder for

documentation on behalf of the foreign entrepreneur, but these services are generally not marketed to local entrepreneurs, and would largely be out of the financial reach of many, particularly young, entrepreneurs. As a result, many Algerian entrepreneurs are unable to escape the challenges of bureaucracy in their country.

2.4.5 Gender Discrimination

Algeria also has another significant problem that further inhibits entrepreneurial activity in the country, which is gender discrimination. Benhabib et al. (2014), Boufeldja (2014), and Ghiat (2016; 2018) offer three distinct studies that engage with the reasons why more women do not set up their own businesses in Algeria, and the types of discrimination that prevent them from doing so. Boufledja (2014) and Ghiat (2016) both identify that Algerian women are culturally disadvantaged because Algeria has a patriarchal society that positions women as an underclass or sub-class. This means that females have routinely been positioned as not being suitable as entrepreneurs, and conformed into more traditional roles of being a wife and mother, whose natural place is at home.

The effect of this is that Algerian women have difficulty being accepted as entrepreneurs by their peers, regardless of their capabilities or business ideas; they have been positioned as ‘other’ or otherwise abnormal in a business setting. This manifests itself with not only a lack of encouragement from society but also active refusal from people to do business with them or attempting to halt their business aspirations. Both Boufledja (2014) and Ghiat (2016) note that the practical outcome of that is that it can be extremely dispiriting being a female entrepreneur in Algeria, and the respondents in their studies noted that one of the biggest barriers to their success is the amount of fortitude and determination required to achieve even a modest success. This means that many female entrepreneurs either give up or do not start a business at all due to these challenges. However, some of the respondents in the same studies argued that this is where they draw their inspiration from; their determination to succeed in business comes from a sense of bitterness and anger at how women are treated in Algeria, and to use their entrepreneurial activities as a means of driving a social change (Boufledja, 2014; Ghiat, 2016). This ties in well with the material that examines the motivations of young Algerian entrepreneurs, in that their business activities are only partly commercial in motivation, but they also see it as a powerful means of potentially starting a social change in Algeria.

It has been argued that, when looked at demographically, female entrepreneurs offer perhaps the largest potential in terms of economic development for the country. It was previously

observed in the work of Benhabib et al. (2014) as well as that of Boufledgja (2014) and Ghiat (2016; 2018) that historically, women have been denied the same access to education and development opportunities as men, and this means that they have to overcome major technical skills gap compared to male entrepreneurs, which not only makes it harder to succeed but it also narrows the field of potential businesses that they could potentially enter into. Patriarchal societies generally do not allow women to reach their full economic potential, but in a country like Algeria which has all the additional barriers to entrepreneurship as recorded in this literature review, it means that approximately half of the population are not making an economic contribution.

2.4.6 Soft Skills

Not only are women refused many opportunities to develop their skills, but the whole population also lacks proper access to learning key soft skills. A variety of studies (Djennadi, 2006; Izzrech et al., 2013; Maaradj, 2009) demonstrated that one of the things that can lead to uneven opportunities for entrepreneurs is that some of the soft skills required to succeed in business in Algeria are not easily accessible to all people. It is particularly noted that the ability to speak good French is a critical asset for entrepreneurs, because of the legacy of French colonialism that still permeates many institutions (Djennadi, 2006). There is a dichotomy within the country that suggests that people that speak French are cleverer, more sophisticated, and likely to be successful, whereas non-French speakers are viewed as uneducated and unworldly (Jacob, 2019). This manifests itself in terms of access to networks, the facilities that banks offer, access to the best opportunities such as state concessions or auctions, and favourable treatment in most interactions with the government.

In an economy that is based to an extreme extent on personal relationships, patronage, and networks, the development of these ‘softer’ skills alongside technical abilities has been cited as the key barrier that prevents the majority of the population from becoming successful entrepreneurs. However, it should be noted that these soft skills are what stop new business endeavours from growing, but it does not stop young entrepreneurs from starting a business at all. Therefore, it is perhaps more pertinent to argue that these cultural issues are a barrier to entrepreneurs seeking to either develop their small business idea into a larger business or those seeking to formalise what might be a cash business into a legal entity.

It is observed in much of the literature that many people within the communities in Algeria are very difficult for researchers to access, and therefore there are very few pieces of research that provide detailed data on these obstacles and how these are handled. It has also been observed that the sheer size of Algeria is also a difficulty as most of the academic research has been previously focused on entrepreneurship around the capital Algiers only. There is likely to be a highly variable experience and expectations of entrepreneurs across the country, but there are very few academic studies that explore this.

2.5 ENTREPRENEURSHIP ENABLERS

This section discusses some of the enablers of entrepreneurial activity (globalisation, policy programs, social change) that could be framed in the Algerian context.

2.5.1 Globalisation

One of the key entrepreneurship enablers in Algeria is globalisation. Globalisation is quite difficult to define, but in this study, it is referred to as the context of increasingly globalised trade. Broad literature on globalisation suggests that a period of profound economic change began to manifest in the latter part of the twentieth century, driven by advances in communications technology and the advent of containerised shipping services (Erikson, 2014; Hirst et al., 2015). The goal was to create a more interconnected world where it would be possible to move various economic activities such as manufacturing around the world (Erikson, 2014; Hirst et al., 2015). Development of the Internet and the digitisation of many aspects of life have further continued this process, and there are various theories such as the time-space compression and the notion of a ‘global village’ as a means of trying to represent the idea that the world is more interconnected (Erikson, 2014). The more interconnected the world is, the less dependent the country becomes on one source of economy.

One of the more interesting aspects is the potential decline in the importance of the nation-state in organising economic activity and labour flows, as there is an increase in the number of mobile workers in the world (Held & McGrew, 2007). These workers’ sense of identity is also less rooted in nationality, and this impacts on choices they make about where and how to work (Erikson, 2014; Hirst et al., 2015). This could potentially be considered as one of the reasons for the high emigration rates in Algeria, although some scholars have argued that high emigration is mostly caused by the economic need as opposed to the desire to work mobile.

In the case of Algeria, there is an interesting phenomenon where digital forms of work are becoming separated from the country and its legal structures, instead, they exist solely in cyberspace. As discussed before, people can acquire and complete work, as well as accept payment for it, purely digitally. Currently, this is a rather nascent process, and it remains quite difficult to set up a system of working that is completely independent of the laws of the country where one lives, but it demonstrates the potential to move away from the rigid structures of the Algerian state.

As mentioned before, the government of Algeria has been the major source of economic activity for Algerians. The great advantage of economic globalisation is that it gives entrepreneurs a wider market where they can try to establish their businesses. This is not, necessarily, all positive because it exposes Algeria to a highly competitive global marketplace in which it might be quite challenging to compete (Held & McGrew, 2007). At the level of individual entrepreneurs, they must compete against other global entrepreneurs when launching businesses, winning customs, and growing. However, it is arguable that this is a significant enabler for Algeria, as currently, Algerians do not have the opportunity to compete on fair terms in their own country due to the constraints. Therefore, while globalisation might generate several obstacles for young entrepreneurs, it is still more beneficial than remaining without any route into the global market.

At a more profound level, some literature places the idea of globalisation in a context of power, rather than economic activity. For instance, this can be either a positive or negative application of power, in the sense that globalisation can be seen as exploitative when used to try and lower the costs by exploiting lower wages and not following the regulations in some countries (George & Wilding, 2003; Held & McGrew, 2007). However, if one were to consider the case of Algeria, globalisation is an enabler, because it removes power from the bureaucratic and corrupt state and places it in the hands of the entrepreneurs (Hirst et al., 2015). While some entrepreneurs will prosper more than others, at least the power has been given to them, as opposed to imposed on them.

There is a body of literature that suggests that one of the best things that governments can do to promote entrepreneurship is to simply let them innovate and develop without restrictions. There are many contexts in which that could be considered a rather political move, but in the case of Algeria, it can be seen that economic globalisation is how the state provides entrepreneurs with more freedom.

2.5.2 Policy Programs

The government of Algeria does not have specific programs designed with the specific aim of driving entrepreneurship, but some should be considered. The major one is the Agence Nationale de Soutien à l'Emploi de Jeune, which is an agency designed to support the employment of people under 40. This has been in operation since 1964 and has the remit of trying to stimulate economic activity by offering loans at zero interest, in conjunction with the main banks. Several studies have demonstrated that it is very difficult to track the performance of this program because the only source of data available comes from the government, which has a vested interest in making the scheme successful. The Algerian government has claimed that this program has been very successful in recent years, with the number of young people entering into work doubling from 2010 to 2020 to approximately 200,000 per annum. However, there is no way of verifying whether these numbers are true. Some scholars argue that interest-free loans are just another technique to pacify young people in the short term, and there is no actual economic stimulus from the loan package. It has also been observed that this program has no link to entrepreneurship in the sense that the loans do not have to be to start or develop a business, but can be used for other purposes. In addition to this, there has been a critique that there is no long-term benefit from the loans because there is no connection to the development of technical skills that might be of use in the Algerian economy.

There is some evidence within the literature that there was some support provided to entrepreneurs through programs such as selling state-owned land and offering planning exemptions, and this may be why the majority of foreign investors have entered into the construction and property development sectors. There is very little evidence of how this scheme is administered, and whether it is particularly focused on entrepreneurship or raising capital through land sales. However, one could argue that this is an example of an accidental program that supports entrepreneurs; one that is not a deliberate attempt from the government.

There is increasing evidence to suggest that the main policy programs that benefit entrepreneurs only come from outside Algeria. There is some emerging work on the progress made by the Global Entrepreneurship Week program, which developed an Algerian chapter sponsored by the North Africa Partnership for Economics Opportunities (NAPEO). Within this chapter, some data demonstrates that the program started in 2011 with 20 events and workshops, and in its latest incarnation had more than 2200 events and workshops designed to promote and support entrepreneurship across Algeria. In 2019 the United Nations Institute for Training and Research announced that it was to institute a training program for young Algerian entrepreneurs in association with a private sector business forum in Algeria, which is a further example of

enabling programs for entrepreneurs coming from outside Algeria, as opposed to the Algerian government.

There is evidence to argue that some private companies may try to use entrepreneurship as a means of accessing the Algerian market. A new start-up incubator has been launched in Algeria, named IncubMe, which although does not have any government support, has attracted support from other international companies such as the Oxford Business Group, Digitsole, Zhor Tech, and Frater-Razes Laboratories. It could be argued that these companies are looking for a low-risk way of gaining exposure to the Algerian start-up scene and are using entrepreneurship training as a vehicle for achieving that goal. This also puts these organisations in a beneficial position if the Algerian economy develops in a positive direction, and the economic climate becomes more advantageous for potential investments.

It could be argued that this is a classic form of globalisation, as it refers to the same idea of removing the direct power from the Algerian government and putting it back into the hands of entrepreneurs and other organisations (Haugh & Talwar, 2016). Globalisation could also be considered as a means by which resources are provided to entrepreneurs where a government is unable or unwilling to do so. This is particularly relevant to the provision of training, development, and opportunities that the Algerian government fails to provide. Globalisation creates links between entrepreneurs and the opportunities that they need and helps to remove the obstacles that were there before.

Past literature on entrepreneurial ecosystems in developed countries reveals the multiplicity and diversity of organisations engaged in providing these enabling opportunities to entrepreneurs, such that the question then becomes about the quality and appropriateness of these provisions, and whether the creation of such vast ecosystems can end up inhibiting entrepreneurs by creating a bureaucracy of its own. Therefore, the fact that there are only two or three identifiable programs of this nature within Algeria, with the key ones being provided by external organisations, means that Algeria has a lot more potential in terms of offering programs that can enable entrepreneurship.

2.5.3 Social Change

The work of previous scholars such as Benhabib et al. (2014), Boufeldja (2014), and Ghiat (2016; 2018) help not only showcase the gender discrimination that female entrepreneurs face in Algeria, but also to highlight how gradually social attitudes about women have begun to shift in the country, and this offers a different perspective on the power of globalisation.

It is widely acknowledged how globalisation has begun to drive change for women around the world, both positively and negatively. There are a wide variety of studies that demonstrate that the internet has been an extremely powerful tool in challenging prevailing patriarchal narratives about the roles of women (Steyaert & Hjorth, 2008). There is a body of literature that has demonstrated that the Internet simply allows people greater access to other cultures in a mediated form, particularly through social media, and this has a very powerful effect in shaping perceptions of society and culture (Haugh & Talwar, 2016). Thus, people in Algeria are now much more likely to be exposed to different kinds of media that challenges and confounds their understanding of women, and the roles that women play in society. It has also been demonstrated that, particularly in Arabic countries, social media allows people to search for like-minded people, whether it is positive or negative (Hirst et al., 2015; Kew et al., 2013). So female entrepreneurs and businesspeople have the mechanism to come together in a mutually supportive way, to lessen the burden of residual stigma that exists in Algeria, share best practices, and generally provide a support network for each other.

There is still a great deal of stigma toward female and other minority entrepreneurs, despite the recent societal changes in the last few years. There is also not enough evidence that would allow us to conclude whether other marginalised groups can experience the same level of support in Algeria, particularly those that lack the necessary soft skills or non-native French speakers (Jacob, 2019). The process of social change is a significant enabler of entrepreneurship as it opens more doors to people that could become entrepreneurs, which in turn increases the number of businesses that exist in the country (Haugh & Talwar, 2016; Steyaert & Hjorth, 2008). It could be argued that the social stigma being witnessed in Algeria are likely to reduce but not completely disappear. Moreover, entrepreneurs can never be entirely independent of the society in which they operate, but there is considerable value in reducing the social obstacles that they experience.

One of the more interesting questions found in the literature is whether social change is a precursor of entrepreneurship, or whether entrepreneurship drives social change. One would suggest that social change is driving, or at least enabling, entrepreneurship within Algeria. Entrepreneurship is, potentially, an enabler of social change, particularly for younger people (Dey & Steyaert, 2018). Therefore, an answer to the question is that both can be true at the same time, as both entrepreneurialism and social change are fluid concepts; they can exist in a reciprocal or a reflexive context, where they can both amplify each other (Haugh & Talwar, 2016). Thus, social change, in one way or another, is an important component of entrepreneurship.

Social entrepreneurship is about driving forward the social changes that make broader entrepreneurship possible. Social entrepreneurship is a concept that can help to act as the precursor of commercial entrepreneurship, or indeed a component of commercial entrepreneurship in countries like Algeria (Steyaert & Hjorth, 2008). It is not an entirely altruistic endeavour, in terms of improving the lives of young people, it has a broader purpose in opening out the economy and scope of opportunity (Dey & Steyaert, 2018). What past studies have not considered is the link between social change and entrepreneurship, rather than the applied impacts of it, which this study will attempt to address.

2.6 CONCLUSION

This chapter provided a comprehensive overview of the Algerian economy, the current obstacles faced by the young people in the country and highlighted several issues in Algeria, which offered more background into why the current research is important. Scholarly literature on the barriers and enablers of entrepreneurship, with a particular focus on the availability of capital, corruption and the rule of law, bureaucracy, gender discrimination, soft skills, policy, social change, and processes of globalisation were discussed in conjunction to provide a comprehensive context to the Algerian entrepreneurial scene. Some issues were raised and discussed throughout this chapter. This chapter also identified several gaps in existing research, which will be further discussed in Chapter 3.

Table 2.1: A summary of key issues relating to the Algerian context (Research gap)

- The state policy development and controversial forces are pushing young Algerians toward entrepreneurship of various forms.
- Barriers and enablers of youth entrepreneurship in Algeria
- No existing research that draws together all these strands of knowledge
- Unknown impact of entrepreneurship on Algeria
- Competition and efficiency in the market
- Social issues of unemployment, housing, and skilled labour.

Overall, the main ambition of this research is to try and place entrepreneurship within the trajectory of development in Algeria so that it captures the inherent fluidity of both the country and the subject matter.

CHAPTER THREE

LITERATURE REVIEW-THEORETICAL FOUNDATION

The purpose of this literature review is to identify the research objectives by analysing the wider landscape of business literature that has focused on the Algerian context. The purpose is to try and establish the research gap and develop research objectives to aim to address this gap. The structure of the literature review is as follows. The **first** substantive section provides an overview of the literature on youth engagement and employment, to offer an initial assessment of the literature that has previously examined entrepreneurship in the specific context of young people, both conceptually and in the context of Algeria.

The **second** substantive section of the review focuses on the literature on models of development economics, and the theories that describe the way that undeveloped countries can become developed. The purpose of analysing these theories is to demonstrate that they are not applicable in the Algerian context before proposing a new model of development economics. This model combines some of the key points about youth entrepreneurship, with a hybrid model of development economics that seeks to address some of the critiques from the previous models. The goal of this model is to explore how Algeria could pursue a strategy of economic development in the future.

The study uses the opportunity-based theory of Peter Drucker and the impact analysis theory. In principle, the opportunity-based theory posits that entrepreneurship represents a response to a stimulus, through a business venture, where an unemployed person exploits available opportunities as a response to social, technological, and cultural changes in the environment. The impact analysis theory is a paradigm that deconstructs the causes and effects of a phenomenon (i.e., youth entrepreneurship) to afford greater understanding and appreciation of the research agenda while providing an indicative assessment of the overall impact of the issue. Both of these theories will be discussed in this chapter.

3.1 THEORIES AND MODELS OF YOUTH ENTREPRENEURSHIP

3.1.1. Background

First, the concept of youth and youth entrepreneurship must be explained. Youth refers to the transition period from childhood to adulthood (Lewis & Massey, 2003). There is no specific age range to classify “youth,” but a typical range is between 15-24 years old (Kuratko, 2016). Youth entrepreneurship can therefore be defined as any entrepreneurial activity carried out by someone within this age bracket. Presenting a specific theory or theories of youth entrepreneurship is difficult because there is very little literature that looks at this group as a variable of entrepreneurship.

Current literature is limited to a series of scholarly interventions that highlight the lack of interest in age as a predictor variable of entrepreneurial outcomes. Lewis and Massey (2003) argue that young people are not common in research on entrepreneurship, in that they are never separated as a predictive demographic characteristic. This is in contrast to gender, ethnic origin, and sexuality, where many studies consider differences in these characteristics as a defining aspect of entrepreneurship. Lewis and Massey (2003) note that there is a functional reason for this, in that many countries do not collect the age of company owners in a structured way, whereas other characteristics are observed, and therefore the data is not readily available. Lewis and Massey (2003) also note that this is a particularly unusual circumstance because since the 1980s there has been a huge promotion of entrepreneurship as not only a good career choice but also as a contributor to the economy and the overall economic performance of a country. Over the last twenty years, unparalleled resources have gone into promoting entrepreneurship among young people through schools, competitions, and marketing (Kuratko, 2016; Lewis & Massey, 2003; Nielsen et al., 2017). It is therefore surprising that much of the existing scholarly work has not given age more consideration for entrepreneurship.

3.1.2. Theoretical Models

It can be argued that this gap can have a profound effect on how theories about entrepreneurship are developed. When one considers different theories of entrepreneurship, most of them conceptualise only several key points; that is, how entrepreneurs make decisions, the determination of deciding to become an entrepreneur, and how the decisions of entrepreneurs are influenced (Geldhof et al., 2014). Moreover, many of them are meta-cognitive approaches to understanding entrepreneurs, that is, how entrepreneurs think about thinking; how they choose to prioritize their thought processes, how to think about opportunities and constraints,

and how to identify their own biases (Cho & Jung, 2014; Haynie et al., 2010; Urban, 2012). The existing models noted here serve the purpose of demonstrating how existing theories do not consider age to be a relevant input variable for models on entrepreneurship. Below is the first model by Cho and Jung (2014).

Figure 3.1: A Metacognitive Model of Entrepreneurs

Note: Derived from “The relationship between metacognition, entrepreneurial orientation, and firm performance: An empirical investigation” by Cho, Y. S. & Jung, J. Y. (2014) in *Academy of Entrepreneurship Journal*, 20 (2), p.75.

Alternatively, there are established models such as the Recognition Primed Decisions (RPD) model, which offers insight into how entrepreneurs process information about potential options and evaluate constraints and opportunities, usually in complex situations (Baron & Ward, 2004; Gray, 2001; Gustafsson, 2006). This model is presented in Figure 3.2.

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Figure 3.2: Recognition Primed Decisions

Note: Derived from: “Four models for a decision support system” by Mirchandani, D. & Pakath, R. (1999) in *Information & Management*, 35 (1), pp. 31-42.

These bodies of literature are notable because they do not consider how these approaches might vary with age as a predictor variable. There are analyses of how different groups might approach things such as decision-making, such as the work around the differences between genders and how they take decisions and engage different information structures as entrepreneurs; but the same is not true of age (Marlow & Patton, 2005; Mirchandani, 1999; Welter, 2011). There is some promising work that considers the barriers to entrepreneurship, though this is a very small field of literature. There are a variety of ways in which barriers to entrepreneurship are considered, ranging from what might be called economic barriers, such as lack of capital, legal restrictions on company formation or investors, difficulty in getting licenses, and permits, but not on age alone.

Age is a more complex personal characteristic within this body of literature, in part because of the lack of data on the age of business owners. However, it has been identified by past literature that there is a bias within all literature on personal characteristics; that is, there is an obvious benefit in enlarging the entrepreneurship franchise to the people considered underrepresented (Marlow & Patten, 2005). There would appear to be no valid reason for arguing that one group should have less opportunity to become entrepreneurs, or that they are inherently less entrepreneurial than others (Marlow & Patten, 2005). However, the aspect of underrepresentation in business with respect to age has not been fully explored by research.

All research approaches tend to draw on sociological understandings of entrepreneurship, such that they examine barriers in the discursive sense, whereby these barriers are social. Ruef and Lounsbury (2007) noted that sociological engagements with entrepreneurship appear to be incoherent and grudging; that is, sociologists have never developed distinct models of entrepreneurship, youth or otherwise, but have taken common sociological theories, notably that of Weber, and have sought to apply them to a variety of case studies in a rather indiscriminate manner (Ruef & Lounsbury, 2007). These are useful approaches nonetheless as they help to understand disparities in business ownership and entrepreneurship, such as describing the distinction between fewer female and non-white business owners compared to male and white business owners. The value of these models is that they try and pinpoint what needs to be done to improve the situation for these demographics

There is an increasing body of literature that questions the largely unspoken assumption that being an entrepreneur will always be beneficial for the individual involved. This can be considered a weakness in all literature on entrepreneurship, in that it is assumed that being an entrepreneur is an end goal in itself, and if one does not succeed it is because of a technical failure in running the business, not because there were better opportunities of work (Oosterom, 2018; Geldhof et al., 2014). Of significance to this thesis is the work that considers the case of young entrepreneurs, particularly in the developing world.

It is argued that the narrative that entrepreneurship is empowering and represents a viable form of work for young people is far from straightforward, and there is incredible complexity in the experience of entrepreneurship by different age groups. There is research that suggests that for some young people, becoming an entrepreneur is not only a stressful and peripatetic occupation but is a worse choice than going into any other employment available to them (Geldhof et al., 2014; Oosterom, 2018). Oosterom (2018) argued that what loosely is referred to as ‘supply

side' approaches to fostering youth entrepreneurship, mainly through providing training and experience opportunities, are largely ineffectual. His study provided a meta-analysis of different schemes and found that there is no evidence at all that these approaches would result in either improved incomes for young people or that their long-term prospects are enhanced in any way (Geldhof et al., 2014; Oosterom, 2018). Thus, in reality, being a young entrepreneur may be more challenging based on the limited support available to them.

Some studies suggest that there is a relationship between age and level of education, but in the inverse to what one would expect; better entrepreneurial outcomes are experienced by young people with relatively limited education rather than those with better education (Oosterom, 2018). A variety of explanations have been suggested for that outcome, such as that in the developing world, and certainly, in the short-term there is more of a premium for those working in transactional, cash-based businesses rather than those developing businesses that might require a broader economic infrastructure to sustain them (Williams & Horkova, 2013). However, those explanations appear to make significant assumptions about the structure of economic activity in developing nations that may not be true in reality.

3.2 THEORIES OF ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

In the context of how the economic development of Algeria might be theorized, there is a challenge in selecting the right kind of theory for this unique environment. Economic development has been a focus of scholarly work for a long time, however, the focus on how to develop poorer nations only really accelerated after the Second World War. A wide array of theories have been proposed since then, and there is value in considering them in chronological order because they represent a distinct trajectory of work within academia. Most theories represent a means of engaging with the perceived failures of that which occurred in the past.

Table.3.1 Development of Economic Theories

Theory	Key Period of Development & Use
Mercantilism	Pre-20 th Century
Economic nationalism	Early 20 th Century
Linear Stages of Growth	Mid-20 th Century
Structural Changes Model	Mid-20 th Century
Dependence Theory	Late 20 th Century
Free Market Ideologies	Late 20 th Century

Note: Developed by Osmani Abderrezzak (2023) based on secondary literature

3.2.1 Mercantilism and Economic Nationalism

The first acknowledged period of development economics emerged through the idea of mercantilism, which emerged during the seventeenth century as the nation-state began to emerge as the dominant unit of organisation. Sections below will describe this concept in more detail while discussing its development economics.

3.2.1.1 Mercantilism

Mercantilism is an economic policy that is designed to maximise exports and minimise imports for an economy. Mercantile approaches to development argue that countries develop by hoarding their capital (Lal, 2000). This was to be achieved by practicing aggressive protectionism to achieve a disproportionately high trade balance; maximising exports and minimising imports, subsidising home industries, and applying tariffs to imports (Lal, 2000). In other words, this mechanism was designed to grow the economy through growing volumes of wealth and multiplying it with strategic economic practices.

3.2.1.2 Economic Nationalism

Nationalism is an economy that favours state interventionism over other market mechanisms. Economic nationalism holds the same principle true, but it emerged slightly later and with a crucial distinction; mercantilism argues for colonialism as a key means of creating the right balance of trade, whereas economic nationalism does not. Both theories have been subject to some conceptual critiques; the first is that both objectives seek to maximize the amount of capital that is held by the state, not private entrepreneurs or other institutions, which requires that the nation-state is the prime mover of economic activity (Arrighi, 1994). In turn, this belies the overreliance of the theory on the nation-state as the primary object of organization, and that the world can be understood as a competition between nations (Arrighi, 1994). While these theories are straightforward, they represent a starting point for a body of work that has considered economic development as a research area in its own right; distinct from individual

acts of economic development, business studies, or entrepreneurship, and focused on the idea of moving from a state of undeveloped to developed.

Table. 3.2 Mercantilism and Economic Nationalism

Mercantilism	The object of economic development is the maximisation of capital.	Relies on colonialism as the prime means by which the ability to secure capital is made real.
Economic nationalism	Economic development remains about maximising capital.	This theory does not require empire building, but still assumes that the nation state is the primary unit of engagement in economic activity.
Linear Stages of Growth	Countries go through a linear trajectory of growth closely associated with scientific and technological change. The model requires efficient allocation of capital, and the acquiescence of entrepreneurs to a model of delayed gratification; profits need to be reinvested in growth rather than consumption. Therefore, private business rather than the nation state is assumed to be the driver of economic activity.	Ultimately quite a simplistic theory that squeezes all of the different experiences of nations through the industrial revolution and beyond into the same process. A backward-looking model, in the sense that it has been developed knowing how history played out, and has been devised to suit the historical record; much less clarity about its utility for prediction.
Structural Changes Model	Similar in ontology to the stages of growth model but has a very specific focus on the idea that development is achieved by surplus labour involved in agriculture being rationalised into productive endeavour.	Very little interrogation of the basic assumption that there is a huge amount of untapped labour available in agriculture. Little conception of what might cause all of this untapped labour, should it exist, to coalesce around industrial activity.
Dependence Theory	Dependence theory argues that developing nations can be forced into a permanently subordinate relationship to developed nations, through the rubric of aid and development finance.	It is not a particularly helpful theory for the developing nation, because its fundamental ontology requires that they exist as a victim; there is no positive future for developing nations in this theory.
Free Market Ideologies	Markets know best how to allocate resources and capital, and the state should simply get out of the way; that is the most effective way of achieving economic development.	This model would only work if each country was equally prepared and developed; otherwise, some countries are much better prepared to survive the vicissitudes of market forces, and all that happens is that existing inequalities are compounded.

Note: Developed by Osmani Abderrezzak (2023) based on secondary literature

3.2.2 Linear Stages of Growth- Rostow's (1960) Classic Model

After the Second World War, there was a more general focus on the idea of nations as part of an international order not just discrete units in competition with each other, especially in the case of economic rebuilding efforts following the war. As such, several theories began to emerge that were more about the type of world that should be brought about by development economics, and that entailed a more collegiate, less competitive, winner-take-all approach than

economic nationalism (Arrighi, 1994). The basic premise is that economic development relies on the efficient allocation of capital to development tasks, and the generation of savings or capital efficiencies through technology, and this can be thought of in terms of five key stages of development as posited in Rostow's (1960) classic model: the traditional society, the pre-conditions for take-off, the take-off, the drive to maturity, and the age of high mass-consumption (Figure 3.3).

Figure 3.3: Rostow's Stages of Growth

Note: Derived from “The stages of economic growth: A non-communist manifesto” by Rostow, W. W. (1960). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press

This model is based heavily on technological development on how progress is made and therefore shares several characteristics with enlightenment theories, where science and rationalism are believed to be the most important elements of the human condition. The traditional society phase is characterised by a lack of surplus production; not a complete absence, but a situation where the most of production is agricultural, and subsistence in level. Society is completely hierarchical, and the economic outlook is turbulent, with things like famine or war a permanent risk, particularly in terms of limiting the ultimate resource of development, labour. Rostow (1960) argues that the pre-conditions for take-off involve a fundamental shift in society, particularly in countries that have the longest-established social order. The pre-conditions for take-off commence with the gradual shift away from an agrarian society, and in tandem, there is a broadening of trading relationships with other countries, which

creates international markets for the country. However, the critical issue at this phase is that as this nascent commerce starts to generate surplus capital, that capital is then reinvested back into the economy, not on acts of consumption.

Rostow (1960) argued that to be successful, this reinvestment level should be above 5% of the national income; this creates the momentum for growth. In addition to this, the role of agriculture shifts from subsistence to the generation of a surplus, such that it can meet the twin goals of supporting the emerging urban population and become a major export industry to generate reserves of foreign currency. Rostow (1960) argued that as this process takes place, and particularly as the country is exposed to external markets and influences, then attitudes toward risk-taking and entrepreneurship change, and the potential for sustained economic growth emerges.

The take-off section is described by self-sustaining, dynamic economic growth. Critically, Rostow (1960) claimed that this is largely about attitude and sentiment; the public has to have made an emotional switch such that they value economic development more than tradition. Beyond this, Rostow (1960) has three specific requirements for the take-off phase.

1. The rate of productive investment should rise from approximately 5% to over 10% of national income or net national product
2. The development of one or more substantial manufacturing sectors, with a high rate of growth.
3. The existence or quick emergence of a political, social, and institutional framework that exploits the impulses to expansion in the modern sector and the potential external economic effects of the take-off.

Rostow (1960) also speaks of the development of a particular entrepreneurial ethos that focuses on reinvestment rather than consumption, and therefore the acceptance not just of large amounts of risk, but also the acceptance of delayed gratification. Following this, Rostow (1960) advocates for four factors necessary to sustain growth.

- Existence of enlarged, sustained effective demand for the product of key sectors.
- Introduction of new productive technologies and techniques in these sectors.
- Society's increasing capacity to generate or earn enough capital to complete the take-off transition.

- Activities in the key sector should induce a chain of growth in other sectors of the economy, that also develop rapidly.

Table.3.3 Time periods of take-off and maturity

Country	Take-off Period
Great Britain	1783-1802
Russia	1890-1914
United States	1843-1860
Germany	1850-1873
Canada	1896-1914
China	1952
India	1952
Country	Maturity Year
Great Britain	1850
Russia	1950
United States	1900
Germany	1910
Canada	1950

Note: Developed by Osmani Abderrezzak (2023) based on secondary literature

The stage of maturity was reached when there was a complete, self-sustaining mode of economic growth formed around reinvestment rates of up to 20%, coupled with a focus on technology. This leads to the economic landscape of the country being subject to continual remaking as sectors evolve, new ones are created, and older ones level off. Rostow's (1960) work was built around the experiences of countries in the West, particularly those that had gone through the industrial revolution of the seventeenth century. The tables above illustrate some of the mooted periods for both take-off and maturity.

The age of mass consumption, as argued by Rostow (1960), is not necessarily defined by economic growth but by a generational shift, such that the people no longer have any living memory of a subsistence life or the hardscrabble early years of economic development; they have known nothing but an age of choice and plenty. Rostow (1960) went on to postulate another stage in the development, which he described as the search for quality; where lifestyles are defined by the complete normalisation of economic security and involvement in things beyond consumerism, such as arts and philanthropy.

This is a model that held great sway in academia and policy circles, despite some obvious critiques. The first is that one could argue that the five stages model is something of a stylised model; it takes an enormous diversity of economic situations and forces them into a simple linear categorization. In addition to this, Rostow's (1960) model is backward-looking; he developed the model having already known what the 'result' is and could therefore be accused of engineering a model that just fits the historical record, irrespective of whether that has any

utility for the future. This also presages a further critique; the age of mass consumerism in the US in the 1950s and 1960s, the time in which Rostow was writing, seems to be accepted as an end in itself; that is self-evident why a society would want to reach that stage. A more substantive critique emerges around the idea that it is not clear, despite the mention of technology and entrepreneurialism, what the motor for change is; it is unclear what starts and sustains the drive toward economic development in a capitalist style.

3.2.3 Structural Change Model-Lewis (1954) Model

The structural change model is an approach that emerged after Rostow's (1960) five stages of economic growth, but treads very similar ground in terms of postulating a model that moves from the agrarian to the urbanized industrial.

Figure 3.4: Lewis' Structural Change Model

Note: Derived from “Economic development with unlimited supplies of labour” by Lewis, W. A. (1954) in *The Manchester School*, 22 (2), pp. 139-191.

In this case, the body of literature tries to consider a broader process of societal as well as economic change. Lewis (1954) proposed the two-sector surplus model, which identified a simple hypothesis that subsistence agriculture contained a vast amount of surplus labour that could be turned toward industrial development with the right policy. Chenery (1960) proposed something more sophisticated, that rejected the one-size-fits-all methodology of Rostow (1960) and argued for a more individualized understanding. Chenery's (1960) theory will be discussed next.

3.2.4 Chenery (1960) Theory

Chenery (1960) proposed a theory of patterns of development, whereby each country would likely follow a different proximate trajectory of development, which is dependent on the individual characteristics of that country. For example, Chenery (1960) notes that its absolute

territorial size and its endowed resources will likely play a significant role in both how and how quickly a country becomes wealthy. This can then be amplified by factors such as relative strengths and weaknesses compared to other countries.

While this does, in theory, offer a more sophisticated lens with which to consider countries, many critiques of the linear stages of the growth model have been made to this model. The core critique is that it remains unclear what the motor of the sequential change is, the world seems to have an innate desire to shift from the agrarian to the industrial. Lewis' (1954) model was also critiqued for making a similar assumption made with little empirical evidence, that there is a large amount of surplus labour in agrarian societies (Kirkpatrick & Barrientos, 2004). Thus, not one country can be assumed to be the same in terms of reaching economic growth.

3.2.5 The Dependence Theory

In the 1970s and 1980s academia became infused with a cultural turn, as postmodernism and poststructuralism started to become a significant part of the theoretical approach to a wide range of disciplines. At the same time, some nations that had been subject to colonial rule or were under a non-capitalist system started to develop a path of economic independence; certainly, if one considers some of the global emerging market powers like China and India, this would be the case. There was a growing body of work that considers post-colonial legacies around the world, not just in countries that were formally colonised, but in the system of exploitation and the dynamics of power that characterised this.

This work partly emerged from a desire why the sequential economic development models described in the preceding sections did not really seem to be working in large parts of the world. For instance, in the case of the majority of Africa and South America, the countries did not seem to be following the stages presented in the model in any meaningful way, particularly in terms of making progress through the pre-conditions for take-off and the path to growth (Escobar, 2011). Therefore, there was an effort to explain this discrepancy, not simply to try and fix the sequential model of growth, but to propose new models.

The critical dimension of these models is that they identify the barrier to economic growth as external, not internal; whereas previous models identify the barrier to economic growth as internal conditions of labour supply and technology, the dependency model looks outside (Weaver, 2008). This model argues, in basic form, that many of the poorest nations are physically prevented from developing because they are dependent on richer, more powerful

nations, and those nations have a vested interest in maintaining that power dynamic (Escobar, 2011; Weaver, 2008). This theory initially started from Marxist leanings, but multiple formations have moved away from that toward a more functional understanding of how to deconstruct some of the more malignant forms of dependency. One of the more interesting critiques of this approach is that it suffers from the kind of problems that Derrida noted with any deconstructive approach; there is no point in being able to offer a deconstruction of any social phenomenon unless one can suggest an alternative to replace it (Freeman & Soete, 1997). In the case of theories of dependence, there is a large focus on identifying the systems of exploitation that need to be eradicated, but very little work on suggesting what is to replace them, except that it requires radical state intervention at both the international and domestic levels.

3.2.6 Free Market Ideologies and Neoclassical Theory

The 1980s, the 1990s, and certainly the contemporary period have been marked by a move toward free market ideologies. These are based on the simple premise that the state should have little or no role in economic development, and capitalism should be left to do its thing unhindered. It is argued that unfettered markets are the most effective means of ensuring the efficient means of allocation of capital, and therefore rapid economic expansion (Ghatak, 2003). All of these have been grouped under the broad heading of neoclassical economics, but there are a multitude of theories grouped within this.

The original free-market approach and the public-choice theory are avowedly libertarian approaches that argue that governments are necessarily and fundamentally negative and have no positive factors at all, and therefore any state involvement in the economy is considered inefficient. The market-friendly model has been closely associated with the development economics of the last twenty years, and principally backed by the World Bank (Ghatak, 2003). This model is a broadly open market approach, but with a recognition that developing nations often have inconsistencies and problems that need to be addressed for commerce to flourish, and therefore some limited state intervention in the economy is acceptable (Kapur et al., 2011; Staples & Sayward, 2006). This differs from the previous models as it concentrates on the internal issues within the country.

3.3 TERRITORIAL AND ETHNIC CONSIDERATIONS

Further work has been done to try and determine how different models might be impacted by various aspects of the territory and the people that live within a country. There was some

powerful analysis from Sachs, Mellinger, and Gallup (2001) to the effect that countries that have a coast or navigable waterway appear to develop much faster than those which do not. Similarly, those countries that are in temperate climates seem to develop much quicker than those in the tropics (Sachs et al., 2001). There are some critiques of this theory, on the basis that it works by looking back as opposed to forward, but when considering the future of economic development and contemporary trends such as digitisation and globalisation, the logic seems much less certain.

In addition to this, there has been a vibrant body of work in the twenty-first century on the relationship between ethnic diversity and economic development. Some classical economists are working to see if there is a mathematically identifiable causal link between the diversity of a country and economic development but with very few firm conclusions (Collier, 2007). A second stream of work has taken a more sociological approach, to the extent that there is a theory that the contemporary neoliberal, neoclassical approach to economics exacerbates and potentially inflames ethnic differences, which inhibits economic growth and promotes conflict (Collier, 2007). It can be argued that ethnic diversity does affect the economy, but the extent of its influence is not entirely clear.

3.4 RESOURCES CURSES AND POST-OIL DEVELOPMENT

There is a particular body of work that is pertinent to the case of Algeria because it looks exclusively at countries that are reliant on extractive industries for their income. The resource curse is a body of work that has looked at what happens when a country that has a large resource endowment is unable to develop its economy in a balanced and deliberative way (Humpreys et al., 2007). A common misconception is to assume that the presence of the resource is a curse, but that is not true. The United States, for example, is a huge oil exporter but without a curse as such (Humpreys et al., 2007). The problem lies with the overreliance on a particular resource for growth.

Theories of this include the inequities of the rentier model. This is where the country allows foreign companies to extract the resource, but this is never an equal relationship and is likely to result in the host country receiving only a fraction of the income it should get (Harvey, 2005; Ray, 1998). This is often compounded by corruption and incompetence, and it also leads to countries being dangerously exposed to the cyclical nature of commodity markets (Humpreys et al., 2007). More generally, a resource curse occurs when there is an inability to diversify

away from the extractive industry, so an overwhelming majority of the national income becomes dependent on that resource and therefore completely unbalanced.

Some countries such as Saudi Arabia and the United Arab Emirates (UAE) have begun to explore what comes after a resource-based economy, on the basis that their oil reserves will eventually run dry. This has prompted several debates about the way how that transitional type of economy can be theorised (Humpreys et al., 2007). Saudi Arabia appears to be pursuing a knowledge-based economy approach, while the UAE is trying to become a global travel, entertainment, and real estate hub, but there are very few overarching theories that have been postulated.

3.5 RESEARCH GAP

The overwhelming research gap in the literature is based on the premise that age is under-researched in entrepreneurship generally, as opposed to the wealth of literature on how personal characteristics such as gender or sexuality can impact entrepreneurship. Therefore, studies of youth entrepreneurship are limited, particularly in the case of developing nations like Algeria, and there is a particular lack of empirical validation around key assumptions about the benefits of entrepreneurship in terms of both personal outcomes and the broader context of economic development.

Other sections of this thesis have reviewed literature that covered the Algerian economic landscape in several different ways, primarily focused on exploring the literature on development economics, through mercantilism, linear stages of growth, structural change, dependence, and free-market approaches. It was then demonstrated that the recent economic history of Algeria did not seem to match any of the models in any meaningful way and that there is a need for a particular model of development economics that could help to fuse youth entrepreneurship and development economics that would make sense in the prevailing landscape of Algeria.

The research gap that this thesis aims to explore is that there is no existing piece of research that draws together all these strands of research so that it becomes possible to see how promoting youth entrepreneurship drives economic growth. Arguably, there is a further research gap to be addressed. In pursuing a model of development economics that is free-market and requires entrepreneurs, there is a fundamental assumption that entrepreneurship always and exclusively leads to positive economic outcomes both for the individual and the state, which is quite a broad claim. From the literature review, it is not possible to say what, if any, impact

entrepreneurship might have in solving the economic difficulties of Algeria as a whole even if the proposed model of development economics is very successful. One could argue that this is essentially a scalar issue; the literature that looks at entrepreneurship is quite applicable and considers the practical barriers and enablers for businesspeople and investors. In contrast, the economic development literature is located at the level of abstract systems and metrics like GDP, so the connection between the two is difficult to make.

If one were to compare this literature to literature that considers the impact of entrepreneurship in mature economies like the UK and the US, then one would find that there is a lot of data and associated analysis about the broad impact of entrepreneurs on the current and future economy, and there are metrics that track entrepreneurial activity and can indicate how this will impact on different sectors. The literature review here has offered some explanations on why that is not possible in the context of Algeria, so there is value in attempting to try and quantify and formalise the impact of youth entrepreneurialism in Algeria.

Therefore, there is an opportunity for a piece of work that tries to quantify what the larger impact of entrepreneurship on young people could be. If young entrepreneurs were given the right support, training and then allowed the time to develop experience and scale their businesses, what impact would that have on the economy overall? There is a theoretical argument that this could result in huge economic gains, and help drive competition and efficiency in the market, while also helping address the broader social issues of unemployment, housing, and the issues around large numbers of skilled people emigrating. Therefore, the research objectives specified in the introductory chapter are based on addressing that specific lacuna in the literature.

3.6 A MODEL FOR ALGERIA

The previous sections have considered a variety of different models of economic development that have been postulated for how to make a developing nation a developed nation. There is no suggestion that there is a perfect model or theory that describes these, and the goal of this section is to see what components of these various models seem to have some resonance in the case of Algeria. To achieve that, it is necessary to engage with some of the literature that has sought to provide an analysis of the recent history of the Algerian economy, to see how these apply to these theories.

3.6.1 Understanding the Algerian Economy

Algerian economy, at first glance, may appear like it offers a propitious climate for entrepreneurs and is an example of investing capital returns to achieve economic growth. It is worth noting that the recently resigned President Bouteflika promised a significant expansion of the Algerian economy with more than \$60bn of infrastructure spending on new housing, Algeria's metro system, and a new East-West Highway project, alongside far-reaching reform of both the banking and the hydrocarbon industries (Lloyds Bank, 2019). This would initially appear to be a textbook deployment of the World Bank's market-friendly approach for the state, providing the infrastructure for private businesses to build upon and doing so on a significant scale.

This was designed to transform the Algerian economy, and if one looks at the GDP figures then it would seem to be working. Since 2014, Algeria's economy has enjoyed a growth of between 3% to 4% per annum (Lloyds Bank, 2019). Moreover, if one looks at the non-oil part of the economy, growth has been closer to 6% per annum (Reuters, 2019). Algeria also has a strong foreign currency reserve, and the mid-2000s were characterised by a significant debt relief program following the end of the Algerian civil war (Lefevre, 2017). Moreover, the Algerian economy also has a significant trade surplus, since the oil price has recovered, meaning that there is surplus revenue to invest in economic expansion (Lefevre, 2017). However, if one examines the detail of this economic expansion, then there appear to be several features that are not connected to different aspects of economic development as described in the models above.

While it is undeniably a good thing that the non-oil economy is growing, it has been observed that the percentages can be quite misleading. For instance, more than 70% of all economic activity in Algeria is related to hydrocarbons, with the bulk of that done through state-owned oil companies (Constable, 2019). Moreover, the growth of 4% per annum is not related to any economic activity or policy directed by Algeria; it is a simple manifestation of the global recovery in crude oil prices. However, as several studies have suggested, the Algerian economy is now heavily unbalanced and with no plan for a post-oil economy, and therefore there is an impending collapse within the economic lifetimes of those under 30 (Constable, 2019). In that sense, it is a classic example of the economic development associated with a resource curse.

The literature notes that countries like Saudi Arabia, Kuwait, and United Arab Emirates are investing large amounts of their oil wealth in developing a post-oil economy, as the oil reserves

decline. At the same time, there are global moves to reduce hydrocarbon consumption, and the viability of the oil industry only extends into the medium term (cf. Al-Sabah, 2017; Isik, 2018). Even then, it is acknowledged in the literature that there is no certainty that these oil-reliant countries have acted quickly enough, or whether they will be successful in transitioning their economies (Isik, 2018). The challenge with Algeria is that there is no clear effort from the government to think beyond the funds generated by the oil industry (Constable, 2019). It is difficult to model exactly what the impacts on the Algerian population would be if the oil revenue were to decline rapidly, but it has been theorised to be catastrophic (Aljazeera, 2019). Thus, it is a matter of urgency for the Algerian economy.

While much of the capital investment in Algerian infrastructure took place, there is significant doubt over the impact that it has had on the overall health of the economy. There is a desperate shortage of housing in the country; while the government has pledged to add 2m units to the country's stock of 8.5m (of which 50% are state managed), they have encountered significant tax rises on the property and banned the import of building materials (Oxford Business Group, 2018). Unemployment is running at a high rate of 11%, while the public sector is the second largest employer in the country, meaning that the commercial economy accounts for a comparatively small amount of employment (Reuters, 2019). This is in contrast to some of the market development theories because the Algerian public is far from persuaded that economic development of this kind is the right thing to do for their country. Ultimately, the sequential stages of growth models are free market in orientation, as they do not work for the majority of economic activity.

It has been argued in several studies that the large number of people employed in the public sector is a deliberate strategy on the part of the government to pacify large numbers of people; putting them on the public payroll is a fast way to quiet discontent and foster a large percentage of the population that is likely to support the government (cf. Lorch & Bunk, 2017; Oxford Business Group, 2018). This has a reciprocal effect on the economy, because all these people need to be kept in employment, and part of the bureaucratic burden on the economy is simply keeping the large volume of public sector workers occupied. This could be argued to be a perverse kind of dependence model of economic growth, but again the primary role of the state is inexplicable in light of the literature presented earlier in the chapter.

It has been noted that a lack of reform has badly harmed the economy in terms of attracting foreign investors. Algerian law enforces a 49:51 rule on foreign investors, such that any

business must be at least 51% owned by Algerians (Oxford Business Group, 2018; 2019). This is a huge deterrent to foreign investors, and there has been a reform mooted on many occasions, but with little action. The state controls the reach of the media and banking sectors, which means that there are entire industries where foreign investors cannot invest. Again, it is very hard to reconcile this with any of the models of development economics discussed in this chapter.

As a result of the centralized economy and lack of genuine opportunities, this created a huge informal and dark economy in Algeria. Temlali (2019) provided a comprehensive overview of the difficulty of trying to quantify a dark economy; by its very nature, it is impossible to accurately locate. Nonetheless, Temlali (2019) noted that it is possible to trace a significant number of people back to economic reforms in the mid-1990s when up to 800 state-owned companies were closed down and around half a million people were made unemployed. Temlali (2019) noted that estimates of the size of the informal economy vary between \$20bn and \$40bn and that the lack of sustained research by the government into this means that there can never be any certainty. Indeed, it is noted that the informal economy is something that the government has appeared to encourage as a mechanism for mitigating social problems and the outcome of their more extreme economy. For example, Temlali (2019) noted that there are huge differences between the official exchange rate for Algerian dinars and foreign currencies and the ones available within the informal economy. Temlali (2019) claimed that the state is aware of this, and tacitly encourages it as an economic facilitator. Further, although the state owns most of the housing, it has allowed the majority of tenancies to be arranged on the black market through unlicensed and unregulated intermediaries because it has provided a highly effective buffer as the tax rises have made housing increasingly unaffordable (Lorch & Bunk, 2017; Oxford Business Group, 2018). It is worth remarking that this is supported by the literature on post-conflict economies. For example, Kosovo has a very large unofficial economy, and regularizing that would be critical to economic growth.

3.6.2 Developing a Conceptual Model of Economic Development and Youth Entrepreneurship for Algeria

Based on the literature presented, it is necessary to suggest a model of development economics that might assist in understanding the dimensions of the Algerian economy and demonstrating the importance of looking at youth entrepreneurship. As the previous section noted, Algeria is very hard to reconcile with most of the popular models of development economics. There is evidence of a resource curse, but the remainder of the models discussed in previous sections rely on a broadly free-market approach, while Algeria is state dominated. One could make a case for a dependency model, in the sense that Algeria is a post-colonial state and is kept in check by its dependence on the oil price, but this seems to be inapplicable in the Algerian context. Moreover, none of these models appear to have any connection to the experiences of young entrepreneurs and the nascent scene of start-ups in Algeria. There is almost no way of connecting these ideas of development economics with the material on entrepreneurship; and therefore, no way of suggesting how Algeria might profitably harness this entrepreneurial desire to derive a model of economic development. Therefore, this thesis can set out to try and analyse a model of economic development that has the following core components:

Figure 3.5: Conceptual Model of Entrepreneurship & Economic Growth for Algeria

Note: Developed by Osmani Abderrezzak (2023) based on previous literature

- The first point is that young entrepreneurs represent the vanguard of the change in sentiment described in the sequential models of economic development, whereby

people want to take on risk with a reinvestment rather than consumption orientation. They view this idea of economic development as preferable to all other available options. The first stage in the model is when this cohort starts to emerge, being given some impetus by the things described in this literature review, but still constrained by the exigent political system and economic structures

- Rather than emerging from an agrarian society, this development economics is based on a move away from state control. The mechanism is the same, in that the desire is to move from a system that has large amounts of surplus labour and capital, to redistribute more efficiently, and use reinvestment to achieve rapid economic growth. This requires the withdrawal of the Algerian state from the economy, as there is evidence of internet-enabled and post-oil opportunities emerging, alongside entrepreneurship mentoring.
- The proposal model seeks to address in detail what the motor of economic development is. It was noted in the introductory paragraphs that this thesis intends to use Drucker's model of opportunity-based entrepreneurship, which states that entrepreneurs respond to an opportunity created by a stimulus. It is what drives that change in attitudes, technology, and outlook that causes a country to move through a sequence of stages of economic development. It is assumed that there is an eventual tipping point, when the number of opportunities becomes self-sustaining, and a compounding effect occurs, where there is a rapid period of growth as opportunities become very frequent.
- The final stage of the model suggests that there is a reciprocal element where the desire to reinvest rather than consume helps the compounding of opportunities for further opportunity development, which creates the conditions for prolonged economic growth. In this case, because of the highly unique status of Algeria as a resource-cursed, state-controlled, post-conflict, and post-colonial nation, the model starts with a hypothesis that young entrepreneurs will be the first, or otherwise most likely, to respond to an opportunity created by some kind of stimulus, as described by Drucker.

Therefore, the proposed model is a hybrid of several models. The essential architecture of the model is that it is both sequential and free-market in outlook, but it tries to incorporate aspects of other development economic models such as resource-curses, post-conflict, and Drucker's opportunity model, to present a much more sophisticated take on how Algeria might develop into the future.

3.7 CONCLUSION

This literature review has sought to provide a context for the research objectives specified in the opening chapter of the thesis and to demonstrate a research gap within that literature. The opening sections noted that there was a particular issue within the existing theories of entrepreneurship, which means that age has not been considered in any detail as a predictive variable in the experiences, needs, or outcomes of entrepreneurs. On the other hand, characteristics such as gender, ethnicity, or sexuality are comparatively well-researched. Therefore, there are several under-researched debates on whether entrepreneurship is a good thing for young people in developing nations, and whether their experiences can be uniform.

Most of the literature review examined scholarly work on the barriers and enablers of entrepreneurship, with a particular focus on the availability of capital, corruption and the rule of law, bureaucracy, gender discrimination, soft skills, policy, social change, and processes of globalisation. The research gap was specifically identified as a lack of connection between literature that engages with the development of entrepreneurship and that which considers the overall development of the Algerian economy, particularly in the post-oil landscape. There is a need for research that considers what supporting young entrepreneurs can bring to economic development and in terms of technical skills development. The literature review has provided a comprehensive overview of the Algerian economy, and the current predicaments of young people within the country, and therefore specified how this project can offer to close some of the research gaps.

The overall effect of that should be to demonstrate that Algeria is a country undergoing a fast-paced change and that entrepreneurship and economic development are never static. Therefore, the review has shown that the literature in the field is always lacking the focus on the events on the ground. Therefore, one of the ambitions of the subsequent analysis in this thesis is not simply to describe the potential impact of entrepreneurship in Algeria, but to try and place that within the trajectory of development in Algeria so that it captures the inherent fluidity of both the country and the subject matter.

Figure 3.6: Final Proposed Conceptual Model of Economic Development in Algeria

Note: Developed by Osmani Abderrezzak (2023) based on previous literature

CHAPTER FOUR

METHODOLOGY

This methodology details how a model of youth entrepreneurship was developed and contextualised in support of the research objectives set out in the first chapter of the thesis. The chapter proceeds through considering the development of a research methodology that starts at the very broadest scale with the development of a research philosophy, and then focuses down through the applied research design and then to the mechanics of data collection and analysis, as well as the ethical considerations of the thesis.

4.1 RESEARCH QUESTIONS AND RESEARCH STRATEGY

4.1.1 Research Questions

The thesis is guided by two key research questions:

RQ1: What can be done to engage the youth in small business entrepreneurship across Algeria and thus implement a sustainable solution to the country's unemployment problem?

RQ2: How to connect the development of entrepreneurship and the overall development of the Algerian economy, particularly in the post-oil landscape?

4.1.2. Research Strategy

When addressing a research question there is an almost innumerable array of methods that could be utilised, and sometimes there is a challenge in selecting the one most appropriate for the extant research objectives. The research onion is a popular and simple way of visualising all the options available, to ensure that all the stages are properly considered and connected coherently (Saunders et al., 2009). Figure 4.1 presents the image of the research onion.

Figure 4.1: The Research Onion

Note: Derived from “Research methods for business students” by Saunders, M., Lewis, P. & Thornhill, A. (2009), p. 108

The research onion is not didactic; it is designed to assist the researcher in putting together the right structure, rather than promote a specific research strategy. The key is to find the most appropriate means of addressing research objectives, as there is no absolute right or absolute wrong ways to address them. The researcher will refer to the strategies outlined in the research onion throughout this chapter.

4.2 RESEARCH PHILOSOPHY

The research philosophy is the set of assumptions about how the world exists, at least for research, and therefore how the research environment is conceptualised (Bryman, 2015). It is an oversimplification to present that issue as a range between positivism and interpretivism, but it offers a useful means of framing the choices available (Jones, Bradbury & LeBoutillier, 2011). Research philosophy is typically composed of ontology and epistemology (Bryman, 2015). Guba and Lincoln (1994) as well as Sexton (2003), suggested that the contrasting issues on philosophies found in the literature are determined by the different views based on the

assumptions of ontology, epistemology, and axiology. All three philosophies will be discussed in the next sections.

4.2.1 Ontology

Ontology is a theory of how the world exists; what it is composed of, and the fundamental components of the research environment. On the other hand, positivism relates to the importance of what exists in general, with a stricter focus to consider pure data as well as facts without being influenced by interpretation and human bias (Saunders et al., 2012; Scotland, 2012). A positivist ontology holds the belief that the world exists independently of human beings; the world that is composed of real, factual elements that exist whether or not human beings coexist with them (Jones et al., 2011). A positive ontology believes that the world is purely external and that there is a single objective reality to any research phenomenon or situation regardless of the researcher's perspective or belief (Carson et al., 1988; Hudson & Ozanne, 1988). Table 4.1 offers a summary of ontology.

Table 4.1: The positivism research philosophy

Ontology (nature of reality or being)	Epistemology (what constitutes acceptable knowledge)	Axiology (role of values)	Typical methods
Real, external, independent One true reality (universalism) Granular (things) Ordered	Scientific method Observable and measurable facts Law-like generalisations Numbers Causal explanation and prediction as contribution	Value-free research Researcher is detached, neutral and independent of what is researched Researcher maintains an objective's stance	Typically deductive, highly structured, large samples, measurement, typically quantitative methods of analysis, but a range of data can be analysed

Note: Derived from "Research methods for business students" by Saunders, M., Lewis, P. & Thornhill, A. (2009), p. 119

In contrast, an interpretivist ontology starts from the proposition that nothing exists outside of the ability of human beings to name or classify events; without that capability, nothing can be a part of human existence (Jones et al., 2011). It is very important to observe that this assumption is not a matter of faith or any political position and should not be accepted uncritically; it is a theory of ontology that is adopted to advance a research methodology (Bryman, 2015). Miller et al. (2010) claimed that knowledge without a positivist foundation is invalid and unclear. The researcher's ontology of choice, based on the analysis above, is that of positivism.

4.2.2 Epistemology

Epistemology is a theory of knowledge, or how it is possible to come to know the ontological substance of the world. Positivist ontologies tend to lean toward empiricist epistemologies. Thus, if one believes that the world is composed of real, independently verifiable facts, then those facts come to be known through a process of collecting data such that a stock of communal knowledge is built (Bryman, 2015). This is best exemplified through the scientific method; a process of developing and verifying or falsifying theory through hypothesis testing, such that over time an ever-larger stock of knowledge is developed.

In contrast, an interpretivist ontology tends to lean toward a deconstructionist epistemology; that is, the world becomes known through a process of interrogating the discursive structures that constitute the world (Gilbert, 1992). Durkheim advanced a theory of social facts, where language and discourse can elevate some social constructs to the status of facts, and other constructs are marginalised (Burr, 2015; Gilbert, 1992). Thus, the business of research is

interrogating these constructs to see the underlying relations of power that enable particular social constructions to endure.

The research onion has another category of research philosophy, which is pragmatism. It is very difficult to pursue a research strategy that is purely positivist or purely interpretivist when conducting research projects in the social sciences and business (Jones et al., 2011). One consideration is that a narrow research approach may not properly address the research objectives as thoroughly as required. A second consideration is that the practicalities of conducting field research, particularly at the postgraduate level, are such that researchers have to work with the art of the possible, and that often means that research needs to combine positivist and interpretivist approaches (Jones et al., 2011). Thus, the pragmatic approach appears to be the most appropriate for this purpose.

This should not be considered to compromise the quality of the research. It can be argued that a pragmatic, mixed-methods approach for social sciences and business yields more insightful data, and that the balance of quantitative and qualitative data structures tends to help make research both descriptive and diagnostic. The current research starts from the pragmatist perspective; advancing the model of youth entrepreneurship is something that requires different data forms and a careful approach to research design since the objects of analysis are slightly elusive.

4.2.3 Axiology

Axiology is the science of inquiry into human values. This inquiry enables people to identify the internal valuing systems that influence their perceptions, decisions, and actions, and to clearly understand, “What do I value? How do I value, and how do I make value decisions?” (Schoof, 1999). Axiology is the science of people’s choice of fundamental values (Engle, 2009). Moreover, axiology helps people clarify their prejudices and biases. It measures how people think and perceive things rather than what they are thinking (Hartman, 1967; Schoof, 1999). Natural science explains human behaviour, and axiology explains and measures the thinking and the valuing process that forms the foundation for, and leads to, human behaviour.

4.2.4. Theoretical Background

To better understand, examine, and explain the significance of youth entrepreneurship in conjunction with the research problem, key questions, and objectives, the study uses the opportunity-based theory of Peter Drucker and the impact analysis theory. In principle, the opportunity-based theory posits that entrepreneurship represents a response to a stimulus, through a business venture, where an unemployed person exploits opportunities engendered by social, technological, and cultural changes in the environment. The impact analysis theory is a paradigm that deconstructs the causes and effects of a phenomenon (in this case, youth entrepreneurship) to afford greater understanding and appreciation of the research agenda while providing an indicative assessment of the overall impact of the issue. Both theories will be used together to analyse the phenomenon of youth entrepreneurship in Algeria.

Essentially, Drucker explains how economic development happens; the original model appears to suggest that economic development occurs apropos of nothing; surplus labour and technological development in manufacturing appear to happen by itself. Drucker's model suggests that there is a particular group of people, entrepreneurs, who see the opportunity in technological and societal change and have the impetus to convert that into new businesses. The conceptual model for this thesis aims to take that a step further and consider the specific context of post-oil countries (in this case, Algeria), and whether there are specific types of entrepreneurs that are best equipped to identify and seize these opportunities.

4.3 RESEARCH DESIGN

There are generally two approaches to reasoning that underpin most research projects. **Deductive reasoning** is where one takes a broad theory and seeks to apply it within a specific research context. When using deductive reasoning, the researcher relies on the existing theory and formulates their hypotheses based on that theory. Depending on the outcomes of their study, the hypotheses are either rejected or approved. In contrast, **inductive reasoning** is where one intends to use the data from the study to generate a new theory which can then be generalized more widely. Inductive reasoning begins with the researcher making specific observations about their phenomenon of interest, recognizing specific patterns, and making general conclusions based on that (Creswell, 2013).

In this case, the thesis is a form of inductive reasoning, because the intention is to generate a new theory from the evidence gathered in the specific research context of Algerian youth entrepreneurship. Abstractive reasoning occurs where the linear process described above, broad

to specific and vice versa, does not fit with the practicalities of the research project (Creswell, 2013). Abstractive reasoning is where the researcher cannot reach a single, discrete conclusion, but instead forms a conclusion by taking multiple pieces of data and forming a conclusion on the balance of the probabilities and their judgement, typical of mixed-method studies (Creswell, 2013). That was the research design pursued here, as the researcher focuses on a specific (previously unexplored) group within the Algerian context, intending to develop a new theory.

4.3.1 Research Method Choices

The research method choices refer to the method used in collecting and analysing the research data. This research is using a mixed-methods design to collect and analyse data using a questionnaire and interviews.

Table 4.2: Quantitative Versus Qualitative Methods

Quantitative Research	Qualitative Research
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Produces statistical data • Where random probability samples are used, survey estimates can be defined within specified bound of precision • Can measure the extent, prevalence, size and strength of observed characteristics, differences, relationship and association • Can determine the importance of factors influencing customers • Uses standardised procedures and questions, enabling the reproducibility of results. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Flexible • Enables the exploration of the meaning of concepts and events • Produces valid data as issues as explored in sufficient depth to provide a clear understanding • Enables the study of motivations and patterns of association between factors • Provides a detailed understanding of how individuals interact with their environment or cope with change.

Source: Davies, 2007, p .9

The study uses qualitative and quantitative data based on the analysis of findings from the interviews and the questionnaire. Although some of the data collected from questionnaire will be numerical/categorical, the researcher will qualitatively analyse the data. Through analysing the interviews using Braun and Clarke's (2006) six-step thematic analysis, the researcher will be able to code repeated patterns and themes from the participants, and this will allow the researcher to develop a new theory about this phenomenon. This method allows the researcher to develop a new theory, which can be later tested by other researchers in the future through hypotheses. The mixed-methods approach is the most appropriate for this type of research, as young Algerian entrepreneurs are not a widely studied group in the research context. The goal behind using both methods of data collection is to maximise the amount of information that the researcher can attain from the respondents. The goal of the questionnaire is to collect key

information about the participants, while the interviews are designed to build on the respondents' answers from the questionnaire.

4.3.1.1. Participant Sampling

It would be possible to create a randomised sample of participants for the interview process, such that a cross-sectional study could be completed (Creswell, 2013). However, the nature of the research environment means that the researcher had to contend with several issues surrounding access and gatekeepers to potential research participants, again meaning that the researcher was required to work with what was available rather than what was desired (Cohen et al., 2011). The sampling methodology was a snowballing technique. The sample of respondents was created based on submitting the questionnaire to an initial group of respondents that the researcher knew personally, who then shared the questionnaire with their own networks. When trying to engage governmental institutions gatekeepers and access to respondents is the most significant challenge, particularly for a postgraduate student conducting an independent research study (Glesne, 2015). The first step in the process was to draw up a set of institutions in Algeria that were involved in economic development and entrepreneurship, and who would make reasonable targets for an interview. These are outlined in the list below:

- Ministry of Training and Professional Education
- Ministry of Education
- Ministry of Start-ups
- Ministry of Industry
- Ministry of Finance
- Ministry of Commerce
- Ministry of Tourism
- Ministry of Public Works, Infrastructure Development and Water
- National Agency of Investment Development (ANDI)
- Agence Algerienne de Promotion du Commerce Exterieur (ALGEX)

Once specific organisations were selected, the researcher had to target each organisation individually. The researcher selected the organisations based on his network, as he knows individuals working in these organisations that could be invited for an interview. The researcher had access to some of his personal contacts within relevant institutions from his work

experience as a CEO of the UK Algeria Business Council, and some of those contacts were able to refer to their own contacts, thus creating a snowballing effect. The interviews were conducted in public places away from the work premises of each respondent. This was done to reassure the participants that the project held little risk for their employment. Initially there were some difficulties in getting enough respondents to agree to take part, which appeared to stem from concerns over potential repercussions in the event that their answers would not be approved of by the government; that is the nature of the public sector in Algeria. Therefore, the approach was modified to focus on absolute anonymity, and potential respondents were approached in person as opposed to via email to minimize potential tracking. In total, ten people from the institutions that were involved in economic development and entrepreneurship consented to take part in an interview.

4.3.1.2 Mixed-Methods

This study will adopt a mixed-methods approach. The description of the strengths and weaknesses of mixed-methods approach are presented in Table 4.3 below

Table 4.3: Strengths and weakness of mixed research method

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Words, pictures and narrative can be used to add meaning to numbers• Numbers can be used to add precision to words, pictures, and narrative.• Can provide quantitative and qualitative research strengths• Researcher can generate and test a grounded theory• Can answer a broader and more complete range of research questions because the researcher is not confined to a single method or approach • A researcher can use the strengths of an additional method to overcome the weaknesses in another method by using both in a research study• Can provide stronger evidence for a conclusion through convergence and corroboration of findings.• Can add insights and understanding that might be missed when only a single method is used• Can be used to increase the generalisability of the results• Qualitative and quantitative research used together produce more complete knowledge necessary to inform theory and practice	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Can be difficult for a single researcher to carry out both qualitative and quantitative research, especially if two or more approaches are expected to be used currently; it may require a research team.• Researcher has to learn about multiple methods and approaches and understand how to mix them appropriately, researcher is not confined to a single method or approach.• Methodological purists contend that one should always work within either a qualitative or quantitative paradigm.• More expensive.• More time consuming• Some of the details of mixed research remain to be worked out fully by research methodologist (e.g., problems of Paradigm mixing, how to qualitatively analyse quantitative data, and how to interpret conflicting results).

Note: Derived from “Toward a definition of mixed methods research” by Jonson, R. B., A. J. Onwuegbuzie, et al. (2007) in *Journal of Mixed Methods Research*, vol.1(2), p. 21.

4.4 DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

The data collection process for this thesis was composed of two parts. The first was a questionnaire that was distributed to as many respondents as possible, to capture a broad set of data that could be converted into a set of dependent and independent variables. The second stage was a set of semi-structured interviews with people in the government of Algeria, with broad responsibility for promoting business and entrepreneurship to provide greater contextual data on the types of opportunities that are available to Algerian entrepreneurs.

4.4.1 Quantitative Data Collection

4.4.1.1 Questionnaire Design

The complete questionnaire is included in Appendix 4 of this thesis. The questionnaire design was intended to offer as much focus as possible while simultaneously maximising the response rate. The literature demonstrates that long surveys experience high drop-off rates, meaning incomplete answers which are later difficult to analyse (Walliman, 2017). When designing the questionnaire, the researcher was mindful of the fact that many respondents would not have previously given immediate thought to starting a business, so the questions were designed to be quite simple in terms of the level of complexity required (Walliman, 2017). A five-point Likert scale has been previously criticised that it allows for a median answer, and that can often be interpreted either as a 'neutral' or a 'not applicable' answer, or something that can be used if the respondent does not understand the question or prefers not to give the true response (Walliman, 2017). However, for a survey of this type, it was necessary to try and capture a median response where the respondent genuinely had an ambivalent response, so the five-point Likert scale was preferred to a four-point Likert scale, which would have required them to select either a positive or a negative response.

4.4.1.2 Questionnaire structure

The questionnaire was designed around measuring three distinct constructs: demographic profiling, entrepreneurial intent, and entrepreneurial readiness. Each of the constructs measured different variables presented below:

- Demographic profiling - Age, sex, sector, and lived abroad,
- Entrepreneurial intent - Outlook for entrepreneurs, number of opportunities as an entrepreneur, Algeria as a good place to invest, and growth of the non-oil economy in the next 10 years,
- Entrepreneurial readiness - Interest in attending an entrepreneurial course, level of preparedness of friends and peers to set up a business, the likelihood of setting up a

business in the next two years, feeling prepared to set up a business now, having an existing business in Algeria.

The structure of the survey was designed to generate a specific type of data set for analysis, specifically those that indicate 'Entrepreneurial intent' or 'Entrepreneurial readiness.' It would have been possible to produce a weighted average of responses for the dependent variables analytically, but the fundamental problem with that approach is that it assumes that the researcher already knows what the appropriate data structure is, whereas the weighting could inculcate all kinds of bias. Therefore, the questions were designed to capture a very broad field of information about entrepreneurial activity, knowledge, and enthusiasm, to then submit the broad data set to a range of testing techniques which could then ensure that the weighted average used for the dependent constructs is the most accurate representation of the data possible.

The questionnaire was limited in length due to concerns about the completion rate, and so a three-part structure was considered to be the most effective means of collecting the necessary information (Iarossi, 2006). The demographic profiling questions were focused on age, as a key component of the hypotheses, as well as gender, the current sector of employment, and previous exposure to living abroad. The subsequent two sections were scale-level questions intending to measure responses to a set of statements.

4.4.1.3 Instrumentation

The demographic profiling questions were built around unscaled responses, as these answers are not measured. Questions two and three were built using a Likert scale. A Likert item is a statement or a proposition that the respondent is asked to evaluate through a set of quantitative responses that are arranged in a bipolar order (Iarossi, 2006). Most Likert questions are fashioned around a bipolar scale of agreement; strongly agree to strongly disagree, but any properly ordered scale could be used. A crucial component of a Likert scale is that it is symmetrical, in that there are equal numbers of positive and negative responses to the proposition; second the scale should be balanced such that there is equal 'distance' between the responses, in terms of the severity of the response that they indicate (Iarossi, 2006). Likert scales can be devised around an even point scale, where there is no option to give a neutral response to the proposition; this is often referred to as a 'forced choice' model and is often used where the content of the proposition is considered contentious or socially revealing, and the researcher wants to avoid a centrality bias from the respondent, which is where the respondent

desires to be seen as ‘normal’ (Iarossi, 2006). In this case, the propositions were not considered socially contentious, so an even-point scale was not considered appropriate.

Table: 4.4 Instrumentation of research

ABBREVIATED QUESTION	CONSTRUCT	SCALE	RATIONALE
Age	Demographic Profiling	Non-Scalar Answer	Need to understand how responses vary between different sections of the population.
Sex	Demographic Profiling	Non-Scalar Answer	Need to understand how responses vary between different sections of the population.
Sector	Demographic Profiling	Non-Scalar Answer	Need to understand how responses vary between different sections of the population.
Lived Abroad	Demographic Profiling	Non-Scalar Answer	Need to understand how responses vary between different sections of the population.
Outlook for Entrepreneurs?	Entrepreneurial Intent	Five-Point Likert Scale. Very Poor to Very Good.	Designed to generate a response about the way they perceive opportunities in general in a changing economy.
Number of Opportunities for Entrepreneurs?	Entrepreneurial Intent	Five-Point Likert Scale. Very Few to Very Many.	Designed to get a more specific response on the number of opportunities arising.
Is Algeria a good place to invest?	Entrepreneurial Intent	Five-Point Likert Scale. Very Poor to Very Good.	Designed to provide an insight into broad thought about economic environment.
How much will non-oil economy in Algeria grow over next 10 years?	Entrepreneurial Intent	Five-Point Likert Scale. Very Little to Very Much.	Designed to provide an insight into broad thought about economic environment; also, to acquire insight into the level of knowledge about the economy.
Would you be interested in attending an entrepreneurship course?	Entrepreneurial Readiness	Five-Point Likert Scale. Not Interested at All to Very Interested.	Designed to understand the desire for immediate practical steps toward entrepreneurship.
How well prepared are your friends and peers to set up a business?	Entrepreneurial Readiness	Five Point Likert Scale. Very Unprepared to Very Prepared.	Designed to understand the extent to which entrepreneurship is discussed and validated as an option.
How likely are you to set up a business in the next two years?	Entrepreneurial Readiness	Five Point Likert Scale. Very Unlikely to Very Likely.	Straight question to determine entrepreneurial intent.
Do you feel that you have everything required to set up a business now?	Entrepreneurial Readiness	Five Point Likert Scale. Nothing required to having everything required.	Designed to generate insight into hesitancy or barriers to immediately starting up a business.
Have you set up a business already?	Entrepreneurial Readiness	Non-Scalar Answer.	Need to straight answers between those with an existing record of entrepreneurship.

Note: Developed by Osmani Abderrezzak- the researcher

4.4.1.4 Questionnaire Distribution

The questionnaire (Figure 4.2) was distributed to respondents via Google Forms, such that it could easily be shared on social media and by email to make it as easy as possible to maximise the number of responses. The data collection process was relatively straightforward; the researcher has a broad array of friends and associates in the governmental sector of Algeria, and the survey link was distributed by what might be called a snowball sampling technique, where each respondent is asked to share the survey link with their peers via email and social media. The researcher contacted his immediate contacts and asked them to complete the survey. Once completed, the researcher asked each respondent he knew personally to forward to at least five other relevant participants.

Figure 4.2: Questionnaire for Youth Entrepreneurship

1- Have you ever thought about starting a business and becoming self-employed?
 Yes No

2- What stops you from starting your own business and becoming self-employed?
 Finance
 Time
 Lack of information and support

3- What support would you like to receive in order to start your own business?
 Mentoring & Coaching
 Loans & Grants
 Business training course
 - If other, please specify. Short-answer text.....

4- In order to address your needs, how important is it for you to use the following services?
 1= Not at all likely 2=Slightly Likely 3=Moderately Likely 4= Very Likely 5=Extremely likely

4.1- Assistance with writing a business plan

	1	2	3	4	5
Not at all likely	<input type="checkbox"/>				
					Extremely likely

4.2- Assistance with access to external finance

	1	2	3	4	5
Not at all likely	<input type="checkbox"/>				
					Extremely likely

4.3- Assistance with specialised mentoring & coaching courses

	1	2	3	4	5
Not at all likely	<input type="checkbox"/>				
					Extremely likely

4.4- Assistance with managing the business

	1	2	3	4	5
Not at all likely	<input type="checkbox"/>				
					Extremely likely

4.5- Workshop-networking, exhibition and promotion Events for North Africa Entrepreneurship

	1	2	3	4	5
Not at all likely	<input type="checkbox"/>				
					Extremely likely

Note: Developed by Osmani Abderrezzak-the researcher

4.4.1.5 Data Analysis and Validity

The data collected from the questionnaires will be either categorical or numerical. However, the researcher will analyse the data using the descriptive method, by simply describing what he can see from the findings. This analysis would involve categorising the findings into three different constructs: demographic profiling, entrepreneurial intent, and entrepreneurial readiness. For each construct, the researcher will simply describe what the findings tell him using the Google Forms data analysis tool. To increase the validity of his data collection, the researcher made sure that each of the questions measured the intended variable and avoided any crossovers between the constructs. This was achieved by developing a questionnaire and testing it on 20 classmates before submitting it to the respondents. The researcher also ensured to send the questionnaire to a larger sample size to ensure greater representativeness. To avoid the common method bias the researcher ensured to avoid complex and ambiguous items in his questionnaire, kept the questions concise, as well as ensuring the anonymity of responses.

4.4.2 Research Direction and Qualitative Data

With regards to the qualitative data collection, the study used an interview guide. A detailed explanation is presented in the following research direction table:

Table 4.5: Research Direction

Aim	Research Questions	Research Objectives	Related Interview Question
To investigate how to engage youth in small business entrepreneurship across Algeria and how to connect the development of entrepreneurship and the overall development of the Algerian economy in the post-oil landscape.	RQ1. What can be done to engage the youth in small business entrepreneurship across Algeria and thus implement a sustainable solution to the country's unemployment problem?	RO1. To explore the general economic and youth unemployment situation in Algeria, including its socio-economic impact	Q1-How important is youth entrepreneurship to the economic development of Algeria?
		RO2. To discuss the youth attitude toward entrepreneurship and what they have done so far to secure economic activity	Q5-Does the government has business development and training programs for local communities in schools and colleges to promote the personal growth and confidence of entrepreneurs?
	RQ2. How to connect the development of entrepreneurship and the overall development of the Algerian economy, particularly in the post-oil landscape?	RO3. To explicate the benefits of youth entrepreneurship in the Algerian context	Q2-Is the present business environment in Algeria favourable for entrepreneurship to thrive in?
		RO4.To identify and discuss the barriers to youth entrepreneurship/business start-ups	Q6-Are finances easy to access for young entrepreneurs wanting to start a business in Algeria?
		RO5. To evaluate the overall impact of government actions and programs on youth entrepreneurship based on the effectiveness of these programs in promoting more entrepreneurship/business start-ups in Algeria.	Q4- How is the government supporting and encouraging youth entrepreneurship in Algeria?
		RO6. To identify key prescriptions for sustainability	Q3-Is youth entrepreneurship high on Algeria's political

		and development initiatives on youth entrepreneurship	agenda as a tool to combat youth unemployment and social exclusion as well as stimulate innovation among young people?
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Note: Table created by Osmani Abderrezzak- the researcher

Interviews are a good method of collecting in-depth qualitative information from the participants. Face-to-face interviews are useful in gathering data that allows the researcher to explore a particular phenomenon in detail, as well as help generate a new theory (Kahn & Cannell, 1957). Hox and De Leeuw (1994) found that the face-to-face interview had the highest percentage of research question completion rate, as opposed to questionnaires. Thus, not only is this data collection method appropriate for this study. It is also the one most likely to yield the highest response rate from the respondents.

Interviews have an advantage over other data collection methods in terms of fewer limitations on the types and number of questions, and the ability to use visual aids. Although one-to-one interviews can be costly and time-consuming, they are valuable because the researcher can use visual aids and script the interviews with observations, and explore all interesting points (a copy of the interview guide is presented in Appendix 2). The following table explains the reasons behind asking specific questions.

Table 4.6: Explanation of Questions Relating to Interview Guide

Question	Reason for asking the question
Q1. How important is youth entrepreneurship to the economic development of Algeria?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Job creation • Improvement of the standard of living • Creates social change • Drives change and innovation
Q2. Is the present business environment favourable for entrepreneurship to thrive in Algeria?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Internal environment <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Entrepreneurs -Managers -Workers -Customers • External environment <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Economic -Political, Legal, Technological -Demographic, Social -Competition -Global
Q3. Is youth entrepreneurship high on Algeria's political agenda as a tool to combat youth unemployment and social exclusion as well as stimulate innovation among young people?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Entrepreneurial learning • Entrepreneurial culture • Start-up support • Career guidance • Mentoring

<p>Q4. How is the government supporting and encouraging youth entrepreneurship in Algeria?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Building a good business environment • Making it easier to access different financing options • Supporting the transition from education to start-up and beyond • Programmes involving training and mentoring services, especially through good practice peer learning. • Copyright, Patent & Trademark Regulation
<p>Q5. Does the government have business development and training programs for local communities in schools and colleges to promote the personal growth and confidence of entrepreneurs?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supporting the nation's innovators • National enterprise academies • Young entrepreneurs' society/schools and colleges • Policy design and delivery • Networking
<p>Q6. Are finances easy to access for young entrepreneurs in Algeria?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial systems and banking structure in Algeria • Grants and subsidies • Finance counselling and assistance • Soft loans and microfinance • Venture capital and angel investors

Note: Table created by Osmani Abderrezzak-the researcher

4.4.2.1 Qualitative Fieldwork

The sample size for the semi-structured interviews was between 10-15 individuals. All participants were the same individuals that had previously completed the questionnaire in this study. After the questionnaire was completed, the researcher invited all respondents to take part in the interviews. He estimated a response from between 10-15 individuals. If that number was not reached, the researcher would invite more respondents from his network.

All interviews were conducted in person and in public places. The interviews were recorded by the researcher for post-interview transcription. The interviews all followed a semi-structured format, meaning that although the same set of questions was asked of each participant, the researcher had the freedom to ask additional questions as and when needed based on the respondents' answers (Dearnley, 2005). The benefit of semi-structured interviews over unstructured interviews or structured interviews is that there is a balance between ensuring that the same questions are asked so that there is a reasonable prospect of comparison of the answers between respondents, and also allowing respondents to pursue points where they want to (King & Horrocks, 2010; Seidman, 2013). Each respondent was asked, during the interview, the same questions as shown in Appendix Two, with each interview lasting between 30 and 40 minutes depending on the length of their answers.

Table 4.7 Profile of the Interviewees

No	Type of institution	Type of sector and activities	Position
1	Ministry of Youth and Sport	Develop and empower the youth	Ministry advisor/ Spend over 20 years as a civil servant
2	Ministry of Finance	Government finances, economic policy and financial regulation.	Head of staff/ Chef de cabinet
3	Ministry of Commerce	Formulating administrative regulations and policies.	Head of staff/ Chef de cabinet
4	Ministry of Industry	Overseeing the economic development and corporate affairs department of the Government of Algeria including Innovation, Science	Director of department
5	Ministry for Knowledge Economy and Start-ups	New ideas, products, services, and business models not only modernise the economic structure, but also create new jobs.	Ministry of start-ups
6	Ministry of training and professional education	Vocational education	Senior manager
7	ALGEX	Promotion of international commerce and exports	Senior manager.

Note: Developed by Osmani Abderrezak- the researcher

4.4.2.2. Reliability and Validity

As qualitative data is often highly subjective, it becomes more challenging to manage reliability and validity. However, the researcher took several steps to maintain reliability. First, the researcher used the reliable and tested six-step thematic analysis technique by Braun and Clarke (2006) when analysing the data, which required him to run the analysis of the themes twice before finalising them. Second, the researcher recorded all interviews, which means that all data was captured accurately, and the researcher did not have to rely on memory or his own bias. The researcher ensured validity by asking the same questions of all participants and asking additional questions to make sure all answers were clearly understood and were not open to interpretation.

4.5 ANALYSIS TECHNIQUES

This section of the methodology covers how the data generated from the survey and the interviews will be analysed. The first point to note is that the research was sequential, in that the survey was carried out first, which then informed the subsequent interview questioning process.

4.5.1 Quantitative Data Analysis

This study will adopt a quantitative descriptive analysis. The focus of this approach is to understand the most important factors in becoming self-employed, support in starting the business- assistance in writing a business plan, access to external finance, managing business, networking, exhibition, and promotion as a young entrepreneur in Algeria. The analysis of the survey results concentrated on how to weigh the variables for 'Entrepreneurial Intent' and 'Entrepreneurial Readiness' by first examining the structure of the data set.

The first step was to conduct an exploratory analysis of the qualitative data. In this case, the data analysis did indicate that there was an underlying structure to the responses. The second step was then to submit each of the underlying factors for analysis. The analysis also included a set of summary descriptive statistics and crosstabulations for the question set, to demonstrate obvious striations in the data. As such it was possible to confidently assemble a weighted average for Entrepreneurial Readiness and Entrepreneurial Intent. All the statistical testing and analysis were carried on in the SPSS 23 software package. The summary information is supplied in the subsequent results and analysis chapters.

4.5.2 Qualitative Data Analysis

The process of emerging codes and themes is a simple process of reviewing the transcripts for words, phrases, or concepts that appear to be repeated or otherwise prominent across the transcripts and grouping them into themes (Grbich, 2007). However, the critical aspect of thematic analysis is that it is done before the data is compared to existing literature. An alternative analysis approach is to use the literature review to generate a series of existing themes, such as the set of components for a model of entrepreneurship (as presented in Figure 5 below), and then test whether they appear in the data collected in the existing study (Grbich, 2007). However, this is a deductive approach, and this thesis focused on the inductive approach (developing own themes as opposed to testing existing ones).

Another problem with this approach is that it is an open invitation for a confirmation bias and can lead to the researcher looking for a specific result in the data, regardless of other themes emerging in their study (Grbich, 2007). This also means that the researcher has a narrow focus on finding confirmation for existing themes (Glesne, 2015). The thematic analysis offers an independent analysis of the data without the influence of the literature review.

This thesis is exploratory research. Exploratory research exists where the research environment is relatively poorly defined or understood, and part of the rationale for the project is to help to

better define and build a new theory (Creswell, 2013). In this case, Algeria is a relatively poorly understood research environment, even if entrepreneurship is not.

Data were analysed using NVivo(R-1) software. All the transcripts were imported into NVivo as separate files. Braun and Clarke’s (2006) six-step strategy for thematic analysis was used to identify initial codes and themes (familiarization of data, generation of codes, combining codes into themes, reviewing themes, determining the significance of themes, and reporting of findings). The researcher reviewed the answers from all participants and the following seven themes emerged out of 61 initial codes from the dataset. Themes that emerged from the coding included: economic development, youth development, challenges for entrepreneurship, conducive environment for entrepreneurship, changes in rules and laws, initiative to promote entrepreneurship, changes in rules and laws, allocation of resources, monetary benefits, development and training programs by the government to promote personal growth and confidence of entrepreneurs, access to finances for youth entrepreneurship, and problems in making the wealth benefit the population and the country’s development. All the themes and their initial codes are described below:

Theme 1: Importance of youth entrepreneurship to the economic development of Algeria

Theme-2: Situation of present business environment for entrepreneurship to thrive in Algeria

Theme 3: Entrepreneurship as a tool to combat youth unemployment and social exclusion as well as stimulating innovation among young people

Theme-4: Ways of supporting and encouraging by government for youth entrepreneurship in Algeria

Theme-5: Business development and training programs by government for local communities in schools and colleges to promote personal growth and confidence of entrepreneurs

Theme-6: Access to finances for youth entrepreneurship

Theme-7: Problems in making the wealth benefit the population and make the country develop and move forward

4.6 STUDY’S ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

The primary requirement of any academic thesis is that it does not place any participant, inclusive of the researcher, at risk of harm. The simplest way of doing this in a social science project of this nature is to approach the project from the perspective of informed consent for all participants (Walliman, 2017). The crux of the informed consent approach is that everybody involved in the project needs to be able to give their consent to be involved from a position of knowledge and power; they must fully understand the nature of the project and their involvement so that they can decide whether it is appropriate for them to take part (Foster, 2018). This means finding a way to communicate the project and its aims effectively to respondents and ensuring that everyone has the same level of understanding of the research context (Walliman, 2017). Participants in this study were adequately briefed by the researcher about the description of the research, the intended outcomes, how individual contributions would be used, and some notes on data protection, storage, and management of the data

As noted in the description of procuring participants, it was a requirement of all participants’ contributions to be anonymous, inclusive of ensuring that they could not be inadvertently identified by details of their work or some other aspect of their life (Walliman, 2017). It was also made clear to the respondents that they could ask any questions at any time and could

withdraw from the project at any time if that is what they prefer (Walliman, 2017). As a requirement of university ethics possibility, all respondents were asked to give written consent to participate using a template consent document. The consent document is included in Appendix Three of this thesis. The researcher ensured that the respect and dignity of all participants were maintained at all times.

4.7 CONCLUSION

This chapter started with a description of the research objectives of this thesis. The overall research philosophy and design were explicated, noting the challenges of the research process. The chapter also discussed the process of collecting the data, and how that data would be processed. The chapter also commented on the ethics of the interview process.

CHAPTER FIVE

ANALYSIS

This chapter presents the qualitative and quantitative findings from the study. Qualitative data was analysed by using NVivo(R-1) software. All the transcripts were imported into Nvivo as separate files. Braun and Clarke's (2006) strategy for thematic analysis was used to identify initial codes and themes. Overall, seven themes emerged out of 61 initial codes. Themes that emerged after the coding included economic development, youth development, challenges for entrepreneurship, conducive environment for entrepreneurship, changes in rules and laws, initiative to promote entrepreneurship, changes in rules and laws, allocation of resources, monetary benefits, development and training programs by government for local communities in schools and colleges to promote personal growth and confidence of entrepreneurs, access to finances for youth entrepreneurship and problems in making the wealth benefit the population and make the country develop and move forward. All the themes along with their initial codes are described below.

5.1 QUALITATIVE ANALYSIS

5.1.1 Importance of Youth Entrepreneurship to the Economic Development of Algeria

The importance of youth entrepreneurship to the economic development of Algeria is reflected by two themes: economic development and youth development. These themes emerged from the initial code allocation of financial resources, better credentials for better economic development, essential to the increase in employment, helpful in overcoming economic challenges, crucial initiative; focus youth energy toward economic development, the generation gap in the management of the business, and qualified workforce. The government is allocating financial resources to boost youth entrepreneurship for the economic development of Algeria, as one of the respondents pointed out “*There were few initiatives by the government during a specific circumstance like the initiative of 2011 when the government put aside considerable financial resources to help and encourage the entrepreneurs and entrepreneurship (FL).*” As previously discussed, venture capital is a significant barrier for business start-ups in Algeria, and there are many shortages across the country in securing financing (Groh & Wallmeroth, 2016). Those that have been offered were often not designed for boosting entrepreneurial activity in the country, but rather for other purposes (Haugh & Talwar, 2016). At the same time, access to bank finance is rigid, competitive, and limited and often requires entrepreneurs in Algeria to seek alternative finance options (Bakari, 2018). Thus, any governmental financial

initiative can be a significant contributing factor to greater youth entrepreneurial activity in the country, which further contributes to greater economic growth.

Better credentials for better economic development are necessary for the companies to contribute to the economic development in Algeria. As pointed out by one of the participants: *“Most companies and the old generation accepted that they have to let young people lead because most are technology-savvy, better equipped, and connected to the outside world. Therefore, they have better credentials to have a modern knowledgeable management style and leadership to get better economic development results (MZ).”* Algeria is one of the countries experiencing a fast-growing interest in new technology, with many young IT-skilled and technology-endowed entrepreneurs taking the initiative to overcome the technology problems in the country that can potentially lead to a better economic situation (Hoxha, 2015). Thus, youth entrepreneurship is essential to the increase in employment and economic development in Algeria. Youth entrepreneurship is also helpful in overcoming economic challenges in the country as this new wave of youth entrepreneurs can help to build more competitive skills across the country and job creation due to technology and sector growth (Boufeldja, 2017). Many well-educated and open to the outside world young entrepreneurs can face the challenges facing future economic growth and development in Algeria by developing the private sector in the country and fostering economic transition (Kew et al., 2013). Thus, it is important to foster ongoing youth entrepreneurship.

The theme of youth development emerged from the four initial codes including the crucial initiative, focus youth energy toward economic development, the generation gap in the management of the business, and qualified workforce. *“Youth entrepreneurship is a crucial initiative for the development of the economy in Algeria for many reasons (MZ)”* mentioned one of the participants. As previously mentioned, young entrepreneurs can develop competitive skills on the market which can potentially lead to more job creation, a more global mindset, and private sector growth (Kew et al., 2013; Momani, 2017). Thus, it can be argued that if the Algerian government focused on encouraging young people towards economic development, that will secure the future of the next generations to come. The generation gap in the management of the business and qualified workforce is evident in the Algerian economy, as emphasised by a participant *“We have a well-qualified workforce in different industries, but badly used. [In the agriculture sector] the producers do not pay any tax at all. The farmer in Algeria has only a card to show he/she are farmers and that opens a lot of doors to them to gain many facilities to do their economic activity (FL).”* Such economic activity does not

contribute to the healthy growth of the economy in Algeria and has been a common practice for many years in Algeria (Lefèvre, 2017). Thus, investing in youth entrepreneurship can have the additional benefit of ending bad economic practices in the country from previous generations.

Table 5.1: Importance of youth entrepreneurship to the economic development of Algeria

Themes	Initial Codes	Frequency	Representatives' statements
Economic development	Allocation of financial resources	1	There were few initiatives by the government during a specific circumstance like the initiative of 2011 when the government put aside considerable financial resources to help and encourage the entrepreneurs and entrepreneurship (FL).
	Better credentials for better economic development	1	Most companies and the old generation accepted that they have to let young people lead because most are technology savvy, better equipped and connected to the outside world. Therefore, they have better credentials to have a modern knowledgeable management style and leadership to get better economic development results (MZ)
	Essential to the increase in employment	6	Youth entrepreneurship is essential to the increase in employment in Algeria. And also, the numbers of youth, university leavers, and youth finishing training are high in Algeria (MZ)
	Helpful in overcoming economic challenges	1	This new wave of youth entrepreneurs are well educated and open to the outside world and can face the challenges facing future economic growth and development in Algeria (MZ)
Youth development	Crucial initiative	1	Youth entrepreneurship is a crucial initiative for the development of the economy in Algeria for many reasons (MZ)
	Focus youth energy towards economic development	4	So, if we can direct and focus youth energy towards economic development that will secure the future of the next generations. That means we have to start right now looking after the interest of entrepreneurs and youth (MZ)
	Generation gap in management of business	1	It was always the father who starts the company and stays in business until he dies. That caused the problem a few years ago because the new generation couldn't stand the management of their fathers or parents. Because they are from different generation with different approaches to management. The young have new ways of leadership, they have been to university, they are familiar with modern technology (MZ)
	Qualified work force	1	We have well qualified workforce in different industries, but badly used. I give you an example about the agriculture sector. In this sector, the producers do not pay any tax at all. The farmer in Algeria has only a card to show he/she are farmers and that open a lot of doors to them to gain many facilities to do their economic activity (FL)

Note: Developed by Osmani Abderrezak- the researcher

5.1.2 The Situation of Present Business Environment for Entrepreneurship to Thrive in Algeria

The situation of the present business environment for entrepreneurship to thrive in Algeria emerged from two themes that include the challenges for entrepreneurship and the conducive environment for entrepreneurship. The themes are a reflection of the initial codes, which include: entrepreneurs are not happy, a challenging environment, changes and turnover of the

official personnel, encouragement of imports, and the rise of imports of goods. The theme of a conducive environment for entrepreneurship emerged from the initial codes: the creation of new companies, enterprises development with a high level of success, new initiatives by the government, young people understanding the projects and risks, and youth and university students being well informed.

While exploring the challenges faced by the participants, it was discussed that the entrepreneurs are not happy and that Algeria is a very challenging environment for the youth to start a business. As one of the respondents pointed out, “*The business environment in Algeria was not at its best and we saw a lot of contradictions in economic decision making and the ranking of the country in how easy the business is done in our economy was not favorable (YS).*” Indeed, widespread corruption and lack of clear rules of power have limited Algeria in terms of economic growth and development, as its immediate impact was that the international aid and sovereign debt were restricted, which would have otherwise potentially contributed to economic expansion as well as greater foreign investor confidence (Sardar, 2018; Strachan, 2018). Moreover, the frequent changes and turnover of the official personnel is another challenge for youth entrepreneurship as described by the respondent in his words: “*In addition, the many changes and turnover of personnel we saw in the recent years in the government and ministries made the progress process slow. The personnel changes slowed down the investments because of the new texts and approaches that the new ministers and government brought. The new leaders and deciders need to review all of the past decisions and decide if they go with them or have a different approach and direction (MZ).*” Due to the overextended period of power for the Algerian President, there was little hope for the government officials to improve the governance standards and embed anti-corruption laws, which led to many of them leaving their posts (Sardar, 2018). With a lack of future perspective, many officials chose not to continue working for the government, leading many people skeptical of a potential change.

On the other hand, a conducive environment for entrepreneurship has emerged in Algeria, as the government is encouraging more imports in response to the policies, as mentioned by a respondent, “*I try to explain what I experienced and what I visualise. Algeria was subjected to a monopole for international trade. The country politically took the socialist path after the independence. Most of the factors of production belonged to the government. So, most of the business with the outside world was done by the government. After signing the EU convention, there was a certain level of trade liberation, and the country saw a huge rise in imports of goods (FL).*” Imports and exports in Algeria have been largely state-owned for the past 50

years, which contributed to significant tax rises, unemployment, and shortages across the country (Oxford Business Group, 2018). An increase in imports is thus considered a contributor to a more conducive environment for entrepreneurship in Algeria.

Another factor that promotes a conducive environment is youth knowledge and understanding of the entrepreneurship sector. Young entrepreneurs appear to understand what's required for them to succeed, as one of the respondents highlighted: *“They have the minds of entrepreneurs, understand the risks, believe in and understand their projects, and work towards realising their projects. Therefore, when I interact with these young people, I am usually very positive and happy about their understanding of their entrepreneurial journey and what they want to do (MZ).”* Young entrepreneurs are more likely to be prepared for the risks and challenges associated with starting and managing a business and are more likely to engage in risk-taking innovative behaviour that promotes profit and growth (Momani, 2017). Moreover, the youth and university students are well informed about the business opportunities, as quoted by one of the interviewees: *“When I talk to the youth and the university students or graduates, I find that they are up to date and well informed, sometimes better than me, who has been helping and consulting businesses for many years now. When I meet these young people to direct them or give them some advice, I find them well informed about what is going on in their country and Europe, and they are well connected with the new inventions and technological advances (MZ).”* Greater information and knowledge can lead to greater globalisation opportunities for Algeria and increased global trade (Erikson, 2014). Algeria has an opportunity to achieve a more profound economic change as a result of greater technological advances and knowledge in the country, leading to a more interconnected world.

Table 5.2: Situation of present business environment for entrepreneurship to thrive in Algeria

Themes	Initial Codes	Frequency	Representatives' statements
Challenges for the entrepreneurship	Business people are not happy	1	To be honest with you; if we look at the business environment in Algeria, I can say many business people are not happy with the business environment. Because of bureaucracy, time spent in the administration to get the necessary documents like registering their new companies will take weeks of completing forms and waiting for approvals (MZ)
	Challenging environment	2	The business environment in Algeria was not at its best and we saw a lot of contradictions in economic decision making and the ranking of the country in how easy the business is done in our economy was not favorable (YS)
	Changes and turnover of official personal	1	In addition, the many changes and turnover of peroneal we saw in the recent years in the government and ministries made the progress process slow. The personnel changes slowed down the investments because of the new texts and approaches the new ministers and government bring. The new leaders and deciders need to review all past decisions and decide if they go with them or have a different approach and direction (MZ)
	Encourage imports	1	The government at the time created this phenomenon and encouraged imports. As import was very lucrative with the facilities, the government gave to this sector. The products imported from abroad were well-liked and wanted from the consumers in Algeria. And as you know, the Algerian dinar is not convertible; the import was an excellent opportunity for the Algerian import operators to gain some hard currency from the Algerian treasury to pay for their imports. Because imports were very lucrative and the gain was fast, most economic operators focused all their resources on importing goods from abroad (FL)
	Rise in imports of goods	1	I try to explain what I experienced and what I visualise. Algeria was subjected to a monopole for international trade. The country politically took the socialist path after the independence. Most of the factors of production belonged to the government. So, most of the business with the outside world was made by the government. After signing the EU convention, there was a certain level of trade liberation, and the country saw a huge rise in imports of goods (FL)
Conducive environment for entrepreneurship	Creation of new companies	1	Because imports were very lucrative, the businesses operating in the industry sector and production created new companies to import to have access to this lucrative activity, which was more profitable than manufacturing. Some of the businesses in the manufacturing industry stopped manufacturing and switched to imports (FL)

	Enterprise development with high level of success	1	This is an area the new government and new leaders are working very hard to change this situation and create an economic ecosystem as a dynamically stable network of interconnected firms and institutions in the Algerian economy and that helps attract some Foreign direct investments and that helps the development of the market and create more enterprises and entrepreneurial activities with high level of success and resilience (YS)
	New initiatives by the government	1	Now, this new government and during the last two years, things are changing, but it is too soon to evaluate the situation because we are transitioning. It is a total upheaval, a significant change of laws, a new approach, a new governance new vision that are taking place right now. We are experiencing many changes in the country at the moment. I am very optimistic that the decisions taken by policymakers and the government at the moment are more acceptable and transparent. I will be able to discuss the outcome of these new initiatives may be in the next few years (MR)
	Young people understand the projects and risks	1	They have the mind of entrepreneurs, understand the risks, believe and understand their projects, and work towards realising their projects. Therefore, when I interact with these young people, I am usually very positive and happy about their understanding of their entrepreneurial journey and what they want to do (MZ)
	Youth and university students are well-informed	1	When I talk to the youth and the university students or graduates, I find that they are up-to-date and well-informed, sometimes better than me, who has been helping and consulting businesses for many years now. When I meet these young people to direct them or give them some advice, I find them well-informed about what is going on in their country and Europe and they are well-connected with the new inventions and technological advances (MZ)

Note: Developed by Osmani Abderrezak- the researcher

5.1.3 Entrepreneurship as a Tool to Combat Youth Unemployment and Social Exclusion as Well As Stimulating Innovation Among Young People.

Whether or not the Algerian government is using entrepreneurship as a tool to combat youth unemployment and social exclusion as well as stimulating innovation among young people was also discussed with the participants of this study. The Algerian government has been making changes in rules and laws and taking other initiatives to promote more entrepreneurship in the country. For instance, the Algerian government had initiated rules on data protection, laws on promoting e-commerce, and issued new laws and texts as pointed out by one of the participants:

“New laws and texts have been issued and studied to make the business environment favourable for young entrepreneurs to work on their ideas and hope to build a promising future in their country. The Ministry of Start-ups and the Economic Knowledge is led by a very young minister aged 26 years old (YS).” Bureaucratic challenges have been a common obstacle for Algerian entrepreneurs, especially with widespread corruption, informal economy, difficulty in engaging with the authorities, as well as the lack of trust in the authorities (Ghiat, 2018). The participant also added: *“The ministry is working with a high level of transparency to evaluate its work, efficiency, and added value in the coming year or years (YS).”* Before the introduction of laws, many Algerian entrepreneurs opted for conducting unlicensed trade, which in no way contributed to the sector or the economy in Algeria (Benhabib et al., 2014). Moreover, the Algerian government introduced initiatives including the *“financing of new entrepreneurial projects, inclination of youth towards digital and technology business, promotion of technology sector, provision of easy and friendly business environment and transparency to evaluate the works,”* as quoted by one of the participants. All of these are considered to be entrepreneurship enablers for the Algerian youth, to create a more globalised and interconnected economy that can contribute more to the world (Hirst et al., 2015). If successful, these could be significant contributors to combating unemployment and developing the sector.

Table 5.3: Entrepreneurship as a tool to combat youth unemployment and social exclusion as well as stimulating innovation among young people

Themes	Initial Codes	Frequency	Representatives' statements
Changes in rules and laws	Government-initiated rules on data protection	1	The government-initiated rules on data protection to help young entrepreneurs to embrace these technologies (MZ)
	Initiative of policies and laws to promote E-commerce	1	We have to encourage and help young entrepreneurs in the tech sector to progress and advance. Many young start-up initiatives have led the government to initiate policies and laws to promote E-commerce in 2019 (MZ).
	Issuance of new laws and texts by the government	1	New laws and texts have been issued and studied to make the business environment favourable for young entrepreneurs to work on their ideas and hope to build a promising future in their country. The Ministry of Start-ups and the knowledge Economy is led by a very young minister aged 26 years old (YS)
Initiative to promote entrepreneurship	Financing new entrepreneurial projects	1	ANSEJ in 2011 spent big government budgets when there was no medium to long-term strategy to help young people succeed in their business and create new jobs by financing new entrepreneurial projects. The government calmed down the boiling tension of young people who lost hope and faith to build a promising future in their country (FL)
	Government created the Ministry of Start-ups	2	The Algerian start-ups participate in many international fairs. The Algerian government created the ministry of start-ups. The government is showing a lot of importance to these sectors and youth entrepreneurship (MZ)
	Inclination of youth towards digital and technology business	1	The enlargement of the technological and digital sector amongst youth is a determinant factor in the economic transformation. Most youths are now inclined towards digital and technology business; this shows that Algeria will not stay on the side-line of change (MZ)
	Promotion of the technology sector	2	They are not talking about setting up a business for import and export of goods, but about setting up a new application that can be marketed and sold to other firms to use in their business. Technology and business work hand in hand, and it is the present and the future for economic growth in Algeria (MZ).

	Provision of easy and friendly business environment	1	Providing an easy and friendly business environment and access to training, finance, and support will attract many young people to explore the possibilities of creating their businesses, growing their businesses, and employing others to help manage their businesses (MR).
	Transparency to evaluate the works	1	The Ministry of Start-ups and the knowledge Economy is led by a very young minister aged 26 years old. The young people connect well with people from their generation, and the ministry doors are open to entrepreneurs. The ministry is working with a high level of transparency to evaluate its work, efficiency, and added value in the coming year or years (YS)

Note: Developed by Osmani Abderrezak- the researcher

5.1.4 Ways of Supporting and Encouraging Youth Entrepreneurship in Algeria by the Government

The study participants also discussed how the government is supporting and encouraging youth entrepreneurship in Algeria. The government is making changes in rules and laws, allocating resources, and providing different monetary benefits to the youth in its policies. The changes included: changes in regulations and laws, the creation of new agencies and ministries, and a high level of logical and rationalized changes as mentioned by a participant in his interview: *“These changes make sense, and they have a high level of logic and rationality. Whatever was decided recently and during these two years will help the entrepreneurs’ progress and grow their businesses in a much better business environment (MR).”* It was previously discussed that Algeria is a highly centralized state that poses a significant challenge for young entrepreneurs, who often experience issues with obtaining permits, permissions, or licenses for their business activities (Strachan, 2018). Obstacles such as the 49:51 rule meant that Algeria was a challenging environment for any entrepreneurial activity, which previously had an aggregated impact on the overall economic growth of the country (Hacini, 2018). Thus, it is possible that creating a more regulated environment would help Algeria to become more autonomous and less dependent on other economies as part of its economic growth, as described by Escobar (2011) in the dependence theory.

Another strategy used by the Algerian government to promote youth entrepreneurship is to allocate funds. As quoted by the study participant *“On the finance side, the government created a fund dedicated to start-ups and new projects. One characteristic of financing new projects, especially those led by young people, is that when the projects are approved, the government*

guarantees that access to invest in the project will be easier and secure (YS).” Monetary benefits included “the exemption from taxes, free of charge services for entrepreneurs, grants for renting or leasing business premises, interest-free credits and management of credit fund for young entrepreneurs.” As one of the participants pointed out “ANSEJ is the Algerian organisation responsible for managing a credit fund to create businesses for young entrepreneurs under 30 years old. It participates in the public employment service, www.ansej.org.dz (MZ).” In the past, Algeria has been criticised for being a “single-sector economy,” relying on its oil resources to drive the economy, which eventually led to a resource curse (Humpreys et al., 2007). The rentier model by Ray (1998) illustrates this problem, where the country allows foreign companies to extract too much of its resources without receiving adequate income in return. Arguably, using some of its funds to sponsor entrepreneurial activity in the country could be one of the strategies to increase Algeria’s post-oil development and more balanced national income (Harvey, 2005). Better financing and greater accessibility for entrepreneurs can positively contribute to economic development in the country.

Table 5.4: Ways of supporting and encouraging by government for youth entrepreneurship in Algeria

Themes	Initial Codes	Frequency	Representatives' statements
Changes in rules and laws	Changes in regulations and laws	1	We have been waiting for these changes and new regulations and laws to govern the businesses for a long time. The work to clean the business environment and make it favorable for innovators and entrepreneurs has started, and I cannot see it stopping or going back to past days (MR)
	Creation of new agencies and ministry	3	The government in Algeria has created new agencies and implemented new agencies to assist young entrepreneurs. For instance, the ANSEJ agency and the other agency is CNAC, which led to creating the Ministry of Start-ups. ANSEJ and CNAC have the same objectives, but the age group of people they deal with is different (MZ)
	High level of logical and rationalized changes	1	These changes make sense, and they have a high level of logic and rationality. Whatever was decided recently and during these two years will help the entrepreneurs progress and grow their businesses in a much better business environment (MR)
Allocation of resources	Allocation of funds	1	On the finance side, the government created a fund dedicated to start-ups and news projects. One characteristic of financing new projects, especially those led by young people, is that when the assignments are approved, the government guarantees that access to invest in the project will be easier and secure (YS)
Monetary benefits	Exemption from taxes	2	These new enterprises as well are exempt from taxes for five years too. These are some of the incentives to encourage young people to go for entrepreneurship (MZ)
	Free-of-charge services for entrepreneurs	1	These two agencies, ANSEJ and CNAC, have experts to assist and consult and guide young entrepreneurs with their projects, and the service is available free of charge for the entrepreneurs (MZ)
	Grants for renting or leasing business premises	1	The new entrepreneurs can also get a grant from the government to rent or lease a premises for their business, and the grants are not refundable. Usually, the grants are not big enough to cover all the rent, but they help the start-ups (MZ)
	Interest-free credits	1	These two bodies have the same objectives, but they deal with different age groups. They help entrepreneurs get credit from the banks to start their projects. The credit is guaranteed by the government and free of interest. The payback will be due after three years when the business is on its feet and operational (MZ)

	Management of credit fund for young entrepreneurs	2	ANSEJ is the Algerian organisation responsible for managing a credit fund to create businesses for young entrepreneurs under 30 years old. It participates in the public employment service. www.ansej.org.dz (MZ)
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Note: Developed by Osmani Abderrezzak- the researcher

5.1.5 Business Development and Training Programs by Government for Local Communities in Schools and Colleges to Promote Personal Growth and Confidence of Entrepreneurs

Business development and training programs for local communities in schools and colleges provided by the Algerian government to promote personal growth and confidence of entrepreneurs have emerged from the initial codes, which included the development of online courses during Covid, entrepreneurship in vocational education and training, free education at universities, lawyers need the training to draft patents to protect the innovations of the entrepreneurs, training centres with certifications at low fees, well-doing courses for managers and widespread low-cost training programs for the young entrepreneurs.

While discussing entrepreneurship in vocational education and training one of the study participants said, *“The Algerian government supporting entrepreneurship in vocational education and training is increasingly important for the government as they seek to improve pathways to the labour market for youth (YS).”* One of the societal issues in Algeria in the past was the significant inequality in access to education and development opportunities for women, which reduced the level of knowledge and skills possessed by half of the country’s population (Ghiat, 2016). Now in Algeria, education is free, even at university, and both men and women can access it more easily than ever before (Momani, 2017). Now young people can link to the outside world online and travel abroad, which contributes to the conditions for growth in Algeria, as per the model proposed in this thesis. Young people in Algeria can see that they can study for a degree at a local University for free, using reasonable and accessible resources in Algeria.

Moreover, training centres with certifications at low fees are available for the youth as quoted by one of the study respondents *“There are many training centres public and private young people can use to develop their capabilities and the areas they wish to build to create their projects or develop their ongoing projects (YS).”* There are widespread low-cost training programs in Algeria as mentioned by a participant *“The government is offering training widely. Every chamber of commerce in every city in Algeria offers diverse training in different*

industries at a low cost to make it affordable to the broader society (MZ).” Thus, investments in training and vocational programs can help more young people acquire the necessary skills either for the workplace or a business without any societal restrictions (Jebari, 2016). This is something that can significantly help to create the conditions for entrepreneurship, but it will not constitute entrepreneurship without other contributing factors in the Algerian economy.

Table 5.5: Business development and training programs by government for local communities in schools and colleges to promote personal growth and confidence of entrepreneurs

Themes	Initial Codes	Frequency	Representatives' statements
Business development and training programs by government for local communities in schools and colleges to promote personal growth and confidence of entrepreneurs	Development of online courses during Covid	1	Covid 19 developed online courses with the pandemic, especially in cities where the internet network is good (MZ)
	Entrepreneurship in vocational education and training	2	The Algerian government supporting entrepreneurship in vocational education and training is increasingly important for governments as they seek to improve pathways to the labour market for youth (YS)
	Free education at universities	1	Here in Algeria, education is free, even at university. Now young people can link to the outside world online, and now they travel abroad, they can see how expensive education can be in other countries like the UK. Even if the Universities in Algeria are not at the level of Oxford or Cambridge universities and have the same reputation and ranking, young people can see that they can study for a degree at a reasonable University with reasonable resources for free in Algeria (MZ)
	Lawyers need training to draft patents to protect the innovations of entrepreneurs	1	When we talk about training programs unified in the hall country, I have not heard about such a program. But when I spoke of the training, I meant soft skills. Like management skills, ICT, languages, especially the English language, communication, legal advice. We need to train our lawyers to draft patents and give confidence to young entrepreneurs that their innovations are protected (MR)
	Training centers with certifications at low fees	2	There are many training centers public and private young people can use to develop their capabilities and the areas they wish to build to create their projects or develop their ongoing projects (YS)
	Well-doing courses for managers	1	The courses might look basic but are a good start for entrepreneurs. The chambers of commerce started as well doing courses for managers to help them develop their businesses (MZ)
	Widespread low-cost training programs	1	The government is offering training widely. Every chamber of commerce in every city in Algeria offers diverse training in different industries at a low cost to make it affordable to the broader society (MZ)

Note: Developed by Osmani Abderrezak- the researcher

5.1.6 Access to Finance for Youth Entrepreneurship

Access to finances for youth entrepreneurship emerged from the initial codes, which include: the creation of an investment fund, finances in the agriculture sector, focus on the international markets and positive vision, free feasibility study from the government, challenges of getting credit, government priority for easy access of finances, improvement, and modernisation in the

banking system, incentives to the investors, online paperwork facility, quickly available to young entrepreneurs and tax advantages.

The government is creating investment funds to promote youth entrepreneurship as mentioned by a respondent: *“The government created an investment fund called Algeria Start-Up Fund. The fund focuses on financing start-ups to encourage young people to innovate and start their projects and entrepreneurship, in general, to develop new enterprises and ensure future economic growth post-oil and gas (YS).”* Algeria’s economy has been significantly reliant on the oil sector and the minimal annual recoveries in oil prices, which has led to a heavy unbalance and lack of future planning for the post-oil economy (Constable, 2019). Reliance on a single economy can be damaging for the long-term wealth and development of the country, thus introducing investment funds for entrepreneurship can be one way of removing this dependence. However, only some sectors are benefitting from these investment funds, as one of the participants said: *“The plan was not successful in general, but there are a few areas where the outcome was acceptable. The sector which I think did well is the agriculture sector. The government leased to groups of young people land and helped them with finance to do agriculture activities. Now we can see that the production of fruits and vegetables in the country exceeded the local need, and the country is ready to export to the outside world (FL).”* Moreover, as the Algerian government has relied heavily on young entrepreneurs to boost the country's economy, the state has granted young entrepreneurs several tax advantages, which were previously only available to sectors such as agriculture. According to Lewis’ (1954) two-sector surplus model, vast surplus labour from one sector can be turned into industrial development of other sectors in the country, with the right policy. Thus, although relying on a single sector can be considered bad for the economy, it can help to boost other areas of the economy.

The government is taking all these steps to promote youth entrepreneurship. Such as promoting different incentives for the investors and reducing the administrative bureaucracy online, one of the respondents said: *“As a new Ministry, we worked to eradicate all the administration's bureaucracy, and now all interactions of young entrepreneurs are online. There is a website <https://startup.dz/> with all the necessary resources, and the entrepreneurs can communicate and organise all the required paperwork online (YS).”* Currently, in Algeria, it is easier for foreign investors to set up a business venture due to the accessibility to a variety of consultant and registration agents that help to manage the documentation and other processes (Momani,

2017). These services are not usually offered (or financially accessible) to Algerian entrepreneurs, which promotes more foreign entrepreneurial activity in the country, which again leads to greater reliance on external factors. Reducing bureaucratic burdens for young Algerians is the first step in creating a more favourable environment for entrepreneurship.

Table 5.6: Access to finances for youth entrepreneurship

Themes	Initial Codes	Frequency	Representatives' statements
Access to finances for youth entrepreneurship	Creation of investment fund	1	The government created an investment fund called the Algeria Start-Up Fund. The fund focuses on financing start-ups to encourage young people to innovate and start their projects and entrepreneurship, in general, to develop new enterprises and ensure future economic growth post-oil and gas (YS)
	Finances in the agriculture sector	1	The plan was not successful in general, but there are a few areas where the outcome was acceptable. The sector which I think did well is the agriculture sector. The government leased to groups of young people land and helped them with finance to do agriculture activities. Now we can see that the production of fruit vegetables in the country exceeded the local need, and the country is ready to export to the outside world (FL)
	Focus on the international markets and positive vision	1	After the seminar, I spoke to a few young entrepreneurs; I was surprised about their determination to focus on the international markets and their positive vision of not being restricted to the local market only. They were well informed and had good feasibility studies about the market and good statistics and what is needed. Of course, there is a lot of work to be done, but these remarks were very positive for the future of the Algerian economy (MZ)
	Free feasibility study from the government	1	The young entrepreneurs have free feasibility study from the government, free training, free grant to pay for rent or lease of the domicile of the activity, and they have a credit which is refundable in the long term with no interest and cost (MZ)
	Getting credit is a challenging task	2	Suppose the government guarantees credit, the access by entrepreneurs is straightforward. But if not, the bureaucracy and complications of the Algerian financial systems and the Banks make getting credit a challenging task (FL)
	Government priority for easy access to finances	1	The president and prime minister of Algeria always stressed other ministries to make it easy and give easy access to young entrepreneurs to finance and access to banks. Therefore, the finance ministry requested other banks to work closely with young entrepreneurs and make it easy to entertain their requests for finance for their projects (MZ)
	Improvement and modernisation in the banking system	1	The changes will come very soon to the Algerian banking system, and there are many private banks from abroad in Algeria like HSBC, Society General. These banks are operating in Algeria. They are linked to the Algerian central bank and the Ministry of Finance, which means they understood that they need to adjust and adapt to the local banking system in Algeria. These foreign banks will help to improve and modernise the banking system in Algeria (MZ)

Incentives to the investors	1	Furthermore, we are encouraging investors to invest in start-ups through crowdfunding. Therefore, the government gave some incentives to the investors to invest in the projects of the young entrepreneurs (YS)
Online paperwork facility	1	As a new Ministry, we worked to eradicate all the administration's bureaucracy, and now all interactions of young entrepreneurs are online. There is a website https://startup.dz/ with all the necessary resources, and the entrepreneurs can communicate and organise all the required paperwork online (YS)
Quickly available to young entrepreneurs	1	Before the pandemic (COVID-19), finance was quickly available to young entrepreneurs when projects were accepted. So, entrepreneurs who went through ANSEJ and CNAC and government schemes were financed in a short length of time compared to other projects outside these schemes (YS)
Tax advantages	1	The Algerian government has relied heavily on young entrepreneurs to boost the country's economy. So, to promote the development of these start-ups, the state has granted young entrepreneurs several tax advantages (YS)

Note: Developed by Osmani Abderrezzak- the researcher

5.1.7 Problems in Making Wealth Benefit the Population and Make the Country Develop and Move Forward.

The problems in making the wealth benefit the population and make the country develop and move forward emerged from the initial codes, which included: fast and unpredictable changes in legal frameworks of the country, lack of integrated and balanced industry and economy, lack of long-term strategy, limiting foreign investor's stake, no industry to support the entrepreneurs, short-sighted and confused decisions by the central government and socialist path sabotaged the development and progress of industry.

The major problems for the economic development include the fast and unpredictable changes in legal frameworks of the country, as emphasised by one of the participants: *“The international partners have always been concerned about the legal framework in the country and the fast and unpredictable changes in directions from year to another. There is hope in this area as since the beginning of 2020, Algeria has embarked on what is probably the most ambitious reform program of its legal framework to open its market to foreign investors (FL).”* Even if any legal frameworks do exist, such as anti-corruption laws, these are rarely enforced in a way that would meet international standards or enhance the trust of foreign investors (Transparency International, 2018). This means that when coupled with

ambiguity, unpredictability, and lack of accountability, there are little prospects for Algeria to reach economic development long-term. Another problem is the lack of integrated and balanced industry and economy in the country, as highlighted by a participant: *“But with all the goodwill and the government's best intentions, it was evident after a particular time that progress was not happening due to miss management, lack of integrated and balanced industry and economy; these public entities became a burden on the Algerian economy. These public companies were employing a good number of populations, but their balance sheets were on the red all the time, and there was no strategy to restructure these companies to save them and make them productive (FL).”* It can be argued that the Algerian government lacks a long-term strategy, which is limiting the opportunities for foreign investment. Moreover, the Algerian government has no central strategy or policy for youth entrepreneurship, which further makes it harder to reach any entrepreneurial progress in the country (Looney, 2016). The Algerian government fails to deliver on some of the key areas of economic development, such as the rule of law, government effectiveness, or control of corruption.

Other problems include the lack of industry to support the entrepreneurs and the short-sighted and short-term decisions by the central government. As one of the study participants mentioned: *“From my experience in the ministry of the industry and finance and as I spent most of my career in the economic side of the activities of these ministries, I saw and witnessed a lot of efforts and goodwill to improve things and make things work. But I think the problem was more political than economic. All the economic decisions and the economic activities were decided by the central government and the decisions were sometimes short-sighted and confusing, but no one dared to challenge these decisions because of the political environment at the time (FL).”* The Algerian government’s policymaking has been chaotic in the past years, with a history of non-completed policies designed to boost the national economy, without any replacements in place (Oxford Business Group, 2019). This meant that many businesses were impossible to sustain in Algeria, as they required a broader economic infrastructure in the country as opposed to short-term policies (Williams & Horkova, 2013). However, this situation appears to be the case for many developing countries such as Algeria, which inhibits more entrepreneurial activity in the country.

Another inhibition to economic development in the country was its government structure. In Algeria, the socialist path was not a great choice for the development and progress of the industry, as highlighted by another respondent: *“Since Algeria’s independence, 1962, the country pursued the socialist path, and most of the organisations were in public ownership*

until the 1990s. All these entities were managed by administration decrees or decisions made directly by the government and politicians. All these made us forget the quality of the infrastructure, the accreditation, due diligence, and certification. That played a significant role in keeping quality low and hindered the development and progress of the industry (FL).”

Historically, the government of Algeria has been the major source of economic activity for Algerians, which meant that Algerian entrepreneurs were not able to compete in the global market due to too much government control (Held & McGrew, 2007). In other words, Algeria was not able to reach linear economic growth due to the absence of conditions for economic take-off (too much economic control by the government), as one of the key determinants of economic growth from Rostow’s (1960) linear stages of growth model.

Table 5.7: Problems in making the wealth benefit the population and make the country develop and move forward

Themes	Initial Codes	Frequency	Representatives' statements
Problems in making the wealth benefit the population and make the country develop and move forward	Fast and unpredictable changes in legal frameworks of the country	1	The international partners have always been concerned about the legal framework in the country and the fast and unpredictable changes in directions from one year to another. There is a hope in this area as, since the beginning of 2020, Algeria has embarked on what is probably its most ambitious reform program of its legal framework to open its market to foreign investors (FL)
	Lack of integrated and balanced industry and economy	1	But with all the goodwill and the government's best intentions, it was evident after a particular time that progress was not happening due to mismanagement, and lack of integrated and balanced industry and economy; these public entities became a burden on the Algerian economy. These public companies were employing a good number of populations, but their balance sheets were in the red all the time, and there was no strategy to restructure these companies to save them and make them productive (FL)
	Lack of long-term strategy	1	Sonatrach Petroleum Corporation is the company with the main revenue to the Algerian economy, and the government did not have a long-term strategy to build an internal industry around this company. The government's main concern is to keep this company producing by using the highest technology possible. Importing all that the company needs was the primary objective and still until now (FL)
	Limiting foreign investors' stake	2	Since the insurance of the 2020 Finance Law in December 2019 the Algerian authorities have removed most of the restrictions curtailing foreign investment, namely the state's pre-emption right on the transfer of shares by or to foreign shareholders, the prohibition on investors to finance their projects in Algeria with facilities from foreign lenders, and the famous 49/51 rule pursuant to which the capital of Algerian companies must be at least 51% owned by Algerian resident persons or entities, thus limiting foreign investors stake to 49% (the 51/49 rule) (FL)

	No industry to support the entrepreneurs	1	So, when we talk about youth entrepreneurship or entrepreneurship in general in Algeria, how are they going to progress with no industry around them to support their growth? It is challenging, if not impossible, to create enterprises without a reasonable industrial tissue and network to support the start-ups to grow and form a network and distribution channels through the start-ups (FL).
	Short-sighted and confused decisions by the central government	1	From my experience in the Ministry of Industry and Finance and as I spent most of my career in the economic activities and departments of these ministries, I saw and witnessed a lot of efforts and goodwill to improve things and make things work. But I think the problem was more political than economic. All the economic decisions and the economic activities were decided by the central government, and the decisions were sometimes short-sighted and confusing, but no one dared to challenge these decisions because of the political environment at the time (FL)
	Socialist path was not the right choice to the development and progress of industry	1	Since Algeria's independence, in 1962, the country pursued the socialist path, and most of the organisations were in public ownership until the 1990s. All these entities were managed by administration decree or decisions made directly by the government and politicians. All these made us forget the quality of the infrastructure, the accreditation, due diligence, certification. That played a significant role in keeping quality low and hindered the development and progress of the industry (FL)

Note: Developed by Osmani Abderrezak- the researcher

5.2 QUANTITATIVE ANALYSIS

5.2.1 Methods used

This study adopted statistical analysis to address the research objectives. This section will first present the data analysis as well as the demographic profile of the participants. Descriptive statistics are also provided to describe the basic features of the questionnaire items. These items are presented in the graphs.

5.2.2 Results

5.2.2.1 Demographic Profiles

There was a total of four hundred thirty-three (433) respondents who took part in this study. The distribution of the sample was based on the demographic variables of the participants, such as age, gender, level of education, and living abroad, which was summarised in Table 1. Moreover, Figures 1 to 4 show the graphical representation of the demographic profile of the respondents. The results show that there were three hundred (300), or 69.9% 18 to 25 years old among the participants, one hundred and twelve (112), or 25.6% were 26 to 30 years old, and twenty (20), or 4.5% were more than thirty (30) years old. Two hundred and ninety-three (293), or 67.7% were male respondents, and one hundred and forty (140), or 32.3% were female respondents. Moreover, three hundred and nineteen (319), or 73.7% of respondents completed university-level education, ninety-eight (98), or 22.6% of respondents finished high school-level education, and sixteen (16), or 3.8% of respondents had no formal education. Lastly, three hundred and twenty-six (326), or 75.2% of respondents had never lived abroad, and one hundred and seven (107), or 24.8% have lived abroad before. In general, most of the respondents were male, aged 18 to 25 years old, completed university-level education, and did not live abroad.

Table 5.8 Demographic profiles

	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
18-25	301	69.9%
26-30	112	25.6%
Above 30	20	4.5%
Gender		
Female	293	32.3%
Male	140	67.7%
Level of Education		
University Level	319	73.7%
High School Level	98	22.6%
No Formal Education	16	3.8%
Lived Abroad		
Yes	107	24.8%
No	326	75.2%

Figure 5.1. Graphical representation of the respondents according to age

Figure 5.2. Graphical representation of the respondents according to gender

Figure 5.3. Graphical representation of the respondents according to level of education

Figure 5.4. Graphical representation of the respondents according to having experiences abroad

5.2.3 Descriptive Statistics for Perceived Youth Entrepreneurship

Table 2 shows the distribution of respondents who thought about starting a business and becoming self-employed. Moreover, Figure 5 shows the graphical representation of the distribution for starting a business and becoming self-employed. Results showed that the majority of the respondents (410 or 94.7%) thought of starting a business and becoming self-employed. Only twenty three (23) respondents or about 5.3% thought of not engaging in business. As previously noted, Algeria is a country where the highest age group is under 30 years old, which is a prime employment age in the country (Ahmed, 2018). However, 29% of these individuals were reported to be unemployed in 2018 (Ahmed, 2018). More importantly, there has been a recent growth among young Algerians in engaging in online freelancing activities on websites such as Upwork, which somewhat offers them a taste of entrepreneurial activity (Jebari, 2016). Thus, it is unsurprising that such a high score was achieved, considering the high unemployment rate in the country, limited opportunities, and growing enthusiasm for freelancing.

Table 5.9: Distribution for starting a business and becoming self-employed

	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	410	94.7%
No	23	5.3%

Figure 5.5. Graphical representation of the distribution for starting a business and becoming self-employed

Table 3 shows the distribution of respondents based on the reasons that will stop them from starting a business and becoming self-employed. Moreover, Figure 6 shows the graphical representation of the distribution for individuals stopping from starting a business and becoming self-employed. Results showed that most of the respondents (368 or 85.0%) thought of finance as the main reason for stopping them from starting their own business and becoming self-employed. This followed time constraints according to 176 respondents (40.6%), and time consideration according to 36 respondents (8.3%). It was previously noted that young people in Algeria have limited access to information about business and skills as these are not offered by the Algerian government (Groh & Wallmeroth, 2016). Most of the soft skills gained by the youth are typically online through online courses or YouTube videos (Groh & Wallmeroth, 2016). At the same time, there is little evidence to suggest that the loans offered by the Algerian government have any effect on boosting entrepreneurial activity in the country, as there is no actual economic stimulus from the loan package (Bakari, 2018). Thus, these continue to be significant challenges for the young people in Algeria.

Table 5.10: Distribution for stopping from starting a business and becoming self-employed

	Frequency	Percentage
Finance	368	85.0%
Time	36	8.3%
Lack of information and support	176	40.6%

Figure 5.6. Graphical representation of the distribution for stopping from starting a business and becoming self-employed

Table 4 shows the distribution of respondents based on the support they would like to receive for them to start a business and become self-employed. Moreover, Figure 7 shows the graphical representation of the distribution for support in starting a business. Results showed that the majority of the respondents (339 or 78.2%) want to have loans and grants that will help them to start their businesses and become self-employed. This is followed by mentoring and coaching according to 287 respondents (66.2%), and business training courses according to 114 respondents (26.3%). These findings link back to the previous finding, which indicated that the biggest challenges for young people were the lack of information and financing options. Government incentives are one of the driving factors of entrepreneurial readiness as proposed in the current conceptual model, with a potential to drive more youth entrepreneurship. Without access to the right information and mentorship, young entrepreneurs in Algeria are unlikely to be prepared to recognize the right opportunities and react in complex situations (Baron & Ward, 2004). Ultimately, without the right knowledge, it becomes more challenging for inexperienced entrepreneurs to survive in a country like Algeria.

Table 5.11: Distribution of support in starting a business

	Frequency	Percentage
Mentoring and coaching	287	66.2%
Loans and grants	339	78.2%
Business training course	114	26.3%

Figure 5.7. Graphical representation of the distribution for support in starting a business

Table 5 shows the distribution of responses and summary statistics of survey items associated with the perception of the importance of different services. The top three items with the highest mean score were: workshop-networking, exhibition, and promotion events for North African entrepreneurship with a mean of 4.52 and standard deviation of 0.95, assistance with access to external finance with a mean of 4.35 and standard deviation of 1.08, and assistance with specialized mentoring and coaching courses with a mean of 4.16 and standard deviation of 1.22. Overall, the respondents would be extremely likely to avail themselves of the workshop-networking, exhibition, and promotion events for North African entrepreneurship. The respondents would very likely avail themselves of assistance with access to external finance, and specialized mentoring and coaching. Lastly, the respondents will be slightly likely to avail themselves of assistance with managing the business with a mean of 2.46 and standard deviation of 1.22 and writing a business plan with a mean of 2.35 and standard deviation of 1.47. Once again, finance and mentorship were highlighted as important services for young entrepreneurs, on top of more specific soft skills required for running a business. These findings confirm that young entrepreneurs in Algeria need a place or a platform to learn and ask questions, as well as access the appropriate financing to access these options.

Table 5.12: Descriptive statistics for perceived importance of different services

No	Survey item	Distribution of responses (%)*					Summary Statistics	
		NA (1)	SL (2)	ML (3)	VL (4)	EL (5)	Mean	Std. Dev
1	Assistance with writing a business plan	189 (43.6%)	71 (16.5%)	62 (14.3%)	53 (12%)	58 (13.5%)	2.35	1.47
2	Assistance with access to external finance	16 (3.8%)	19 (4.5%)	46 (10.5%)	65 (15%)	287 (66.2%)	4.35	1.08
3	Assistance with specialized mentoring and coaching courses	26 (6%)	26 (6%)	58 (13.5%)	65 (15%)	258 (59.4%)	4.16	1.22

4	Assistance with managing the business	107 (24.8%)	140 (32.3%)	101 (23.3%)	49 (11.3%)	36 (8.3%)	2.46	1.22
5	Workshop-networking, exhibition, and promotion Events for North Africa Entrepreneurship	10 (2.3%)	16 (3.8%)	32 (7.5%)	56 (12.8%)	319 (73.7%)	4.52	0.95

*NA=Not at all likely (1.00-1.49), SL=Slightly Likely(1.50-2.49), ML=Moderate Likely(2.50-3.49), VL=Very Likely(3.50-4.49), EL=Extremely Likely(4.50-5.00)

Table 6 shows the distribution of respondents who have set up their businesses already. Moreover, Figure 8 shows the graphical representation of the distribution for setting up a business. Results showed that most of the respondents (254 or 58.6%) do not have their businesses, while the 179 respondents (41.4%) have established their businesses already. Although this may be true, as previously noted many young people in Algeria actively engage in online freelancing work, thus indicating an entrepreneurial interest (Groh & Wallmeroth, 2016). One of the reasons for choosing this route as opposed to a business is the highly complex and corrupted system in Algeria, which prevents them from setting up a business easily and fairly (Sardar, 2018).

Table 5.13: Distribution for setting up a business

	Frequency	Percentage
With business	179	41.4%
Without business	254	58.6%

Figure 5.8. Graphical representation of the distribution for setting up a business

CHAPTER SIX

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

6.1 INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this chapter is to take the raw data material provided in the previous chapter and set out an analysis of the data in light of the literature review chapter. The chapter sets out two broad sweeps into the data, as they pertain to the wider literature. First, the ‘readiness’ of the young entrepreneurs of Algeria to launch into the world of commerce and entrepreneurship, particularly as it pertains to the distinction between entrepreneurship and business in general. The second sweep picks out an unusual theme in the responses, that is, the respondents have a complex relationship with the state, which influences how they think about entrepreneurship and business, and which requires addressing to determine whether Algeria is ready to develop and adopt a new model of economic development.

6.2 READINESS OF YOUTH

The initial sections of the interview responses seem to make two important points. The first is that there is a certain validity to the idea that in the specific case of Algeria, the youth demographic are the ones that hold the key to economic development and are the ones that have the potential to drive the economy forward. The second point is an extension of this, in that this would seem to provide an initial case that young people could be considered as a predicting factor of entrepreneurship. These findings can add a clear contribution to the literature.

The interview responses indicated a very powerful persuasion towards entrepreneurship in general. A majority of the respondents had either set up a business or were actively considering doing so. One might immediately conclude that this is a group that has a natural predisposition toward entrepreneurship. It should be noted that in Algeria, individuals under 30 years old are the age group most likely to suffer from unemployment, which may translate into their willingness to start a business and “risk it all” (Ahmed, 2018). Many young people tend to turn to business and risk-taking as a way of creating opportunities that would otherwise not exist in their country (Bygrave & Hoffer, 1991). It can be assumed that young people are more willing to engage in entrepreneurial endeavours due to boldness and riskiness, and their answers could be seen to be indicative of that particular age group rather than an overview of the views of Algerian society as a whole.

The respondents offered specific reasons why young entrepreneurs might be particularly useful in driving forward the economic development of Algeria; not just a general disposition to the power and adventure of youth. The core of the argument is that the nature of Algeria’s economic

development to date has left them extremely lopsided in terms of knowledge and capability (Momani, 2017). The respondents note that there is a severe lack of knowledge in the economy on digital tools, and a general lack of knowledge about economic matters that do not pertain to the oil and gas industry.

“The business environment in Algeria was not at its best and we saw a lot of contradictions in economic decision-making and the ranking of the country in how easy the business is done in our economy was not favorable (YS).”

This was manifested through several frustrations about people being in positions of power in the government without the faintest idea about what they were doing, and therefore policy initiatives failing before they even started. Algeria is known for its corruption and lack of accountability in its justice system, which meant that many entrepreneurs and foreign investors in the past did not trust the system to pursue a business there (Strachan, 2018). It is notable that through some of the comments around the short-term approach and swift reversals of government policy, a particular frustration was expressed around the fact that it makes planning and developing a vision much harder and difficult to know what the government will do next. The Algerian government has previously engaged in a lot of short-term decision-making, the biggest one is the lack of a plan for a post-oil economy, which would help to maintain the wealth of the country if the oil reserves run out (Constable, 2019). This finding is important because it illustrates the importance that these young entrepreneurs attach importance to a sense of stability and visibility so that they can then develop their business plans with certainty.

The same point was made around the chaotic nature of the justice system and the banking system in Algeria, such that it not only deters international investors but simply makes it hard for entrepreneurs to maintain their businesses in the medium-to-long term. The premium that these entrepreneurs place on the stability of the business context is hugely important for the development of a model of economic development that will bring long-term prosperity and growth to the country (Lefèvre, 2017). However, in the case of a country like Algeria, there is little to no consideration of the post-oil population and its impact on the Algerian population in the future, let alone generate wealth in the future (Aljazeera, 2019). Moreover, this group of young entrepreneurs appears to be using business planning tools and techniques that they have sourced online from Western countries, which are all predicated on the idea that there is a broadly stable legal, economic, and fiscal context in which the proposed business will operate. What this might indicate is that as this group of people mature, and potentially assume positions

of significance in both public and private spheres, they will transfer this knowledge and contribute it into the country. That could be a very powerful component of the future development of the Algerian economy if it is harnessed properly.

What was particularly interesting was the level of responses that dealt with the calamities of the state and how older generations seemed to largely accept that this would always be the case (Lefèvre, 2017). Arguably, a key distinction between the younger and older people in Algeria is the breadth of their horizons. When the respondents talked about a lack of knowledge and understanding on the part of the older generations what they seemed to be talking about was that they had formed a different set of outlooks on the world because they spent a large amount of their time online, and they led a more globalized life even if they had never physically left Algeria. Rostow (1960) defined this as a “generational shift,” whereby the older generation continued to focus on the subsistent life from the past and the early years of economic development, while the youth tended to concentrate on the novel ways of growing and developing. The outlook and understanding of most aspects of life were striated on these age lines, and largely driven by access to digital resources.

“Most companies and the old generation accepted that they have to let young people lead because most are technology savvy, better equipped, and connected to the outside world. Therefore, they have better credentials to have a modern knowledgeable management style and leadership to get better economic development results (MZ).”

“In addition, the many changes and turnover of personnel we saw in the recent years in the government and ministries made the progress process slow. The personnel changes slowed down the investments because of the new texts and approaches the new ministers and government brought. The new leaders and deciders need to review all past decisions and decide if they go with them or have a different approach and direction (MZ).”

These factors created frustration among the young people due to the failures of the state to provide the kind of economic landscape that they wanted to develop. Unlike older generations, they have some taste of a different world or at least a different way of doing things; they can see and hear what young entrepreneurs around the world are performing in a way that previous generations could not. Rostow (1960) argued that changes in lifestyles between generations help to contribute to economic development, as the youth is more likely to seek change and growth. That means that young people are much more willing to express dissatisfaction with

the status quo; older generations simply accept the calamities of the state as the way that their world has been structured throughout their entire lives. That is not to say that older generations are unaware of the drawbacks of the status quo, but rather that they have a lot less to compare it to. The older generation is less likely to engage in risk-taking behaviour, and ultimately less likely to contribute in any substantial way to Algeria's entrepreneurial sector (Jebari, 2016). The comparisons that younger people make between their situation and that of places like Europe or the US are much more immediate and visceral, and that creates this drive for change.

This is a potentially significant research finding. In the literature review, it was observed that when looking at entrepreneurial models like Drucker's Opportunity Model (as cited in Heller et al., 2000), or the psychological models of decision-making. Lots of factors were considered within the broad body of entrepreneurship, but the age of the entrepreneur is something that is under-researched (unlike gender, race, disability, or sexuality) (Marlow & Patton, 2005; Mirchandani, 1999; Welter, 2011). One might argue that there is an assumption within the literature that all entrepreneurs are young, figuratively speaking. Certainly, in the popular lexicon, entrepreneurship has associations with vigour, speed, and aggressiveness that correlate well with word associations around younger people (Marlow & Patton, 2005). Therefore, one might fashion an argument that the reason age has not been a thoroughly researched topic within entrepreneurship, is not because there is an assumption that all entrepreneurs will operate the same regardless of their age, but rather that all entrepreneurs are young. The evidence in this thesis is not enough to support that contention on its own, but the evidence in this thesis does reveal that there are some complexities around entrepreneurship and age, and past literature has not engaged with those complexities to the degree that it merits.

A key part of this literature was concentrated on the idea that where people typically have negative experiences of entrepreneurship, it seems to be concentrated on people who have the highest academic attainment. It may be argued that some of the frustrations in evidence are partially explained by the socio-economic status of the respondents, and the same responses would not be garnered from a respondent group with a lower level of educational attainment. Individuals who come from lower socioeconomic backgrounds typically live in poverty and sluggish environments, thus their focus is on survival as opposed to advancing the economy of the country (Rarbo, 2009). Specifically, one might reflect on the fact that the idea of broader horizons and dissatisfaction with how Algeria compares to the rest of the world is perhaps a product of a group with a higher level of educational attainment and a more worldly outlook (Oosterom, 2018). The evidence in this thesis is not enough to embark on a detailed analysis of

this point, but it is something that stems from the research design and data collection practices and is a signpost for further research.

Much of the frustrations stem from the unique economic circumstances of Algeria, which include a lack of long-term planning for a post-oil economy, corruption, and economic and political uncertainty. The same frustrations and generational divisions are unlikely to be observable in developed nations around the world, but might be observable in countries with similar economic positions (Isik, 2018). For instance, countries such as Saudi Arabia, Kuwait, and the United Arab Emirates are also heavily oil-dependent economies that face the additional pressure of building economic independence (Al-Sabah, 2017). As a result, it can be argued that some of the same frustrations can be faced by young entrepreneurs in these countries who are faced with a lot of long-term uncertainty.

Both broad arguments that have been made in this section of the chapter gave rise to some reflections on the types of economic modelling that were discussed in the literature review chapter. Drucker's opportunity-based model appears to be slightly challenged by this data because the nature and force of the constraints and opportunities that allow entrepreneurs to come forward seem quite different from what he proposes (Heller et al., 2000). In his model, Drucker argued that entrepreneurship represented a response to a stimulus, through a business venture, where an unemployed person exploited opportunities engendered by social, technological, or cultural changes in the environment (Murphy & Marvel, 2008). Drucker's work seems to share the broad assumption mentioned above that there is a generally functioning legal and political context in which entrepreneurs operate, and the constraints and opportunities are defined with a certain set of bounds (Lenjo, 2015). Although Drucker posited his arguments in quite general terms, where he argued that entrepreneurs identify factors of change and then respond to them, it is difficult to reconcile his general approach with some of the factors of change in Algeria. The participants in this thesis would argue that they are indeed responding to change, but the change they are working at is more immediate and visceral than Drucker's general themes. Moreover, Drucker was not talking about failing states, post-oil economies, and autocracies specifically (Dontigney, 2018). So, while you could not say that Drucker's model is irrelevant to the Algerian context, it simply does not go far enough in terms of dealing with the types of change and stimulus in evidence.

Similarly, most of the other linear models that deal with stages of growth, such as those presented or reviewed by Arrighi (1994), Chenery (1960), Freeman & Soete (1997), Ghatak

(2003), Lewis (1954), Ray (1998) or Rostow (1960) also seem highly unsatisfactory with diagnosing the set of conditions that the Algerian entrepreneurs are subjected to. If anything, the evidence in this thesis suggests that they are dealing with a specific and non-linear context. For instance, there are elements of the resource curse at play, combined with extremely complex facilities of government, identified principally as a set of policies that change at a rapid pace without any overarching logic (Humphreys et al., 2007). Thus, it is unsatisfactory to suggest that Algeria is moving through some form of linear progression of economic development. There are distinct epochs to Algeria's economic progress, but they are unrelated to the linear cycle of growth or any derivative of it.

Overall, if one were to look at the singular case of Algeria, one could conclude that there is a need to categorise young entrepreneurs as part of any conceptual framework as a separate entity. It was previously highlighted that none of the conceptual models of entrepreneurship that were previously discussed identified the age of the entrepreneurs as a particular object of analysis; while other demographic factors such as race, sexuality, or gender have received extensive treatment (Marlow & Patton, 2005; Mirchandani, 1999; Welter, 2011). It is clear from the evidence in this study, that in the case of Algeria, there is a very clear distinction in terms of objectives and thought processes of young entrepreneurs as opposed to the other groups. Their age, more than anything else in the content of Algeria, is more likely to indicate certain facets of their entrepreneurial journey, such as the sectors that they want to enter, what they believe the purpose of entrepreneurship is, and how they achieve their entrepreneurial mission.

6.3 AN AMBIGUOUS RELATIONSHIP WITH THE STATE

One of the most striking elements of the material, when taken as a whole, is the nature of the relationship between the young entrepreneurs and the state. In simple terms, the extent to which they expect the state to be the motor of entrepreneurship and an active if not aggressive contributor to the business sector in Algeria, is remarkable, and brings together a series of cautions about the nature of entrepreneurship in Algeria.

Throughout the responses, the prevailing theme is that these entrepreneurs seem to expect that the state should be responsible for their entrepreneurship and general economic development to take place. This is evidenced in terms of the comments that the participants have made about government policies undermining the rule of law and the independence of the legal systems, the chaotic banking systems, the frequent shifts in policy relating to specific industries, and the seemingly uncoordinated way in which they have sought to create the right conditions for

entrepreneurs to flourish in a post-oil world. Algeria's anti-corruption legislation should theoretically attract more foreign investment into the country, but in practice, corruption is rarely prosecuted among the public sector officials (Transparency International, 2018). This puts into question the reliability and effectiveness of the Algerian government in delivering the appropriate conditions for entrepreneurship to flourish. At the same time, current processes in Algeria for obtaining permits, licenses, or permissions for various business endeavours remain extremely complex and bureaucratic (Ghiat, 2018). Until the Algerian government takes the appropriate steps to eradicate these challenges, the young people will continue to highlight it as a challenge, and their entrepreneurial readiness will remain blocked.

The survey respondents reported the chaos of the state and set out an array of things that they could do better, or things that have gone wrong in the past. According to their answers, nothing appears to happen in the country without the state being involved in some form or other. This is also reflected in the conceptual model of this study, where governmental input is highlighted as one of the key factors driving entrepreneurial readiness among the young people of Algeria. If one goes back to the literature sections on neoliberal economic policy, this makes very little sense; significant if only because the Western world has been on a generally neoliberal trajectory for more than forty years. To a neoliberal theorist, this assumption of a prominent role for the state is anathema. The first principles of the neoliberal approach suggest that markets do better than governments, particularly in terms of allocating resources and creating the conditions for entrepreneurship (Steger & Roy, 2010). Most scholars of the neoliberal approach argue for the smallest state that it is possible to get away with and that the state should do only that which a state requires; it should never overreach into areas that are the province of private and individual enterprise (Steger & Roy, 2010). However, in the case of a country such as Algeria, one cannot expect the government to fulfil these functions, as in the past the government has shown that not to be the case due to corruption and ongoing complexity and bureaucracy (Ghiat, 2016). The obvious critique is that opportunities need to be taken advantage of, and not everybody starts from the same position; in particular, possession of capital means that it is much easier to seize an opportunity. In the case of Algerian, financing is one of the key challenges, as the Algerian government has not been shown to offer any grants or incentives for entrepreneurship (Benhabib et al., 2014). Therefore, neoliberalism tends to entrench existing inequalities, and quite often make them worse, by institutionalising the advantages of those who already have positions of power but who also refuse to use that power to positively contribute to the economy.

This makes for an interesting context to consider the assumptions of the role of the state in Algeria. These entrepreneurs have grown up in a country with an autocratic government that controls very large swathes of life (Lefèvre, 2017). For instance, the Algerian youth have never known a situation where the government is not inserted into everyday life or controlled every aspect of it. For instance, the Algerian government controls over half of all foreign investments entering the country, controls most of the jobs and industries, as well as controls the media (Temlali, 2019). In theory, the government is present in everyone's life as it sets the law and defines lots of aspects of how life is experienced. Thus, most of the young people in Algeria have never experienced a life where most of the goods and services that they consume are provided by private commerce, and where private markets are the predominant means of service delivery. In essence, the most likely route to entrepreneurial success in Algeria is to try and move beyond the control of the state and create opportunities that would otherwise not be provided by the government.

Algeria has been in the process of transition to a free market economy for thirty years now, and therefore there is at least one generation that has never lived under a formal socialist system. That might go some way to explaining the frustrations of the participants with the politics of entrepreneurship in Algeria where the legacy of socialism is continuous and ongoing. The main concept behind entering a free market economy is to leave capitalism unhindered, which would mean that entrepreneurship would have little control from the state (Ghatak, 2003). These markets are considered to be the most likely to achieve rapid economic growth as a result of the efficient allocation of capital, something that is heavily controlled by the state in Algeria (Ghatak, 2003). A combination of the fact that the country does not have a properly functioning political system, in the sense that it has been described very loosely and nonsensically as a managed democracy, combined with a resource curse, appears to have created conditions where people assume that the government needs to be in business in some form (Sardar, 2018). That is not to say that there is no awareness of the economic situation, it is rather that there are a lot of unconscious assumptions about what the economic context is.

“I try to explain what I experienced and what I visualise. Algeria was subjected to a monopole for international trade. The country politically took the socialist path after the independence. Most of the factors of production belonged to the government. So, most of the business with the outside world was done by the government. After signing the EU convention, there was a certain level of trade liberation, and the country saw a huge rise in imports of goods (FL)”

It is a unique situation as there are no other countries in the world that have this unusual combination of factors that lead to a hamstrung economy. However, the central point remains for the model of economic development and entrepreneurship. The central flaw in the responses of the young entrepreneurs is that they are waiting for the state to do something for their entrepreneurship to flourish. This suggests that there is a need for greater education on the theory and conceptual basis of entrepreneurship for young people, which could encourage them to think about, ideate, and address issues that require an entrepreneurial response, and then how to manifest that in the prevailing conditions. In other words, some education should be placed on encouraging young people to create and seize opportunities, as opposed to waiting for political and economic change in Algeria (Temlali, 2019). Arguably, a lot of the entrepreneurial behaviour from the respondents is quite stunted; there is a debate to be had as to whether they are businesspeople or entrepreneurs (Pluzhnik et al., 2018). It should be noted that not all businesspeople are entrepreneurs, even if all entrepreneurs are businesspeople. For one to be considered an entrepreneur, there has to be an intent to “think outside the box,” and identify and capture opportunities that simply setting up a business would not achieve (Temlali, 2019). This has significant implications for any future model of economic development in Algeria, particularly where it is considered that entrepreneurs may be at the vanguard of change (Pluzhnik et al., 2018). The importance of this becomes clear in the following quote:

“The government is offering training widely. Every chamber of commerce in every city in Algeria offers diverse training in different industries at a low cost to make it affordable to the broader society (MZ)”

This is supported by the comments from other respondents who argue that university education is cheap or even free, and they see this generally as a positive thing. But the obvious extension of this is to consider what exactly is being offered in these training sessions, which could help young people to reach the appropriate skills and knowledge for an entrepreneur. As it stands, many young people have previously reported learning their soft skills through online platforms as opposed to government-sponsored programs (Momani, 2017). There is some doubt as to whether Algerian chambers of commerce and universities have the required knowledge to design training that is appropriate for entrepreneurs. There is no history of entrepreneurship as either an academic pursuit or practical reality in Algeria, so it is difficult to see where the right course materials or skills would come from (Momani, 2017). Two of the key research objectives of this thesis were to assess the barriers to youth entrepreneurship and to consider the tools that might promote youth entrepreneurship in Algeria, as well as to evaluate

government actions. The evidence in this thesis raises questions about the support available for young entrepreneurs in Algeria, one of which is that the state may not be well-positioned to provide the necessary training, development, and support for a thriving culture of entrepreneurship due to bureaucratic obstacles and ongoing corruption in the country (Sardar, 2018). Therefore, it was surprising to learn that the respondents in this study did not cite the private sector as a potential source of training and support for entrepreneurs and instead overly focused on the government. This raises the importance of government support and government incentives as some of the key drivers for entrepreneurial readiness in Algeria, which was discussed in the conceptual model of this thesis.

There are several issues with relying on the government to provide training and support for entrepreneurship. The main objective of the government is to promote private business and a market economy, not entrepreneurship as a separate driver for the economy. However, the support from the government is more likely to be from the businesspeople as opposed to the entrepreneurs, who are more likely to find a way around the governmental shortcomings (Djennadi, 2006). Entrepreneurship manifests itself through access to different networks, which allows individuals to access various opportunities otherwise inaccessible to most, as well as gain favourable treatment in most interactions with the system (Jacob, 2019). Thus, it is worth considering what might be different for entrepreneurs compared to regular businesspeople. In this respect, the interviews in this study indicated that the lack of legal stability is a critical issue for entrepreneurs in Algeria more than business in general because it is the single largest barrier to attracting overseas investment. Moreover, the legal system is chaotic, it offers no real protection for people with money in Algerian banks, and no protection for shareholders and other stakeholders in Algerian businesses (Momani, 2017). This makes it harder for entrepreneurs to identify the right opportunities and favourably interact with the government. This also means that it is very difficult to develop a culture of venture capitalism and private investment beyond the arms of the Algerian state.

Some caution is required before characterising that as a single step that would unlock entrepreneurship in Algeria. It is a complicated and likely lengthy process, which might require external support, and it would certainly require time before any new legal system has won the credibility and trust of international investors (Groh & Wallmeroth, 2016). The content of the interviews suggested that the respondents had some good ideas on how to bring in more entrepreneurial activity in the country, but there are missing elements in terms of their capabilities to generate business plans and systematically execute them. This is entirely to be

expected given the content of the literature review on Algerian entrepreneurship to date; various schemes have been started and abandoned to try and promote entrepreneurship (Bakari, 2018; Sardar, 2018). Thus, developing a culture of venture capitalism and private investment in Algeria is a long-term plan, which will likely take a long time to manifest.

Therefore, as part of the general research objective of considering the types of economic development that would be most suited to Algeria, and to propose a conceptual model that captures all of the points discussed above, there is a need to tie together several of these points. The respondents noted that the chaotic nature of the government is bad for business. Arguably, they have drawn the wrong conclusion here, or perhaps only half of the available conclusion. The main problem with the chaotic policies and practices of the government is that it results in a climate that means that international investors and businesses are deterred; in turn, this means that young entrepreneurs have no reservoir of capital, skills, and training opportunities to develop their entrepreneurial capabilities (Pluzhnik et al., 2018; Ramona–Diana, 2017). There is, in effect, a reciprocal loop between the fact that the state ends up deterring international business, which in turn leaves young Algerian entrepreneurs with no other source of support but the state (Ramona-Diana, 2017). That is the loop that needs to be broken for the Algerian entrepreneurship sector to thrive, and for Algeria to move into economic development that will lead it to a prosperous post-oil future.

This is particularly interesting to consider when placed in the broad context of the models of economic development discussed in the literature review chapter. Although the paragraphs above indicate that the neoliberal model is the one that would be the most challenged by the nature of these findings, in that these entrepreneurs see a prominent role for the state in the development of their businesses. In truth, arguably all the models of economic development discussed in the literature review have a basic understanding that commerce and the state are separate things; that the state can support commerce, but it is not something that it can do itself, even in the case of the most basic forms of mercantilism. When looking at the variations in the linear stages of the growth approach, there is an essential component which is the motor of the changes in the deployment of private capital in an economic situation, to generate a return.

6.4 RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

6.4.1 Research Objective One

To assess the general economic and youth unemployment situation in Algeria, including its socio-economic impact.

There is no doubt from the evidence provided by the respondents that Algeria is suffering from a significant lack of opportunities and consistency in economic growth, which affects disproportionately the younger age groups, as they have less access to opportunities and lifestyles of younger people around the world, which can create more frustrations. This is amplified by what they see as the avoidable errors of the government; patronage, incompetence, and corruption, which also means that international investors are reluctant to invest in the country and thus grow the economy. Therefore, they can see that there is huge potential for the Algerian economy, and they tend to know lots of other young people who want to launch their businesses, so they can see the gap between what people want to do, and what is happening. Given that the worldwide economy is facing a challenging and uncertain future, as a result of rampant inflation, price controls in the energy markets, and the threat of recession everywhere, there is no time to lose in developing economic independence and resilience, through a powerful entrepreneurial culture.

6.4.2 Research Objective Two

To identify and discuss the barriers to youth entrepreneurship/business start-ups.

The barriers to youth entrepreneurship and business can be thought of in two distinct tranches. The first tranche is those that have already been identified in the literature review, and concern the difficulty in establishing a private enterprise, and the lack of a reliable legal and banking system, which puts off international investors, and leaves the market without capital. All these factors are a barrier to young people, and they are amplified by the chaotic nature of the government and the unclear policies. These structural barriers mean that it is very difficult to establish and sustain a business in Algeria.

These structural barriers have also given rise to what might be termed psychological barriers. Young entrepreneurs have spent so long living in a country where the state controls everything, that they spend most of their life waiting for the state to start their own business. Moreover, the lack of international investors in the country means that they do not know any better or have anything to compare their situation with, so they are missing a key part of the entrepreneurial process, which is how to get started.

6.4.3 Research Objective Three

To evaluate the overall impact of government actions and programs on youth entrepreneurship

In general, thus far, the Algerian government's actions have been chaotic and have further alienated businesses and international investors. However, there are signs of a positive change; the feedback from the participants in this thesis suggests that there has been an appointment of a key ministry and that several programmes have been well received by the entrepreneurial community, which is giving the respondents the confidence that things are improving in Algeria. Whether these are solid foundations on which to build the future of the economy is yet unclear, but it offers help for the future. Of critical importance is that even a few small success stories can start to deal with that psychological barrier of passively waiting for the state to create a change in the country.

6.4.4 Research Objective Four

To identify key prescriptions for the sustainability of development initiatives for youth entrepreneurship.

The evidence from this thesis suggests that consistency is the thing that is lacking across all government programmes. Some programmes have gone well, some have not, and some have never actually gotten off the ground, but the key issue is that young entrepreneurs never know which programme will be the one to succeed. The programmes that have done well in the country did not do so due to careful planning and judgement. Frequent changes in ministers and policies underline the sense of chaos in Algeria. Therefore, rather than focusing on any individual programme or a sector, what needs to happen is the development of a long-term vision for entrepreneurship that is delivered consistently and carefully over time, so that young entrepreneurs can have the time and space to develop and learn their trade.

6.5 KEY CONTRIBUTION

There are several theoretical and practical contributions to this research. First, as previously stated, this study has addressed a gap in the young population of entrepreneurs in Algeria. Young people are not typically studied in the subject of entrepreneurship, and Algeria is not commonly studied in terms of its entrepreneurs. This research study addressed this gap and opened an avenue for future researchers to build on. Moreover, this study adopted a unique and focused approach to the role of economic resilience, politics, and the importance of post-oil economy in the context of youth entrepreneurship. As this subject began to be explored in the

context of Algeria, more research can be done to explore the economies of other developing countries. This study offered an opportunity for future researchers to explore the need for other economies and more entrepreneurship in their own countries.

This study also offered practical contributions. Government officials can use findings from this study to develop better-informed policies for promoting entrepreneurship in the country. As entrepreneurship is an important factor for Algerian officials who are trying to move away from the oil economy dependency, information about required resources and constraints would help policymakers tailor their policies to help young people start their businesses. Moreover, policymakers and other authoritative figures in Algeria can use the knowledge from this study to focus on other economies for the country that eventually shift away from relying on the oil economy alone. This study also helped to start a potential social change in Algeria, where a new perspective can be developed to encourage the government to prioritize young people in its economic development. Moreover, a potential shift within the society could occur where more young people will feel understood, and their needs will be addressed. It is hoped that managers and other existing leaders start to encourage young people to actively take part in learning and developing their skills, something that moves away from the existing public sector-heavy employment, and instead focuses on improving their entrepreneurial skills, something that can benefit the country in the long-term. As a result, more of them would start business ventures in the country and become less dependent on the government for work.

6.6 LIMITATION AND FUTURE RESEARCH

One needs to advance a note of caution in the arguments in this chapter. A clear majority of the respondents in this study were educated at the university level, which is not typical of the Algerian population as a whole. For instance, only 52% of the overall population attends university (Rarrbo, 2009). Furthermore, the university population in Algeria is two-thirds female to one-third male, and the respondent group in this study was almost three-quarters male (Lefèvre, 2017). So, the respondent group is quite different from the overall population of Algeria, but generally aligned with the population of entrepreneurs around the world. Entrepreneurship remains generally a male pursuit.

Another limitation of this study is the available pool of respondents. The goal of choosing the sample is to ensure that it is a reliable reflection of the population that is under investigation. In this case, the limitations are of purposive sampling; the researcher has to work with what is available to him, rather than what would be the best fit for the study. In this case, the analysis

noted some issues within the respondent group that suggest that they may not be representative of Algerian young people, given that they have a higher degree of academic attainment than average; therefore, the results need to be approached with a little caution.

This study only focused on a small aspect of youth entrepreneurship, but more remains to be explored. This study only focused on interviewing a small and carefully selected sample of young Algerians, which does not paint the picture of the country as a whole and does not accurately represent the country's entrepreneurial activity, nor its actual benefits. It would be beneficial to continue to explore this subject with future studies, where Algerian youth entrepreneurship is explored, and monitored, and its impact measured. However, this cannot be achieved with only one study.

Therefore, recommendations for future research would be to adopt a more representative sample of the Algerian population and explore their requirements for starting a business, as well as reasons for not pursuing it. The goal for future research would be to adopt more females, younger and older populations, and those who did not complete the university. Moreover, future researchers could adopt a single-method approach, such as conducting only interviews or a national survey, which could then build on the existing findings from this study. As previously mentioned, this study opened the doors of interest for more future researchers, who wish to explore their economies in the context of entrepreneurship. This study helped to highlight the potential benefits of youth entrepreneurship in Algeria, but more remains to be explored to determine its benefits in practice long-term. Other researchers with other challenging or dependent economies can wish to adopt a similar approach and explore how entrepreneurship among young people can be used as an avenue to improve the economy.

6.7 SUMMARY

To conclude the analysis of the findings, it is perhaps worth stating that the Algerian situation is unique. One of the most powerful contributions of this thesis is highlighting the evidence of how that unique economic and political landscape is manifested in the ways that entrepreneurs work. Young entrepreneurs in Algeria have a strong desire to pursue their business ventures. While this chapter has noted several potential skews arising from the demographic makeup of the respondents, it is appropriate to record that the respondent group reflects a tremendous amount of positivity and desire toward entrepreneurship and that could only be understood as a positive thing for the future of Algeria.

However, this positivity is tempered by the fact that the unique economic situation of Algeria has prevented this energy from finding an outlet. The transition from socialism into a constricted form of market economy dominated by a resource curse with a lack of democratic accountability and security has meant that the kind of start-up scene with technology companies and a culture of venture capital finance has not developed. The core outcome of that is that networks of practice, experience, and support that entrepreneurs need do not yet exist in Algeria. The state has stepped in as a source of training and development, but it is not clear that the young people have the right kind of knowledge and experience that would enable them to successfully set up and run a business.

Ultimately, it could be argued that the solution to these problems is political rather than economical. Unless there is a breaking of the loop that causes excessive dependence on the state, then there is no way to properly seize the energy and desire of these young entrepreneurs. In tandem, it becomes difficult to postulate a new model of economic development without that revision in the role of the state; the training and development that it is providing is unlikely to lead to a sustained change in economic activity or the development of a thriving culture of entrepreneurship unless the current situation in Algeria is changed.

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APPENDICES

Appendix.1: Participants Information Sheet (PIS)

**University of the West of Scotland
School of Business and Creative Industries**

A STUDY OF THE PROSPECTS IN THE YOUTH ENTREPRENEURSHIP SECTOR IN ALGERIA

Abderrezzak Osmani

Dear Sir or Madam,

I want to invite you to take part in a research study. Please understand why the research is being done and what it would involve for you. Please take time to read the information below carefully. Ask questions if anything you read is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether or not to take part.

WHO I AM AND WHAT THIS STUDY IS ABOUT?

My name is Abderrezzak Osmani; I am a Full-time Doctor of Business student at the University of the West of Scotland. My PhD research addresses the key question: What can be done to engage the youth in small business entrepreneurship across Algeria and thus implement a sustainable solution to the country's unemployment problem?

This study provides an examination of entrepreneurship within an Algerian context. It focuses on youth engagement, employment, the motivations and experiences of young people in the Algerian economy. It seeks to establish the core barriers to entrepreneurship in Algeria, whatever the age. It also examines Algeria's different economic forces that appear to be promoting or sustaining entrepreneurship, particularly in young people. This study also intends to examine how the forces that promote youth entrepreneurship are connected to a broader possibility of economic development and how analysis is required that demonstrates the potential upsides of promoting youth entrepreneurship.

WHAT WILL TAKING PART INVOLVE?

Taking part in the research involves participant to take part in a Semi-structured interview with open-ended questions, allowing for a discussion with the interviewee rather than a straightforward question and answer format. The participant is asked questions regarding what the government is doing to encourage youth entrepreneurship in Algeria to secure economic growth.

Q1. How important is youth entrepreneurship to the economic development of Algeria?

Q2. Is the present business environment favourable for entrepreneurship to thrive in Algeria?

Q3. Is youth entrepreneurship high on Algeria political agenda as a tool to combat youth unemployment and social exclusion and stimulate innovation among young people?

Q4. How is the government supporting and encouraging youth entrepreneurship in Algeria?

Q5. Does the government have business development and training programmes for local communities in schools and colleges to promote entrepreneurs' personal growth and confidence?

Q6. Are finances easy to access by youth entrepreneurship?

The participant is informed that he/she is free to stop the interview at any time. The interviews will take place in public places away from each respondent's work premises as part of an effort to reassure them that the project held a negligible risk for them.

This interview will be audio-recorded and will take approximately 30-40 minutes.

WHY HAVE YOU BEEN INVITED TO TAKE PART?

You are invited to participate in the research because your institution has a high level of involvement in developing and encouraging, and assisting entrepreneurship in Algeria. Your participation is entirely voluntary, and you have the right to refuse to take part in this research, refuse any question and withdraw at any time without any consequence whatsoever.

HOW WILL INFORMATION YOU PROVIDE BE RECORDED, STORED AND PROTECTED?

I store the data in the One drive of my UWS account. The access to the information will be with a strong authentication method or second step of identity verification, such as my fingerprint, face recognition, PIN, or a code sent to me via email or SMS. The University network and OneDrive provide warranted security for the storage of confidential information. Data can be transferred to the University network via VPN, an encrypted channel and can be safely moved between devices. Storing the data in my UWS OneDrive account will give oversight of the data to the UWS controller.

WHAT ARE THE POSSIBLE RISKS AND BENEFITS OF TAKING PART?

The Algerian economy has been relying on hydrocarbon revenues for the last 50 years. The natural resources the country has are finite. The study is looking to identify a key prescription for the sustainability of development initiatives on youth entrepreneurship and the overall development of the Algerian economy, particularly in the post-oil landscape.

The research does not have any risks to the participants.

The interviews will take place in public places away from the work premises of each respondent. When recording the study's interviews, the researcher will use participants codes to label data instead of using names, and he will keep a separate list of code-to-name match-ups. The researcher will make sure not to publish enough information that the participants can be identified. Access to the information needs robust authentication methods such as my fingerprint, PIN or code via email or SMS.

The participants' contributions will be anonymous. The participants are assured that they could not be identified by details of their work or other aspects of their life in the interviews.

WHAT WILL HAPPEN TO THE RESULTS OF THE STUDY?

My research results and findings will consist of submitting my dissertation.

I intend to publish project findings in national and international journals and publications.

I will be happy with the research and the models presented in the study to be included for teaching use.

I will use the research for presentations at national and international conferences and meetings of professional associations.

If you have any queries, please do not hesitate to contact my supervisory team:

Director of Studies: Dr Ahmed Beloucif

Supervisor: Dr Alan Murray

I will be happy to send you the final work if you are interested. Thank you for your time and your contribution.

PhD student Abderrezzak Osmani

Appendix 2: Interview Guide for Policy-Makers

Introduction

Thank you for agreeing to take part in this interview.

My name is Abderrezzak Osmani, and I am a researcher from the University of the West of Scotland **UWS**. I am conducting research on-**The Prospects in The Entrepreneurship Sector in Algeria**.

I am now going to ask you some questions regarding what the government is doing to encourage youth entrepreneurship in Algeria to secure economic growth.

You are free to stop the interview at any time.

This interview will be audio-recorded and will take approximately 30-40 minutes.

Thank you in advance for your time.

Q1. How important is youth entrepreneurship to economic development of Algeria?

Q2. Is the present business environment favourable for entrepreneurship to thrive in Algeria?

Q3. Is youth entrepreneurship high on Algeria political agenda as a tool to combat youth unemployment and social exclusion as well as stimulating innovation among young people?

Q4. How is the government supporting and encouraging youth entrepreneurship in Algeria?

Q5. Does the government has business development and training programmes for local communities in schools and colleges to promote personal growth and confidence of entrepreneurs?

Q6. Are finances easy to access by youth entrepreneurship?

In conclusion, is there anything else we haven't discussed that you wish we had?

I will be analysing the information and others gave me. I will be happy to send you the work if you are interested.

Thank you for your time.

Appendix 3: CONSENT FORM

A STUDY OF THE PROSPECTS IN THE YOUTH ENTREPRENEURSHIP SECTOR IN ALGERIA

Abderrezzak Osmani , PhD Student

Contact details email: [REDACTED] [REDACTED]

Please initial box

1. I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet for the above study and have had the opportunity to ask questions.
2. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time, without giving reason.
3. I agree to take part in the above study.

Please initial box

- | | Yes | No |
|--|--------------------------|--------------------------|
| 4. I understand that the interview will be audio-recorded and I agree to the interview being audio recorded | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| 5. I agree to the use of anonymised quotes in publications | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| 6. I agree that an anonymised data set, gathered for this study may be stored in a specialist data centre/repository relevant to this subject area for future research | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |

Name of Participant	Date	Signature
.....
.....

Name of Researcher	Date	Signature
<i>Abderrezzak Osmani</i>

Appendix 4: Questionnaire for Youth Entrepreneurship

Gender Male Female

Age group 18-25 26-30 30+

1- Have you ever thought about starting a business and becoming self-employed?
 Yes No

2- What stops you from starting your own business and becoming self-employed?

- Finance
- Time
- Lack of information and support

3- What support would you like to receive in order to start your own business?

- Mentoring & Coaching
- Loans & Grants
- Business training course
- Others, please specify..... ..
-

4- In order to address your needs, how important is it for you to use the following services?

1= Not at all likely 2=Slightly Likely 3=Moderately Likely 4= Very Likely 5=Extremely likely

4.1- Assistance with writing a business plan

	1	2	3	4	5	
Not at all likely	<input type="checkbox"/>	Extremely likely				

4.2- Assistance with access to external finance

	1	2	3	4	5	
Not at all likely	<input type="checkbox"/>	Extremely likely				

4.3- Assistance with specialised mentoring & coaching courses

	1	2	3	4	5	
Not at all likely	<input type="checkbox"/>	Extremely likely				

4.4- Assistance with managing the business

	1	2	3	4	5	
Not at all likely	<input type="checkbox"/>	Extremely likely				

4.5- Workshop-networking, exhibition and promotion Events for North Africa Entrepreneurship

	1	2	3	4	5	
Not at all likely	<input type="checkbox"/>	Extremely likely				

5- Have you set up a business already? Yes No

6- Sector of the business -----

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